

**TIME SERIES FORECASTING USING THE BOX-JENKINS METHODOLOGY FOR
THE PROJECTION OF THE JAKARTA STOCK EXCHANGE COMPOSITE INDEX**

Undergraduate Thesis

Submitted in Fulfillment of the Requirements to Obtain a Bachelor's Degree

Thesis Supervisor:

Poppy Ismalina, M.Ec.Dev., Ph.D.

Approved 10 Jan 2024

Poppy Ismalina

Written By:

Stevan Harris Budiman

18/429250/EK/22010

**INTERNATIONAL UNDERGRADUATE PROGRAM
DEPARTMENT OF ECONOMICS
FACULTY OF ECONOMICS AND BUSINESS
UNIVERSITAS GADJAH MADA YOGYAKARTA
2024**

UNIVERSITAS GADJAH MADA
FAKULTAS EKONOMIKA DAN BISNIS

Dengan ini saya menyatakan bahwa tugas akhir dengan judul:

***Time Series Forecasting Using the Box-Jenkins Methodology for the
Projection of the Jakarta Stock Exchange Composite Index***

Disusun oleh
Stevan Harris Budiman
18/429250/EK/22010

Telah saya baca dengan seksama dan telah dinyatakan memenuhi standar ilmiah, baik
jangkauan maupun kualitasnya, sebagai skripsi jenjang Pendidikan Sarjana (S1).

Telah diujikan pada 20 Februari 2024

Tim Penguji	Nama Lengkap	Tanda Tangan
Pembimbing	Poppy Ismalina, M.Ec.Dev., Ph.D. NIP 197201271997022001	
Penguji 1	Gigih Fitrianto, S.E., M.Sc., Ph.D. NIKA 111199203202102101	
Penguji 2	Esa Azali Asyahid, S.E., M.Sc. NIKA 99100408	

Mengetahui,
Wakil Dekan Bidang Akademik dan Kemahasiswaan

Bayu Sutikno, S.E., M.S.M., Ph.D.
NIP 197805202005011002

DECLARATION OF ORIGINALITY

I, the undersigned below:

Name : Stevan Harris Budiman
NIM : 18/429250/EK/22010
Year Registered : 2018
Study Program : Economics
Faculty : Faculty of Economics and Business

Declare that in this Thesis scientific document there are no parts of other scientific works that have been submitted to obtain an academic degree at a Higher Education Institution and there are also no works or opinions that have been written or published by other people or institutions, except those that are cited in writing of this document with the sources stated in full in the bibliography.

Thus, I declare that this Thesis scientific document is free from elements of plagiarism and if proven to be plagiarized from the work of another author and/or deliberately submitted work or opinions which are the work of another author, then the author is willing to receive applicable academic and/or legal sanctions.

Yogyakarta, March 8th 2024

Stevan Harris Budiman
18/429250/EK/22010

PREFACE

I praise to Allah SWT that without His blessings, direction, and grace I could not have possibly finished this thesis. This thesis titled “**Time Series Forecasting using the Box-Jenkins Methodology for the Projection of the Jakarta Stock Exchange Composite Index**” is written as fulfilment of the requirements to obtain the degree of “Bachelor of Economics” from International Undergraduate Program of Economics, Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Gadjah Mada. It is completed with much effort and guidance from my thesis supervisor along with countless support from my family and friends. I would like to address my gratitude to the following people:

1. Prof. Dr. Didi Achjari, S.E., M.Com., Ak., CA. as the Dean of FEB UGM.
2. Bayu Sutikno, S.E., M.S.M., Ph.D. as Deputy Dean of Academic and Student Affairs of FEB UGM.
3. Suyanto, S.E., M.B.A., Ph.D. as Deputy Dean of Finance, Assets, and Human Resources of FEB UGM.
4. Gumilang Aryo Sahadewo, S.E., M.A., Ph.D. as Deputy Dean of Research, Community Service, Cooperation and Alumni of FEB UGM.
5. Rimawan Pradipto, S.E., M.Sc., Ph.D. as Head of Economics Department of FEB UGM.
6. Eny Sulistyaningrum, S.E., M.A., Ph.D. as Secretary of Economics Department of FEB UGM.
7. Sekar Utami Setiastuti, S.E., M.Sc., Ph.D. as Head of Economics Study Program of FEB UGM.
8. Poppy Ismalina, M.Ec.Dev., Ph.D. as my thesis supervisor who always guides and supports me on writing this thesis.
9. Gigih Fitrianto, S.E., M.Sc., Ph.D. and Esa Azali Asyahid, S.E., M.Sc. as my thesis examiners.

10. My beloved family, my one and only mama Risdianti Sari, my papa Almarhum Teddy Chandra, my abi Usep, my handsome brother Louis Budiman, my beautiful sister Angely Oktavia Budiman, my lovely little sister Keisha Odellia Ramadhani, and my grandmother Mardiah, who will always be the reasons I keep on going on and doing my best.
11. My lifelong friends who I take as my own brothers, Arfan Madjid Almaghribi, Dwiki Satria, Dwi Langgeng Nur Cahyo, Edgar Raihan Ananto, Gilang Pradana, Jimmy Echlesia Permata, Mahmud Said Ramadhan, Rosyid Nur Salam, Ryvaldo Okta Fahlevi, Fahman Nur Rahman, Fahim Nur Rahim, Farid Kurniawan, and Satria Akbar Mahardika.
12. All my friends in Economics FEB UGM Batch 2018 who I look up to and matter a great deal to me, Dzaki Gumilang Nurrachmat Trimulyono, Aryo Wibianto Purwanto, Ryan Muhammad Hanif Nugraha, Gading Muhammad Damarjati, Severino Abimanyu Suryolaksono, Vinsensa Vitalonga, Mutiara Helga Indira, Marchia Audrey, Pascal Nathanael, Juan Claudeo, Kezia Aquileta, Syarifuddin, Muhammad Faiz Zaidan Alharkan, Data Avicenna, Aldika Prihantara, Yusril Sabilla Ashar, Widhias Setyo Jati, and many others.
13. All lecturers of FEB UGM who have given me so much valuable knowledge.
14. All academic staffs of FEB UGM who always work and assist me efficiently.
15. A special one in my life who was always there with me through the good and the bad times, this is to you, Siti Nuraeni Putri, wherever you are in life, I wish happiness, success, love, and health are always with you in every step of your path. You deserve all the best things that life can give.

I hope this thesis can be helpful to all readers and contribute an analytical procedure of time series forecasting for an economic variable, specifically for the prices of the Jakarta Stock Exchange Composite Index.

Yogyakarta, March 8th 2024

Stevan Harris Budiman
Stevanharris@mail.ugm.ac.id

TABLE OF CONTENTS

PREFACE	iii
TABLE OF CONTENTS	v
LIST OF TABLES	vii
LIST OF FIGURES	ix
LIST OF APPENDICES	x
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	xi
INTISARI	xii
ABSTRACT	xiii
CHAPTER I. INTRODUCTION	1
1.1. Background	1
1.2. Problem Formulation	14
1.3. Research Questions	16
1.4. Research Objectives	16
1.5. Research Benefits	17
1.6. Research Contributions	17
1.7. Scope of the Research and Research Limitations	19
1.8. Outline of the Research	21
CHAPTER II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND LITERATURE REVIEW	22
2.1. Theoretical Framework	23
2.1.1. Time Series Forecasting	23
2.1.2. The Box-Jenkins Framework	28
2.1.3. Efficient Market Hypothesis	31
2.2. Literature Review	35
2.3. Hypothesis	36
CHAPTER III. RESEARCH METHOD	42
3.1. Research Design	42
3.2. Operational Variable Definitions	45
3.2.1. Dependent Variable	45
3.2.2. Independent Variable	46
3.3. Population and Sample	47
3.4. Research Instrument	49
3.5. Data Collection Technique	49
3.6. Data Analysis Technique	50
3.6.1. Autoregressive (AR) Model	53
3.6.2. Moving Average (MA) Model	54
3.6.3. Autoregressive Moving Average (ARMA) Model	55
3.6.4. Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) Model	57
3.7. Model Identification	59
3.7.1. Stationarity Test	59
3.7.2. Autocorrelation Functions Analysis	61
3.8. Parameters Estimation	63
3.8.1. Parameter Significance Estimation	63

3.8.2. Criterion Information Estimation	64
3.8.3. Coefficient of Determination Estimation	66
3.8.4. Error Estimation of Candidate ARIMA Models	67
3.9. Diagnostic Checking	69
3.9.1. Autocorrelation Test	69
3.9.2. Heteroskedasticity Test	70
3.9.3. ARIMA Process Invertibility Test	71
3.10. Forecasting	72
CHAPTER IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	71
4.1. Descriptive Analysis	71
4.2. Model Identification Results	79
4.2.1. Stationarity Test Results	79
4.2.2. Autocorrelation Functions Results	81
4.2.3. Candidate ARIMA Models	85
4.3. Parameters Estimation Results	86
4.3.1. Parameter Significance Estimation Results	86
4.3.2. Criterion Information Estimation Results	87
4.3.3. Coefficient of Determination Estimation Results	88
4.3.4. Error Estimation Results of Candidate ARIMA Models	89
4.4. Diagnostic Checking Results	91
4.4.1. Autocorrelation Test Results	91
4.4.2. Heteroskedasticity Test Results	93
4.4.3. ARIMA Process Invertibility Test Results	94
4.5. Forecasting Results	95
4.6. Discussion	98
CHAPTER V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION	105
5.1. Conclusion	105
5.2. Research Limitation	108
5.3. Implication	109
5.4. Recommendation	111
REFERENCE	113
APPENDICES	121

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1.1. Comparison of the Main Stock Market Indexes Growth in Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, and Thailand 1990-2021	5
Table 1.2. Descriptive Information of The Indonesia Stock Exchange 2019-2021	6
Table 2.1. Literature Review List	36
Table 3.1. Operational Variable Definitions and Data Source	47
Table 3.2. Research Samples Periods	49
Table 4.1. Descriptive Statistics of JKSE Training Samples Time Series	73
Table 4.2. Descriptive Statistics of IJKSE Training Samples Time Series	77
Table 4.3. Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test of IJKSE at level	79
Table 4.4. Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test of IJKSE at First Difference	80
Table 4.5. Sample Autocorrelation Coefficients of Significant Lags at 95% Confidence Interval	83
Table 4.6. Candidate ARIMA Models	85
Table 4.7. Results of Candidate Models Parameter Significance	86
Table 4.8. Results of Candidate Models Criterion Information	87
Table 4.9. Results of Candidate Models R-squared Estimations	89
Table 4.10. Results of Candidate Models Error Estimations	90
Table 4.11. Results of ARIMA (20,1,1) Model Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Test	93
Table 4.12. Dynamic and Static Forecasts Performance Comparison of ARIMA(20,1,1) Model	95

Table 4.13. Comparison of the Projected IJKSE Monthly Prices from ARIMA(20,1,1) Static
Forecast and the Actual JKSE Monthly Prices, January - October 2022 97

Table 4.14. Estimation Results of the ARIMA(20,1,1) Model 98

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1.1. Annual JKSE Price 1990-2021	3
Figure 2.1. Stages of the Box Jenkins Method	28
Figure 4.1. Distribution Plot of JKSE Training Samples Time Series	70
Figure 4.2. Monthly Price of JKSE Training Samples	75
Figure 4.3. Distribution Plot of IJKSE Training Samples Time Series	78
Figure 4.4. IJKSE series at First Difference	81
Figure 4.5. Correlogram of IJKSE at Level	82
Figure 4.6. Correlogram of IJKSE at First Difference	83
Figure 4.7. Correlogram of ARIMA(20,1,1) Model Ljung-Box Test	92
Figure 4.8. Quantiles Plots of ARIMA(20,1,1) Residuals	93
Figure 4.9. Result of ARIMA(20,1,1) Model Invertibility Test	94
Figure 4.10. Static Forecasted and Actual JKSE Monthly Price Movements	101
Figure 4.11. Growth of IDX Indicators 2018 – 2021 & Oct/2022	102

LIST OF APPENDICES

Appendix I	JKSE Monthly Price Time Series	121
Appendix II	Descriptive Statistics and Histogram of JKSE Series	123
Appendix III	Descriptive Statistics and Histogram of IJKSE Series	124
Appendix IV	Augmented Dickey-Fuller Unit Root Test of IJKSE Series before Differencing	125
Appendix V	Augmented Dickey-Fuller Unit Root Test of IJKSE Series after Differencing ..	126
Appendix VI	Correlogram of IJKSE before Differencing	127
Appendix VII	Correlogram of IJKSE after Differencing	128
Appendix VIII	Parameter Estimations of Candidate ARIMA Models	129
Appendix IX	Forecast Performance of Candidate ARIMA Models	133
Appendix X	Correlogram of ARIMA(20,1,1) Autocorrelation Test	136
Appendix XI	Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test of the Residuals	137
Appendix XII	ARIMA Process Invertibility of ARIMA(20,1,1) Model	138
Appendix XIII	Static Forecast Performance of ARIMA(20,1,1) Model	139

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ACF	Autocorrelation Function
AIC	Akaike Information Criterion
AR	Autoregressive
ARIMA	Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average
ARMA	Autoregressive Moving Average
EMH	Efficient Market Hypothesis
IDX	Indonesia Stock Exchange
JKSE	Jakarta Stock Exchange Composite Index
MA	Moving Average
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
MAPE	Mean Absolute Percentage Error
PACF	Partial Autocorrelation Function
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
SC	Schwarz Information Criterion
SSR	Sum of Squared Residuals
YoY	Year on Year

INTISARI

Realisasi pergerakan harga indeks pasar saham terus-menerus dipenuhi dengan ketidakpastian di mana peneliti dan profesional di bidang pasar modal telah bertahun-tahun mempelajari pendekatan untuk memprediksi variabel keuangan seperti indeks pasar saham dengan tantangan substansial. Tantangan yang dihadapi dalam memprediksi indeks pasar saham adalah karena karakteristik data *time series* yang sering menunjukkan non-stasioneritas, yaitu sifat statistik yang bervariasi dari waktu ke waktu atau karena fenomena sosial dan ekonomi yang tidak terduga yang mempengaruhi dinamika pasar saham, sehingga mempengaruhi keakuratan hasil perkiraan. Penelitian ini mencoba untuk merumuskan model prediksi dengan ukuran *goodness-of-fit* yang signifikan, melalui metodologi *Box-Jenkins* (ARIMA). Tujuan penelitian ini adalah untuk memprediksi proyeksi harga bulanan dari *Jakarta Stock Exchange Composite Index* (JKSE) untuk periode 10 bulan dari Januari hingga Oktober 2022, menggunakan nilai historis dari indeks itu sendiri dari Mei 1990 hingga Desember 2021. Sebuah prosedur iteratif *Box-Jenkins* kemudian dilakukan mulai dari tahap identifikasi model, tahap perkiraan parameter, tahap pemeriksaan diagnostik, dan proses prediksi. ARIMA (20,1,1) dipilih sebagai model penelitian terbaik dibandingkan dengan semua model kandidat, berdasarkan penilaian di semua tahap yang diperlukan dari metode ARIMA. Perkiraan model menghasilkan parameter model yang signifikan pada tingkat signifikansi 5%, residu *white noise* pada interval kepercayaan 95%, dan akurasi perkiraan 2,23% rata-rata persentase kesalahan mutlak sebagai perbedaan rata-ratanya antara harga JKSE yang diprediksi dan aktual selama periode pengujian.

Kata kunci: Perkiraan *Time Series*, Harga Indeks Pasar Saham, *Box-Jenkins Framework*, *Data Time Series*, *Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average Model*, Investasi

ABSTRACT

The realization of stock market index price movements is constantly filled with uncertainty where researchers and professionals in the field of capital markets have over the years studied approaches to forecasting finance variables such as a stock market index with substantial challenges. The challenges faced in forecasting stock market indexes are either due to the characteristics of time series data that often indicate non-stationarity whereby the statistical properties vary over time due to any unexpected social and economic phenomena affecting the dynamics of stock market that can basically happen at any given time, hence, influencing the accuracy of forecast results. In this reasoning, this research tries to formulate a forecasting model with significant goodness-of-fit measures, through the Box-Jenkins (ARIMA) methodology. The objective of this research is to forecast projections of the Jakarta Stock Exchange Composite Index (JKSE) monthly prices for a 10-month period from January to October, 2022, using the historical values of the index itself from May, 1990, to December, 2021. An iterative Box-Jenkins procedure is then conducted starting from the model identification stage, parameter estimation stage, diagnostic checking stage, and the forecasting process. The ARIMA(20,1,1) is selected as the best model of the research compared to all candidate models, based on the evaluations in all required stages of the ARIMA method. The model estimation results in significant model parameters at 5% significance level, white noise residuals at 95% confidence interval, and a forecast accuracy of 2.23% mean absolute percentage error as the average difference between the predicted and actual JKSE prices in the testing period.

Keyword: Time Series Forecasting, Stock Market Index Price, Box-Jenkins Framework, Time Series Data, Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average Model, Investment

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

The movement of stock index prices can be one of the benchmarks in estimating the general macroeconomic conditions of an economy, in a sense that the increase or decrease of stock index prices within a particular period could be due to whether the economy's performance is thriving or struggling, respectively (Nachrowi & Usman, 2007). In this globalization era whereby information spreads and can be shared easily, there also exist factors which may affect investment decisions such as news sentiments of companies' strategies, political and security conditions of the country which a certain stock market operates in, etc. Through this reasoning, forecast analysis of the foreseeable future of stock market performance can be beneficial to better prepare investors, professionals, and policy makers, for possible opportunities that are yet to come.

A forecast is generally viewed as a prediction of future outcomes on the basis of historical data. There are two common approaches of forecasting in the field of stock markets investment, that the professionals and investors use in constructing their investment decisions, which are fundamental analysis and technical analysis (Sadeq, 2008). Fundamental analysis in forecasting securities price movements analyzes the impacts of microeconomic and macroeconomic factors on a company's business and the configuration of the company's financial ratios performance, in order to forecast intrinsic values of the company's stock (Baresa et al., 2013). On the other hand, technical analysis is a forecasting technique that takes into account past observations of a time series in a particular period of time, to describe the

future outcomes of the series through sets of mathematical forecasting procedures (Rode et. al., 1995). In constructing predictions about stock and stock index price movements, technical analysis concentrates on analyzing the historical information of stock and stock index prices, such as values from a given period, patterns, and trends (Chen, et. al., 2018). Aligning the definitions and application of technical analysis with formulating a forecast model for stock index prices, the focus of this research is to forecast the realizations of a stock index price solely based on its historical values. Thus, the approach of technical analysis in forecasting is pursued in this research.

The author chose the Jakarta Stock Exchange Composite Index (JKSE) as the subject of forecasting analysis in this research for two main reasons. The first reason is that the JKSE price has performed an excellent growth in the observation period of this research, as would be shown in Figure 1.1. The second reason argues that specifications of the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) such as market capitalization, number of listed companies, and participation of both domestic and foreign investors, have also recorded significant growth in recent years, as indicated in Table 1.1. Given the overall positive trend that the Indonesian stock market has experienced over the years, the author believed a forecast study of the JKSE price would provide insightful analysis in anticipating the ever-unpredictable movements of stocks and stock indexes prices.

The Jakarta Stock Exchange Composite Index (JKSE) is the main stock market index of the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX), which represents the Indonesian stock market's performance. The JKSE index was established in 1983 and it reflects the movements of all stock prices in the Indonesian stock market as a whole (IDX, 2023). As per the month of October, 2022, 810 stocks were listed in the IDX, which amounted to 3,042.093 trillion

Rupiah of IDX’s market capitalization (Central Bureau of Statistics of Indonesia, 2022). Similar to the other popular indexes acknowledged by the IDX such as LQ45, Jakarta Islamic Index (JII), KOMPAS100, IDX BUMN20, PEFINDO25, etc., the JKSE index is also calculated through a method of capped free float adjusted market capitalization weighted average. The capped free float adjusted market capitalization is an index calculation method with a weighted average based on the free float market capitalization of outstanding shares (Bareksa, 2022).

Over the period of 1990 to 2021, the Jakarta Stock Exchange Composite Index (JKSE) has performed outstanding growth, from its value of 417.78 Rupiah on December 1st, 1990, to 6,581.48 on December 1st, 2021, as shown in Figure 1.1. The remarkable growth that JKSE price has experienced manages to portray the Indonesian stock market as one of Southeast Asia’s most vigorous capital markets.

Figure 1.1. Annual JKSE Price December 1st 1990 - December 1st 2021

Source: Yahoo Finance, processed (2022)

Throughout the 1990s, the Indonesian economy was strongly driven by agriculture and natural resources sectors, which reflected on the JKSE's price fluctuation by a steady growth that were due to favorable macroeconomic conditions along with government regulations designed to promote capital markets (Kim & Wei, 2002). It was only in the 2000s that significant rallies were recorded by the JKSE price as a result of the economic and market reforms, which eventually helped the Indonesian economy to quickly recover from the Asian financial crisis of 1998-1999 (Laeven & Valencia, 2012).

Research by the World Bank (2010) focusing on the Indonesian economy transition from recovery to sustainable growth, stated that as the economy continued its development, it resulted in a robust economic growth in the mid-2000s and early 2010s, boosted by a growing middle class and investments injected into the economy which was consequently followed by a substantial expansion of the JKSE prices. Nevertheless, the Indonesian stock market managed to endure tough challenges and slow-down of growth during the notable crises in the past, which were; the great recession of 2008; the geopolitical tensions of oil price collapse in 2015; and the recent financial crisis of 2020 due to the global pandemic; leading to temporary declines of the index performance as shown in Figure 1.1. In facing these challenges, the Indonesian government made efforts of stimulus packages and proactive measures in stabilizing the economy, which indeed contributed to the index's strong recovery in each financial crisis that the Indonesian stock market faced (World Bank, 2021).

From 2011 to 2021, a trend of consistent growth was performed by the JKSE prices, supported by the Indonesian economy's status as an emerging market, a growing productive population, and increasing interest from foreign investors (International Monetary Fund, 2019). The JKSE's consistent growth from the period of 2011 to 2021, corresponded with the

increased of the Indonesia's gross domestic product (GDP) of 7,290 trillion Rupiah to 11,120 trillion Rupiah during the period, respectively, in constant 2010 prices, which indicated a growth of 52.54% of GDP (World Bank, 2023).

According to Statista (2021) as per December 2021, the Indonesia Stock Exchange ranks third in market capitalization within the Southeast Asia region, behind the Singapore Exchange and the Stock Exchange of Thailand. For the sake of comparing the stock index price's growth of the markets in the region, the author purposely picked the five largest markets based on market capitalization as exhibited in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1. Comparison of the Main Stock Market Indexes Growth in Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, and Thailand 1990-2021

Stock Index	Price*		Growth
	December 1990	December 2021	
JKSE (Indonesia)	417.78	6,581.48	1,457.32%
PSEi (Philippines)	653.11	7,122.63	990.57%
KLCI (Malaysia)	492.19	1,501.70	205.11%
STI (Singapore)	1,154.81	3,123.68	170.49%
SET (Thailand)	645	1,657.62	157.00%

**Stock index prices stated in each country's respective currencies*

Source: Trading Economics, processed (2022)

Among the five leading stock markets based on market capitalization in Southeast Asia, the Indonesian stock market's major index, JKSE, led the historical growth between the period 1990-2021. The JKSE index recorded a staggering 1,457.32% of index price growth, which was a quite significant performance compared to that of the Stock Exchange of Thailand

Composite Index's (SET) growth at 157%. A rapid growth of index price for the given period was also exhibited by the Philippine Stock Exchange Composite Index (PSEi) of 990.57%, which was quite a significant difference compared to those of the Kuala Lumpur Composite Index (KLCI) and the Strait Times Index (STI) at 205.11% and 170.49%, respectively. However, the growths of main stock market indexes shown in Table 1.1. merely pointed out the stock markets' performance based on their historical values. To alleviate the effects of numerical differences among the stock index prices in understanding the stock market's strength, attributing factors such as market reforms, domestic and foreign investors participation, and economic development, have to be taken into account (Putri & Manurung, 2021).

Table 1.2. Descriptive Information of The Indonesia Stock Exchange 2019-2021

Information	2019	2020	2021	Growth 2019-2021
Market Capitalization (Trillion Rupiah)	7,265	6,970	8,256	13.64%
Domestic Ownership (Trillion Rupiah)	4,047	3,962	4,851	19.86%
Domestic Ownership (%)	55.71%	56.85%	58.76%	3.05%
Foreign Ownership (Trillion Rupiah)	3,217	3,007	3,404	5.81%
Foreign Ownership (%)	44.29%	43.15%	41.24%	-3.05%

Listed Companies	668	713	766	14.67%
Investors of Stocks and Other Securities*	1,104,610	1,695,268	3,451,513	212.46%

**Stated in number of individuals*

Source: Indonesia Central Securities Depository (*KSEI*), Central Bureau of Statistics of Indonesia (*BPS*), processed (2022)

More recent data describing specifically the stock exchange of Indonesia are indicated in Table 1.2., was collected per the end of year from credible sources, for the three-year period of 2019-2021. The data highlights the IDX market capitalization's growth of 13.64% - equaling to an increase of 991 trillion Rupiah from 2019 to 2021. The impacts that the Indonesian stock market endured in the first year of the global pandemic came into realization, whereby its market capitalization decreased by (295) trillion Rupiah, contracting a minus 4.06% YoY from 2019 to 2020. The growth contraction of the IDX's market capitalization in the first year of the global pandemic of 2020 in Indonesia, is viewed by the author as a temporary knock-down, because the IDX managed to recover its market capitalization at 18.45% YoY from 2020 to 2021. This success of the stock market's recovery due to the effects that the global pandemic had on the Indonesian economy, redeemed the Indonesian stock market as an intriguing and growing investment hub for both the domestic and foreign investors.

Table 1.2. indicates that in the IDX from 2019-2021, foreign investments increased by 5.81% or an equivalent of 187 trillion Rupiah, and domestic investment increased by 19.86% or an equivalent of 803 trillion Rupiah. Contrary to these positive trends mentioned beforehand, foreign ownerships in the IDX decreased by 3.05% from 2019-2021. However,

the decrease of foreign ownership in the market share was majorly due to the rising participation of domestic investors, such that the government policy of local lockdowns and work-from-home business activities along with marketing campaigns of investing in capital markets induced the Indonesian population's awareness regarding the allocation of their income and savings for investment purposes (Putri & Manurung, 2021). In overall, the awareness of investment opportunities in the IDX has had positive signs on the investment demand of stocks and other securities, whereby from 2019-2021, there were additional 98 number of enterprises going public, along with an increase of 2,346,903 number of investors which was a significant growth of 212.46% in the stated period.

The positive trend that JKSE price has experienced over the past three decades, specifically since 1990, has brought considerations to the author regarding efforts and approaches which can be pursued by investors, policy regulators, and the general public to foresee the index's outcomes in the upcoming future. Stocks as securities traded in the Indonesian capital market can also be pooled into other sophisticated investment products such as mutual funds and exchange-traded funds, whereby their performance relate to the fluctuations of JKSE price and offer investors opportunities of capital gains filled with its own risks (Pohan, 2022). In the field of investment, particularly in stock markets, there is no such thing as certainty. Movements of stock prices and indexes are unpredictable and random, in a sense that even professional analysts and investors found difficulties in constructing forecasting models that consistently outperform the market (Malkiel, 2019). Barber & Odean (2008), argued that both individual and institutional investors tend to be alert of recent news regarding corporate plans and economics issues, affecting their behavior of potentially buying and selling stocks. The latter study was also followed up by Barber et al., (2009) that examined how such responsive

acts, for instance, panic-selling of investors' stocks holdings, consequently led to investors' wealth erosion exhibited in the early 2000s stock market crash and the great recession of 2008. The nature of unpredictability of the stock markets ensures the author of this research regarding the necessity in formulating a forecast model based on statistical analysis, that is able to help investors navigate through the stock market's uncertainty.

This research identifies the JKSE price's series as a single variable for the univariate time series regression model in forecasting its future realizations, since the time series value is only the historical prices of the index itself. In projecting future values of a series, the univariate time series regression analysis focuses the series' single variable past observations by taking into account the consecutive nature of time series data to exhibit trends and patterns (Montgomery, Jennings, & Kulahci, 2015). Among the other approaches to forecasting time series data, this research utilizes the Box-Jenkins (ARIMA) method as it is both prominent and applicable to forecast financial time series data of stocks and stock indexes (Brooks, 2014).

The Box-Jenkins methodology, popularly known as the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model, is an approach for time series forecasting that uses historical information of a particular time series data to predict a specified data range (Box et. al., 2015). The ARIMA model involves four major steps that are identification, parameter estimation, diagnostic checking, and forecasting, which will be explained later in this research. The use of the ARIMA model in forecasting the financial markets' dynamics is well-suited as the model is formulated to handle financial time series data like stocks and stock indexes prices, whereby the property of such time series is prevalingly non-stationary due to behaviors of seasonality and trends (Wei, 2006). The effectiveness of using the ARIMA model to forecast

stock market movements have been demonstrated over the years, as according to Brooks (2014) researchers and professionals have extensively utilized ARIMA models to forecast prices of stocks and indexes with satisfactory results. Robust performance of the ARIMA model in forecasting financial time series that shows repetitive and consistent patterns, was also indicated by previous studies, especially when the model is used for short-term projections, (Meyler et. al., 1998; Gujarati & Porter, 2009; Tsay, 2005).

Previous studies by Murwaningsari (2008) and Grestandhi et al., (2011) have also shown that the Box-Jenkins methodology (ARIMA) has performed well, if not better, when compared to other time series forecasting approaches in forecasting JKSE index prices. The former study forecasted JKSE monthly prices using monthly observations from 1992-2006 through ARIMA model and Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity (GARCH) model, in which the results indicated that the ARIMA model produced the least differences between forecasted value and actual value of the JKSE monthly prices compared to results of the GARCH forecast model. The latter study used daily JKSE prices from January 4th 2010, to September 13th, 2011 in forecasting for the price of JKSE through the ARIMA and GARCH models, in which based on the observed time series data the ARIMA(0,2,1) model succeeded to outperform the GARCH(1,1) model in terms of prediction accuracy for short-run forecasting. Similar empirical results were also provided by Nachrowi & Usman (2007) using daily observations of JKSE prices from January 3rd, 2005, to January 2nd, 2006, to forecast the next 90 daily prices and the study selected ARIMA(1,1,0) as the best model to predict the series with forecast errors from the actual prices at 0.9% that is more accurate compared to the other capable GARCH(2,2) model with forecast errors at 4.5%. Another comparable study was also conducted in Malaysia by Miswan et al., (2014) forecasted

monthly prices of the Kuala Lumpur Composite Index (KLCI) using ARIMA and GARCH models, where ARIMA(7,1,7) model produced better accuracy measures of Akaike information criterion (AIC) at 10.60028 and root mean square error (RMSE) at 44.45587 that are smaller than those of GARCH(7,1) model's AIC at 10.75714 and RMSE at 57.14706, respectively. The consistency of ARIMA models for predicting the JKSE prices inattentive to which sampling period used as referred to these previous studies, ensures the author of this research regarding ARIMA model's adequacy in forecasting the index prices.

Theoretically, it is not necessarily indicated that the ARIMA model is perfect for all subjects of forecasting research with different approaches and frameworks. The GARCH model does possess an advantage against the ARIMA model, whereby Tsay (2005) emphasized that more complicated forecasting models such as the GARCH model and Vector Autoregression (VAR) model are proficient in seizing long-term dependencies and volatility. According to Nachrowi & Usman (2007), time series forecasting models such as GARCH and VAR models are methods based on causality approach, that is the movement of stock index prices could be analyzed from other variables which affect the prices formulation. The clear difference between these aforementioned models is that ARIMA model is a univariate time series analysis to model autocorrelation in the data, while GARCH is a multivariate time series analysis to model volatility in the data. The GARCH model is commonly utilized to process heteroskedastic data that features unequal variable variance of the residuals over a certain range of observed values which associate interdependencies surrounding multiple variables. Thus, GARCH forecast modeling may be more efficient for long-term prediction because historical trends and patterns of the variable alone might not reoccur similarly over long-term period in the future. However, Tsay (2005) and Meyler et. al., (1998) also emphasized

ARIMA model's competitiveness in forecasting short-term outcomes due to achieving stationarity and homoskedasticity within the data such that variances are constant throughout the observed values and as a result, ARIMA model concentrates on capturing trends and patterns of the univariate data itself. The robustness of ARIMA model in short-term forecasting can help determine optimal trading strategies, especially for short-term predictions that are statistically valid (Dadhich et al., 2021) for investors who are exploring for stocks investment positions and capital gains.

Given the focus of this research being to project realizations of the JKSE prices on a monthly basis, at the time of writing this research the author noticed a literature gap of limited accessible research papers, journals, and studies, which conducted forecast analysis for the JKSE index using ARIMA model specifically with monthly intervals. In comparison, there have been many studies that forecasted stock market indexes for markets across the globe using ARIMA model based on monthly time series, for instance, Rounaghi & Zadeh (2016) forecasted the stock markets of the United States and England through the ARIMA model that produced superior predictions of the London Stock Exchange and S&P 500 indexes monthly returns for medium-term compared to other forecasting methods. Evidence in Asia was provided by Li et al., (2017) that predicted monthly prices of the Shanghai Composite Index for a two-month period of November to December 2016, using the ARIMA model based on a training period of monthly prices from January 2005 to October 2016 and the forecasted projections had only 2.4% average error from the actual prices - indicating a high accuracy and effectiveness of the model. Another example was in Nigeria, which operates the second-largest stock market by market capitalization in Africa (NGX Group, 2022), forecasting studies were pursued to predict the Nigerian Stock Exchange index prices based on monthly

observation by Eke (2019) utilizing monthly time series over a 10-year period training sample and Etuk et al., (2012) using monthly time series over a 21-year period training sample, in which the ARIMA model successfully captured the trends and noise of the stock market prices, resulting in significant monthly forecast outcomes of the Nigerian Stock Exchange index.

Due to the opportunity of literature gap in monthly forecast for the JKSE index that specifically authorizes ARIMA modeling, this research is written by looking up to the frameworks of existing ARIMA forecasting studies of the index prices which utilized daily time series by Haerani & Nugraha (2022); Pardede (2019); Wahyudi (2017); and Yenice & Tekindal (2015). This research would then modify the existing frameworks mentioned by applying the JKSE index prices series in monthly intervals and logarithmic transformation of the series, with a training sample of a 32-year period, from May 1990 to December 2021, in order to forecast a ten-month period of January to October 2022 which has never been provided by any previous study forecasting the JKSE prices at the time of writing this research. The framework of this research is also inspired by Mashadihasanli (2022) that produced excellent static forecast outcomes of the stock market index price of Istanbul using the ARIMA model with monthly time series and Pillay (2020) that successfully obtained better predictions and statistical inference of the ARIMA model in forecasting the Johannesburg Stock Exchange Index by transforming the initial index's series into a logarithmic function.

Based on the evidences indicated in the aforementioned studies, the author of this research tries to emphasize the benefits in which the ARIMA model offers, because an adequate ARIMA forecasting model can help investors, stakeholders, policy makers, whom are

affected by the Indonesian stock market's dynamics, and even the general public who are looking into investment opportunities, to be equipped with a prolonged projection of the JKSE prices in the time ahead. As will be discussed in the upcoming chapters of this research, the forecasting model manages to significantly forecast the JKSE monthly prices with significant model parameters at 5% significance level with residuals that are white noise and ARIMA forecast model that do not suffer from issues of heteroskedasticity, autocorrelation, and invertibility.

As a disclaimer, this research is not a form of recommendations, tips, nor instructions to buy or sell any particular investment products within or related to the JKSE index in any period of time. Rather this research aims to provide knowledge as well as trigger further curiosity regarding the Box-Jenkins method and the field of stock market index forecasting.

1.2. Problem Formulation

Serving as the major stock market index in the IDX, the movement of JKSE prices is commonly viewed as one of the benchmarks for analyzing whether the Indonesian stock market fare overwhelmingly or underwhelmingly in its performance. As indicated through Table 1.1. the impeccable growth of the index reached to 1,457.32% from 1990 to 2021. The author of this research argues that such growth of a stock market's index price deserves both its recognition and fair criticism, in which among them the author wonders; will such growth of the JKSE price be sustainable in the future? On the contrary, will the JKSE price eventually head for a downturn after its immense rise from 1990 to 2021? Decisively, is there a way to foresee the JKSE prices' realizations in the upcoming future with a viable and statistically significant analysis? Both in the past and present times, similar questions might have brought

upon the necessity for possible approaches to forecast stock markets' performance with adequate accuracy.

Following the Neoclassical growth theory introduced by Solow (1956; 1957), economists continued to develop the concept of investment causes economic growth, in a sense that an increase of investment into an economy will sequentially improve the ratio of capital to labor which energizes the growth of an economy (Hunt, 2007). For instance, previous ARIMA forecasting studies by Banerjee (2014) and Reddy (2019) provide evidences of the connection between growths of a nation's economy and its stock market, whereby both studies forecasted stock indices within the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) and the National Stock Exchange (NSE) in India using the ARIMA method, such that their empirical results highlighted the progression of major stock market indices in-part corresponded with the growth of the Indian economy. Hence, by assuming that movements of a major stock index price depict the general performance of the particular stock market, the author of this research argues that the positive impacts which stock market investment can bring into an economy and the challenging task in predicting future outcomes of the economy's stock market fluctuations, formulates a research motivation of a sound and accurate stock market index forecasting analysis.

Referring to the discussion and findings acknowledged from studies stated in this research's background, this research addresses an approach of time series forecasting to project or predict the realizations of the JKSE index. This research by design utilizes monthly observations of the index prices in the efforts to try to capture a longer period of more years within the training sample as compared to smaller units of interval i.e., weekly or daily, etc. In the existence of a significant price differences of the JKSE index prices between the period of 1990s to the period of early 2020s, this research proposes a formulation of forecast analysis

based on the Box-Jenkins theory, due to the methodology's compatibility in handling characteristics of time series data, pioneered by the work of George Box and Gwilym Jenkins (1970). Therefore, the goal that this research tries to accomplish is to project the realizations of JKSE monthly prices for a ten-month period of January to October, 2022, using the ARIMA forecasting model based on past observations of the index price from May, 1990, to December, 2021.

1.3. Research Questions

This research is pursued to answer the following research questions:

- i. How can the Box-Jenkins methodology operated in a form of ARIMA model be employed to forecast JKSE monthly prices?
- ii. How does the employed ARIMA model fit with the JKSE time series data through the meticulous parameter estimation and diagnostic checking stages?
- iii. How accurate is the forecasted projection of the JKSE monthly prices produced by the ARIMA model compared to the actual realizations of the index monthly prices in the concerned forecast period?
- iv. How can the use of ARIMA forecasting model be of service to the readers in obtaining adequate prediction of the JKSE monthly price movements as the main stock market index in the IDX, specifically in their pursuit of capital gains?

1.4. Research Objectives

Through this research, the author aims to conduct empirical test by taking into account past observation of the monthly JKSE prices from May, 1990, until December, 2021, to be treated

with the ARIMA forecasting model in order to formulate monthly predictions of the index prices in January to October, 2022, as well as to analyze how the projected outcomes progress in the forecasted period with respect to the index's actual realizations.

1.5. Research Benefits

There are two focused benefits of constructing this research, the author states them as follows:

1. In theoretical benefits perspective, this research is expected to be a new contribution to the field of education, particularly to the field of time series analysis and forecasting studies using the Box-Jenkins methodology. Furthermore, the author hopes that this research will create more opportunities and possibilities of improvements for research in the future.
2. As for the practical benefits, the presentation of this research for educational purposes is expected to provide a research framework or fundamental ground which can contribute as a reference for further studies, in the hope that this research would practically benefit the readers regarding the subjects of time series forecasting, investment and capital market, and any research related to the Box-Jenkins methodology.

1.6. Research Contributions

Previous studies have analyzed time series data of the JKSE index in order to create predictions of the index price movements with different types of samples interval for both the training and testing periods. The goodness-of-fit analysis conducted and the estimated accuracy rate of the forecasting models by using the ARIMA approach also differ for each researcher. On top of that, the author of this research found a more-limited numbers of studies applying the ARIMA forecasting model that predicted the movements of the index prices

using time series data with monthly interval, as compared to studies which utilize smaller interval i.e. weekly, daily, etc., that are more common to be found. The works of Haerani & Nugraha (2022) and Pardede (2019) have successfully predicted the Jakarta Stock Exchange Composite Index daily prices with high accuracy using the ARIMA model, however, the former study lack the evidence of P-value coefficient significance for each AR and MA terms used in the model and the latter study's forecast results might be less precise than expected since no heteroskedasticity test was conducted to analyze whether the processed time series has variance which changes over time or otherwise. In response to this window of improvement, this research would also add contribution of a more thorough goodness-of-fit measures in the ARIMA forecasting model which include the analysis of; stationarity, information criterion; parameter significance; coefficient of determination; model's invertibility; autocorrelation; heteroskedasticity; and forecast error evaluation.

The author of this research believes that the occurring rarity of ARIMA forecasting studies, specifically used in projecting JKSE prices with monthly samples interval, is due to the method's efficient competence in producing short-term forecasts highlighted by Meyler et. al., (1998), which could induce researchers to work with smaller intervals such as daily or weekly, etc. Given the lesser common use of monthly time series data in previous ARIMA studies that predicted the JKSE prices (Murwaningsari, 2008), the author of this research would then aim to provide empirical proofs in a sense that utilizing monthly intervals of the JKSE series within the model is also capable of producing accurate forecasts. Additionally, during this research's writing process, the author found no accessible study that forecasted the JKSE prices through the Box-Jenkins methodology which observed the index series for more than 30 years of observation. Therefore, the novel contribution of this research is to

analyze the JKSE series data from 1990 to 2021 using the ARIMA approach - which is unprecedented, by utilizing its monthly observations to produce a short-term prediction of 10-month period, that spans in January - October, 2022.

This research's approach to forecasting the JKSE index is expected to also provide assistance in easing decision making and regulation formulating processes surrounding investment opportunities for investors, stakeholders, policy makers, and government regulators. For instance, if policy makers and regulators aimed to predict an economic series' future trends that might be related with the stock market's performance as one of the considerations in formulating policies, a similar methodology such as the ARIMA method used in this research could be utilized. Moreover, the author hopes that this research can create rooms for improvement and more sophisticated approaches to further studies, specifically in the field of time series forecasting.

1.7. Scope of the Research and Research Limitations

To formulate a forecasting model for the JKSE prices, this research is constructed based on several previous research that performed forecasts for stocks and stock indexes prices using the ARIMA methodology, supplemented by additional model modifications which align with research frameworks of the previous studies. This research puts to use a time series data of the JKSE prices in the past, to be employed with this research's model in producing a projection of its prices for a specified testing period. By assuming that a long-term uptrend of a stock index would most likely be succeeded with a short-run rises due to the trend-following behavior of investors (Hurst, Ooi, & Pedersen, 2017), this research is expected to produce forecast results of the index which contain potential gains by investing in the stock market of

Indonesia throughout the forecast period, accommodated by a positive trend that the index prices have experienced over the last three decades.

The variable taken into account for this research's modeling is then only the prices of the JKSE index, as this research analyzes a univariate time series forecasting model which essentially describes future values based on the series' own past information. The author of this research takes into account the possibility of a bias to occur within processing the time series data using the ARIMA model, and thus, goodness-of-fit tests are conducted to ensure that the model fits comfortably with the data in producing an accurate projection of the index. The author also considers research barriers in obtaining the data used, that being the case, the usage of data in this research is limited to the following notions:

1. The specific stock market index analyzed in this research is the Jakarta Stock Exchange Composite Index (JKSE), which resembles the performance of the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) as a whole.
2. This research utilizes a sole variable that is a time series data of the JKSE prices in monthly observations from the period of May, 1990, to December, 2021, as the training sample processed in the model.
3. For the forecast projection period, this research analyzes a ten-month period that spans from January, 2022, to October, 2022, as the testing sample. This research resorts to comparing how the predicted outcomes perform with respect to the actual realizations of the index during the testing period, such that accuracy measures could prompt this research's forecasting model capability in projecting future movements of the index which is equipped with significant statistical evidence.

4. Given this research's main purpose which is projecting movements of the JKSE prices in the testing period, the author acknowledges that the entirety of modeling process and forecast results analysis would be limited to the sole subject of the JKSE index prices. The main available data required for this research's forecast model is the monthly JKSE prices, as for discussions related to the topic of Indonesian stock market, this research also utilizes information of the IDX's characteristics including (i) number of investors in the stock market, (ii) number of listed companies in the stock market, (iii) value of the stock market capitalization, and (iv) value of both domestic and foreign investments in the stock market.

1.8. Outline of the Research

The writing of this research will be outlined in five chapters, with each chapter's contents arranged as follows:

- i. Chapter I: Introduction

Chapter one consists of the subchapters of background, problem formulation, research questions, research objectives, research benefits, research contributions, scope of the research and research limitations, and outline of the research.

- ii. Chapter II: Theoretical Framework and Literature Review

Chapter two is an explanation of the theories which serve as the theoretical framework and foundation of analysis in this research. The summary of literature review based on previous studies conducted in the past is also covered in this chapter.

iii. Chapter III: Research Method

Chapter three describes the methodology of this research, including the subchapters that explain research design, operational variable definitions, population and sample, research instruments, data collection technique, data analysis technique, model identification, parameter estimation, diagnostic checking, and forecasting.

iv. Chapter IV: Results and Discussion

Chapter four examines and unveils the analysis, interpretation, and results incurred from processing and modeling the data which is conducted by this research, aligned with the discussions and arguments explained in the previous chapters. This chapter ultimately reveals the conformity of empirical results with the applied hypotheses.

v. Chapter V: Conclusion and Recommendation

Chapter five comprises the conclusion and policy recommendation based on this research's results and limitations. This chapter concludes the research as the final chapter which also contains suggestions for further studies in the future.

CHAPTER II

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Theoretical Framework

2.1.1. Time Series Forecasting

Time series forecasting is a process of quantitative approach and modeling to analyze time series data over a particular observation period in order to create forecasts of the target series' future information (Karanikola et al., 2021). It is used in a wide range of fields such as economics, business, policy regulation, and many branches of social and natural studies. To better understand the analysis and purpose of time series forecasting, one can acknowledge the definitions of time series and forecasting separately. Time series is a type of data that contains a sequence of observations taken consecutively in time (Box et al., 2015). Examples of time series data sets include hourly stock prices, daily weather conditions, weekly number of accident cases, annual sales of a company, and so forth. An essential characteristic of time series is that adjacent observations are dependent, in a sense that two or more observations of a time series are adjacent if and only if the value of one of the observations is the instant predecessor of the other observation's value. The analysis of time series data addresses methods for analyzing this dependency.

On the other hand, forecasting is a procedure of calculating approximate future value for a variable by taking into account the variable's past and/or present information within the analysis process (Muschilati & Irsalinda, 2020). In other words, forecasting can be defined as a technique that employs previous values of a particular

variable as inputs to generate estimates which are projective in shaping the variable's realizations and trends in the future. In short, forecasting is an activity that requires a set of analytical procedures in processing historical information to predict or project future outcomes. By conducting forecasts using historical information of one or more variables, changes in situations and conditions of a particular focus of research in the time ahead can be anticipated. If research can predict the future outcomes, then it can change or alter the current behavior of individuals anticipating such results in the future (Pianda, 2018). According to the work of Al Arif (2012), the fundamental activity required to conduct a forecast is to gather data about a phenomenon in the past with respect to its present information.

The focus of this research, that is the forecasting of the price of the Jakarta Stock Exchange Composite Index (JKSE), influences the author's decision to analyze a type of time series data which is a univariate time series data. According to Box et. al., (2015) univariate time series is defined as a time series that contains a single data observed sequentially over time. The work of Pohan (2022) highlighted that since it is understood the prices of stock or stock index are classified as a univariate time series data, its modeling through forecasts has become an important consideration for investors in making decisions due to stock prices' characteristics of high risks and fluctuation. With this reasoning, concise forecasts of stock and index prices with results reaching as close as possible to the actual stock prices can help the decision making of investors.

Based on the definitions in the preceding paragraphs, this research defines time series forecasting as an analysis technique that is performed using historical

information and statistical methods to determine the future realizations and trends. Time series forecasting is not limited to only the field of economics, but can also be utilized to other branches of studies that aspire to analyze time series data in the efforts of portraying the future events. Such analysis that is able to estimate future events with significant statistical measures can help to facilitate plans, regarding the next activities to be carried out to anticipate the changes of a variable's outcomes in the time ahead.

There are several methods used in forecasting time series data. In its practice, the five approaches in conducting forecasts based on time series according to Gujarati and Porter (2009) are briefly put in words as in the following:

1. Exponential Smoothing Method, is a method of forecasting univariate time series data that has both linear trend and seasonal pattern. The principle of this method is that predictions are weighted linear sums of past observations or lags. It is basically a method of fitting a suitable curve to historical data of a particular time series. Methods of this approach include *Holt's linear method*, *Holt-Winters' method*, and *single exponential smoothing*. The use of the exponential smoothing method is proper for non-stationary data or data that contains a trend or seasonality (Makridakis et al., 2008).
2. Single-Equation Regression Model, is a method of regression models that estimate the relationship between a dependent variable and independent variables. In the focus of time series forecasting, it is proposed that the dependent variable is a function of the independent variables which affect the dependent variable. One can estimate a suitable model of the dependent variable using time series data of the independent variables. For instance, a company sales forecast is a function of the

company's product prices, consumer income, interest rate, production costs, advertising expense, and other significant variables. Single-equation regression models can be in forms of *linear regression model*, *log-linear model*, or *nonlinear regression model*.

3. Simultaneous-Equation Regression Model, is a method of regression models that estimate the relationship between a dependent variable and other dependent variables, instead of only independent variables. In essence, the principle of this approach to forecasting is that the variables on the right-hand side and the variable on the left-hand side of the same equation affect each other simultaneously or at one and the same time. These methods were very popular during the 1960s and 1970s for forecasting economic models in the United States, however, such forecasting methods were later heavily scrutinized by the *Lucas Critique* and specifically due to the phenomena of 1973 oil price shocks (Lucas Jr, 1976). The main issue of this approach which is emphasized by the *Lucas Critique* is that an econometric model's estimated parameters are dependent on the occurring policy at the time the model was formulated and the estimated parameters will change as a transformation of policy takes place. This becomes important because simultaneous-equation regression models may result incompetent forecasting performance as the *Lucas Critique* reveals that the estimated parameters are not invariant in the existence of changes of policy.
4. Vector Autoregression (VAR) Models, are stochastic process models that generalize the univariate autoregressive model by recognizing multivariate time series within the models in order to apprehend the linear interdependence between

the various series (Sims, 1980). The approach of VAR in forecasting is similar to simultaneous-equation models whereby it takes into account multiple endogenous variables together except for every endogenous variable is described by its lagged or historical values and the other endogenous variables' lagged values in the model (Harvey, 1990; Pankratz, 2012). In other words, VAR models engage with time series data and produce forecasts by accounting for the casual relationship among the variables (Parvin & Khanam, 2018).

5. Box-Jenkins Method, is a time series forecasting technique in which its prominence is on analyzing the probabilistic properties of a time series data rather than on formulating single-equation or simultaneous-equation regression models. Unlike the regression models whereby the regressand, or the dependent variable, is described by k regressors $X_1, X_2, X_3, \dots, X_k$, the Box-Jenkins models of time series data allow the dependent variable to be explained by the models' previous or lagged values of the dependent variable itself and its error terms. The Box-Jenkins method is also scientifically well known as the ARIMA methodology. According to Gujarati & Porter (2009), the key point in utilizing the Box-Jenkins method is achieving either a stationary time series data or a time series data that is stationary, after differencing through first order difference or d number of orders difference processes. The assumption of Box-Jenkins models' features that are constant through time specifically for future periods is important such that by any model acquiring stationarity or a stable state can provide a sound footing for forecasting (Pokorny, 1987).

These methods of time series forecasting can be differently used for different research purposes based on each particular model's specifications and statistical procedures of samples concerned. In this research, the Box-Jenkins method would be the underlying framework as the researcher sides with previous studies and findings that the Box-Jenkins method can produce good forecasts results of stock index price movements.

2.1.2. Box-Jenkins Framework

The Box-Jenkins framework is a method of mathematical procedure designed to forecast data ranges based on information or historical values from a specific time series data, named after its inventors George Box and Gwilym Jenkins, whose method originated in their work, Box and Jenkins (1970). The Box-Jenkins approach to analysis, forecasting, and control of time series data is a powerful but rather complicated process that is useful in many kinds of situations which involve the formulating of models for different time series and dynamic systems (Chatfield & Prothero, 1973). The method operates in forms of an autoregressive (AR) process, a moving average (MA) process, or the combination of both processes which are autoregressive moving average (ARMA) and autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) models. Specifically in the field of stock price forecasting, the method is technically known as the ARIMA models. The ARIMA modeling can be used in forecasting the performance of stock and stock index by utilizing the information obtained from the variables itself to forecast its trend.

The ARIMA model regresses a specific variable, such as a company's stock price or a stock market index, on its own historical price values. The ARIMA forecasting

model utilizes a univariate analysis or an analysis that carries out on only one variable to describe or summarize the variable (Babbie, 2007), which in this research the price of Jakarta Stock Exchange Composite Index (JKSE) is the variable of study. By connecting the stock market index forecast with the Box-Jenkins philosophy of “*let the variable speak for itself*”, the design of Box-Jenkins models in this research is to forecast future outcomes of the JKSE based on its past values.

Figure 2.1. Stages of the Box-Jenkins Method

(Source: Gujarati & Porter, 2009)

The Box-Jenkins forecasting model consists of four main stages which are model identification, parameter estimation, diagnostic checking, and forecasting as illustrated in Figure 2.1. Elaboration of the model’s procedure and specifications in processing time series data will be explained in following chapters of this research. In brief, the identification stage processes a given time series data in the first place to discover possible ARIMA models by analyzing significant lags of the Autoregressive (AR) and

Moving Average (MA) parameters, complemented with deciding whether any differencing order of the original series is needed or not, such that the series is stationary. Secondly, the parameter estimation phase looks into the parameter significance of each candidate models' coefficient, AR, and MA terms because a desired best model should have significant terms to work with any further, as insignificant AR and MA terms could lead to the model unfitting the series data and such, producing a potentially bias and/or inaccurate forecasts. Among the candidate models with significant terms, the information selection criteria and error evaluation would also be conducted in this stage to determine the best model for forecasting the series. The goodness-of-fit measures are then performed in the diagnostic checking to examine that the selected model actually fits the series data. If instead diagnostic tests results indicate that the fitted model is not suiting the data comfortably, the first and second steps of Box-Jenkins framework must be restarted to figure out another model that can satisfy diagnostic checking tests. The last stage, that is the forecasting act, would finally utilize the best ARIMA model which surpasses all previous steps to create projection of the initial series for a decided forecast period.

Around the time of the Box-Jenkins method's early developments, there were other methods used based solely on the historical values of time series data. Several other methods utilizing this approach were applied in the works of; Winters (1960) which forecasted sales using exponentially weighted moving averages; Brown (1963) which researched smoothing, forecasting, and prediction of discrete time series and; Harrison (1965) which also focused on short-term sales forecasting. These studies utilized the same type of data used in the Box-Jenkins method, a univariate data that consists of

only one time series variable. The comparison of the Box-Jenkins methodology with the aforementioned studies were conducted and it was found that by involving more than 50 observations, the Box-Jenkins method resulted in the best forecasts for most time series (Reid, 1971). More evidence of the Box-Jenkins method's performance in a 50 macroeconomic series was given by Granger and Newbold (1972), whereby Box-Jenkins inclined to produce better forecasts than both Holt-Winters and step-wise autoregression.

In facing forecasting challenges of seasonality issues, many time series tend to show seasonal behavior as for example, the value of stock prices, company sales data, commodity prices, etc. are likely to fluctuate in certain cycles that take place frequently depending on a particular season. Despite the Box-Jenkins method's intricate procedure, analysis of time series has been adapted to seasonal forecasting problems as nearly any seasonal forecasting method should produce good results (Harrison, 1965). A more recent study also examines how the Box-Jenkins modeling responds to seasonality, whereby in their book Gujarati & Porter (2009) suggests that the seasonal influence can be withdrawn by taking a certain difference order of a variable's historical values and thereafter, choosing the type of ARIMA model to proceed.

2.1.3. Efficient Market Hypothesis

The market condition where all available information are reflected in all traded securities prices is known as an efficient market (Agustin, 2019). Stock market efficiency has its implications for both individual and institutional investors. For instance, money is put into the stock market in forms of investments with the purpose

of generating returns on the invested capital, accumulation of savings, and so forth, but the general thing known to a lot of investors is to try obtaining profitable capital gains by pursuing ways or analyses of how to beat the market (Krugman, 1995, 2009). In the light of institutional investors competing with each other to make the highest investment returns in order to satisfy clients' portfolio performance and the efforts of individual investors in putting their money into rational investments, the efficient market hypothesis (EMH) was put forward by Fama (1970).

The hypothesis states that no one has access to information not already available to everyone else such that no investor owns an advantage over the other in predicting stocks returns. In such conditions, no patterns of investment can be taken into account as fluctuation of stocks prices are random instead of predictable. This randomness of price movements is referred to as 'Random Walk' of prices (Pavlov & Yang, 2010).

Based on the efficient market hypothesis (EMH) developed by Fama (1970), there exists three forms of market efficiency as explained by Pavlov & Yang (2010):

1. Strong efficiency, argues that all private and public information in the stock market are accounted for in a stock price. There is no advantage gainable from any source of information for any investor.
2. Semi-strong efficiency, means that in the market all public information is computed and figured into a stock's price in the current period. There is no approach of analysis, be it a technical nor fundamental analysis, that can pave a way for investors in earning superior capital gains.
3. Weak efficiency, postulates that the market consists of current stocks prices which fully reflect all past prices. Technical analysis of historical trends and patterns is

then unable to forecast future price realization and that beating the market is not feasible.

In today's globalized world, everybody can create connections with anyone across the globe, information is shared, interpreted differently among the readers, and consequently, anyone could react based on the information received in any way he or she prefers to. The same analogy works about in the day-to-day mechanism of a stock market. Indeed, every investor have the same availability to access public information of corporate strategies, market information and statistics, etc., however, there is always insider insights limited to private parties, either only to regulators and/or the concerned corporate personals itself, regarding certain corporations which could drive market sentiments, this in fact would violate the strong market efficiency.

As for semi-strong market efficiency, fundamental analysis of a company based on the most recent financial reports, will generally create a fuzz of short-term excitement or disappointment of the company's stocks prices depending on what the financial reports unfold. As happened often in today's globalized and virtual media platforms, such sentimental information such as a company's latest financial performance tends to be accessible sooner to those with access. Therefore, enabling these beneficiaries of technical or fundamental information to perform investment decision making with a more in-depth analysis compared to what the common investors have by relying only on public information which violates the semi-strong market efficiency.

The weak efficiency of EMH is the hypothesis that this research would try to address through the application of the Box-Jenkins (ARIMA) model in forecasting monthly JKSE prices. Previous studies have analyzed that technical analysis of trends

and patterns observed from past prices is able to predict formulations of prices in the future. Kim & Shamsuddin (2007) examined the market efficiency for Asian stock market in which among the countries observed, results indicated that Indonesia, Philippines, and Malaysia stock markets have not exhibited any signs of market efficiency. This result aligns with a more recent study by Utami (2018) that stated during the global recession of 2008, the stock market of Indonesia (IDX) was inefficient. After the global crisis, the IDX were unstable in between inefficient and efficient depending on the period observed. Gunarso et al., (2017) have also analyzed fluctuations of stocks prices in the IDX and process of random walk were not indicated by the observed stocks prices, inferring issues of autocorrelations within the observed series data.

Referring to the findings from these literatures mentioned beforehand, this research will try to prove the weak form market efficiency by obtaining empirical results from stationarity and autocorrelation tests. Stationarity test result at level implies a series being a random walk process based on the inability to reject the null hypothesis, or in other words the null hypothesis means that the weak form market efficiency holds true. The autocorrelation test results at level will indicate random walk process if the P-value is greater than threshold 0.05 and there exists no significant autocorrelation lags at the 95% confidence level, vice versa. Conclusively, the concerned series data must be stationary at level to prove for a random walk process, implying P-value of unit root test that is not larger than threshold 0.05. If the series was proven to be not stationary at level, the empirical result would indicate the series as not a random walk and that the changes of variable's prices were not random.

2.2. Literature Review

This research utilizes six previous studies as the main literature review for formulating the research background, searching the literature gap, building the quantitative model, and selecting the method of analysis. The six literature reviews were published in the span of the year 2015 until 2022. The six literature reviews explained that there have been many researches and studies pursued to project future realizations of stock market indexes in the IDX and in stock markets overseas. On the other hand, there have been limited numbers of published studies that specifically try to forecast the Jakarta Stock Exchange Composite Index (JKSE) using the ARIMA model based on monthly series observations. Furthermore, the author found no publicly accessible studies of ARIMA model forecasting for the JKSE monthly prices with a training sample from 1990 until 2021 at the time of writing this research.

Previous studies predicting price movements of the JKSE using the Box-Jenkins (ARIMA) method commonly only utilized daily observations of the JKSE series to explain its future outcomes (Haerani & Nugraha, 2022; Pardede, 2019; Wahyudi, 2017; Yenice & Tekindal, 2015). In this window of research gap, the competence of ARIMA modeling in short-term forecasting, or in other words producing forecasted values for a period of less than a year, envisions the author to utilize monthly time series to forecast a ten-month period of JKSE prices in January - October 2022, with a training sample of monthly data from May 1990 to December 2021. The author's decision in taking into account a monthly time series which is rarely used in forecast studies of the JKSE index prices, is expected to shed new light and insights for investors, professionals, policy maker, etc., who are striving for a larger coverage period of training sample and forecast results, whilst ultimately authorizing ARIMA model's

competitiveness in producing short-term projections (Tsay, 2005; Gujarati & Porter, 2009; Meyler et. al., 1998).

This research applies an ARIMA forecasting model with monthly time series data based on a previous framework conducted by Mashadihasanli (2022), that utilized 144 monthly observations into the selected ARIMA (3,1,5) model which significantly projected a 3-month forecast period for the stock market index price of Istanbul. However, a modification of the aforementioned study is conducted in this research whereby the dependent variable, the JKSE time series, is transformed into logarithmic values inspired by Pillay (2020) in which log transformation of the Johannesburg Stock Exchange Index price series was performed and led to a better statistical inference of the ARIMA model’s sample distribution. The following Table 2.1. consists of the summary from the six main literature reviews which are used in the writing of this research.

Table 2.1. Literature Review List

No.	Author, Title, and Research Objective	Methodology and Variable	Findings
1	<p>Shafa Luthfia Sari Haerani & Edwin Setiawan Nugraha (2022) in “ARIMA Model in Predicting Jakarta Composite Index“</p> <p>The study aims to predict the daily price of the Jakarta Composite Index (JCI), also known as the JKSE index, using the ARIMA forecasting model.</p> <p>The forecast period intended in the study were the next 15</p>	<p>The study involves a training sample of 130 daily closed price observations of the JCI index, specifically from June 10th, 2019, to December 6th, 2019.</p> <p>In constructing the predictions of daily Jakarta Composite Index price, the study employs an ARIMA model of;</p> <p>i. $Y_t = c + \alpha_1 Y_{t-1} + \dots + \alpha_p Y_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t + \beta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_q \varepsilon_{t-q}$</p> <p>The study utilizes the variables of Y_t as predicted value of JCI, α as the AR parameter, β as the MA parameter, and ε</p>	<p>Based on the parameter estimation, the best model is chosen, ARIMA (21,1,2), among other candidate models.</p> <p>ARIMA (21,1,2) is selected in the study to forecast JCI index as its RMSE and AIC criteria have the least values, along with the model's confidence interval at 99%.</p>

	market days from the training data period, which were from December 9th, 2019, to January 2nd, 2020.	as the error term. The ARIMA model's stages are performed sequentially, from the identification stage, to parameter estimation process, and eventually diagnostic checking right before the forecast was conducted.	The chosen ARIMA (21,1,2) model used for the predictions of daily JCI index prices has also completed the goodness-of-fit diagnostics, namely the normality and white noise tests.
2.	Setyo Tri Wahyudi (2017) in "The ARIMA Model for the Indonesia Stock Price" The study's objective is to formulate daily predictions of the Indonesia Composite Stock Price Index (CSPI), also known as the JKSE index, through ARIMA modeling. The forecast period is the consecutive 10 market days after the training sample.	The study collected time series data of the daily CSPI closing prices from January 4th, 2010, to December 5th, 2014, which totaled to a training sample of 1,204 observations. The study applies a general form of the ARIMA model; i. $Y_t = c + \alpha_1 Y_{t-1} + \dots + \alpha_p Y_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t + \beta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_q \varepsilon_{t-q}$ The study utilizes the variables of Y_t as stationary value of CSPI, α and β as the model's coefficient of AR and MA, respectively, and ε as the residual. The methodology of the study includes the identification of data patterns in order to achieve stationarity, testing assumptions of the candidate ARIMA models, checking the diagnostics of the selected ARIMA model's significance, and forecasting.	All the stages of the ARIMA forecast model conducted have provided the best model for the study which is ARIMA (0,1,1) based on its lowest AIC criteria. Empirical results of the study indicate that the ARIMA (0,1,1) model has achieved stationarity after the first difference with 99% confidence interval, as well as fulfilling the normality and white noise assumptions.
3.	Tamerlan Mashadihasanli (2022) in "Stock Market Price Forecasting Using the ARIMA Model: An Application to Istanbul, Turkiye" The study aims to solve the challenges that professionals and investors face in projecting monthly movements of the stock market price index through	The study gathered 144 monthly data of the Istanbul stock market price from January 2009 - December 2020 as the training sample to estimate the model. The model used in forecasting SPI monthly prices in the study is; i. $\Delta dY_t = c + \alpha_1 \Delta dY_{t-1} + \dots + \alpha_p \Delta dY_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t + \beta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_q \varepsilon_{t-q}$	Identification and parameter estimation processes provided the best model among others in the study, which the ARIMA (3,1,5) is selected based on least information criterion values, largest adjusted R-squared, and parameter significance tests. The diagnostic test results

	<p>the application of the ARIMA model. Specifically, the study analyzed and forecasted the Istanbul stock market price (SPI).</p> <p>The testing period of forecast in the study is the first three months of the calendar year, January 2021 - March 2021.</p>	<p>The variables of ΔdY_t indicates a differenced dependent variable, α and β indicate the model's coefficient of AR and MA, respectively, ΔdY_{t-1} and ΔdY_{t-p} indicate the lagged dependent variables, ε_{t-1} and ε_{t-q} indicate the residual previous values, and ε indicates the residual term.</p>	<p>of the selected model of ARIMA (3,1,5) indicate normal distribution, no heteroskedasticity and serial correlation, along with achieving ARIMA's process invertibility.</p> <p>Static and dynamic forecasts are performed and the static forecast is chosen as the final forecast values, since it produces the highest prediction accuracy with the least RMSE values.</p>
4.	<p>Sedat Yenice & Mustafa Agah Tekindal (2015) in "Forecasting the Stock Indexes of Fragile Five Countries through Box-Jenkins Methods"</p> <p>The study aims to forecast the daily closing values of the major stock indexes of Brazil, India, Indonesia, South Africa, and Turkey, using the Box-Jenkins method.</p> <p>The forecasted period of the study is a 90-day period from January 1st, 2015, to March 31st, 2015.</p>	<p>The study consists of a dataset of 3-year period daily closing prices of the major indexes for the five countries between January 1st, 2012, to December 31st, 2014.</p> <p>In forecasting the stock market indexes, the study utilizes an ARIMA model as the following;</p> <p>i. $Y_t = c + \alpha_1 Y_{t-1} + \dots + \alpha_p Y_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t - \beta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} - \dots - \beta_q \varepsilon_{t-q}$</p> <p>Whereby the variables of Y_t represents the initial time series differenced at d degree, α as the AR parameter, β as the MA parameter, and ε as the error term coefficient.</p> <p>The study's methodology establishes the Box-Jenkins ARIMA model through its four main stages, namely; the model identification; the parameters and diagnostic estimations; the ARIMA model forecasting; and the compliance tests of the forecasted results.</p>	<p>The study transforms the original time series of the five stock market indexes into logarithmic functions, since the original time series exhibited non-normal distribution and high variance of the samples.</p> <p>The logarithmic transformation and first differencing processes managed to attain stationarity and normal distribution within the models. Based on parameter estimation of the ACF and PACF, the ARIMA (3,1,0) is selected as the best model for forecasting, specifically for the stock market index of Indonesia (JKSE).</p> <p>The ARIMA (3,1,0) fulfilled the diagnostic checking tests and produced a forecast</p>

			accuracy of 74.29% for the testing period.
5.	<p>Paiaman Pardede (2019) in “Application of the ARIMA Model in Predicting the Indonesia-Jakarta Composite Stock Index Price“</p> <p>Titled in Bahasa Indonesia “Penerapan Model ARIMA dalam Memprediksi Indeks Harga Saham Gabungan Bursa Efek Indonesia-Jakarta “</p> <p>The study’s objective was to determine the most adequate ARIMA model to forecast daily JKSE prices.</p> <p>The forecast period in the study consisted of the last 10 days of the sample population.</p>	<p>The study used 226 daily observations of the JKSE closing prices from January 2nd, 2015, to December 1st, 2015, that would be a training sample to estimate the model.</p> <p>The study performs a general form of the ARIMA model;</p> <p>i. $Y_t = c + \alpha_1 Y_{t-1} + \dots + \alpha_p Y_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t + \beta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_q \varepsilon_{t-q}$</p> <p>utilizing the variables of Y_t as stationary value of JKSE, α and β as the model’s coefficient of AR and MA, respectively, c as the constant, and ε as the residual.</p> <p>The methodological approach of the study involves four main stages of the ARIMA modeling which are identification, parameter estimation, diagnostic checking, and forecasting.</p>	<p>Based on results of the identification and parameter estimation stages, the ARIMA (2,1,2) is selected as the best model to explain the data in forecasting, with the least standard error and AIC criteria compared to other possible models.</p> <p>The ARIMA (2,1,2) model indicates no autocorrelation issues, which is desirable for an ARIMA forecasting model.</p> <p>The forecast results are significantly close to the actual values of JKSE in the testing period. It was indicated that static forecast produced better outcomes than dynamic forecast, based on the accuracy rated with RMSE and MAE.</p>
6.	<p>Surendran Pillay (2020) in “Determining the Optimal ARIMA Model for Forecasting the Share Price Index of the Johannesburg Stock Exchange“</p> <p>The objective of the study is to decide the optimal ARIMA model in constructing a sound forecast of the Johannesburg Stock Exchange Index prices, based on quantitative approaches of the Box-</p>	<p>The study’s dataset includes a time series of the Johannesburg Stock Exchange Index’s daily closing price, opening price, high price, and low price from August 1st, 2019, to July 31st, 2020. The time series contains 251 daily observations serving as the training sample for model estimation.</p> <p>The study employs an ARIMA model as in the following;</p> <p>i. $Y_t = c + \alpha_1 Y_{t-1} + \dots + \alpha_p Y_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t + \beta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_q \varepsilon_{t-q}$</p>	<p>The time series used in the study exhibits non-stationarity such that a random walk pattern is noted. In order to provide statistical inference, the series would undergo log transformation and first differencing processes.</p> <p>The first order differing and a log transformation managed to achieve stationarity within the</p>

<p>Jenkins method.</p> <p>The testing sample being forecasted in the study are daily index prices from working days in January 2021 to October 2022, which the daily forecasts are concluded into monthly forecasts of the testing period, as per the predicted index closing prices for each month.</p>	<p>Whereby Y_t represents the stationary value of the Johannesburg Stock Exchange Index prices, c as the constant or intercept, α and β represent the model's coefficient of AR and MA, respectively, and ε as the random error.</p> <p>The methodology of the study involves identification stage to visualize the time series and determine its stationarity, parameter estimation stage to construct the ARIMA model with significant operators, diagnostic checking stage to analyze whether the model fits the data, and forecasting to obtain the expected prediction results.</p>	<p>series. Subsequently, the parameter estimations indicated that ARIMA (4,1,4) is the best model compared to other possible ones, based on the AIC criteria and accuracy rates of RMSE, MAPE, MAE.</p> <p>The ARIMA (4,1,4) also fits the data such that homoskedasticity and normality of the residuals are achieved based on the Q-Q plot.</p> <p>The forecasted results are statistically significant to predict the monthly index price movements for a period of January 2021 to October 2022.</p>
--	--	--

2.3. Hypothesis

Based on the theoretical framework and literature review of previous studies that have been discussed earlier, the hypotheses of this research are as the following:

1. The autoregressive (AR) and moving average (MA) indicators of the ARIMA model are expected to significantly affect formulations of the JKSE monthly values during the testing period, by processing the JKSE series monthly data from the training period. This hypothesis is enacted due to AR and MA components' purpose in the model, such that the AR indicator projects future values relying on the preceding values of the index and the MA indicator projects future values based on the stochastic error values of the index in both current and past periods.

2. The ARIMA model's capability in forecasting monthly JKSE prices by employing historical values of the index itself to describe future realizations is expected to be soundly viable with significant empirical results by fulfilling model tests of goodness-of-fit measures. This hypothesis tries to counter the notable propositions against predicting future movements of stock markets, such as the Random Walk Theory by Malkiel (1973) that argues historical prices of stocks and stock indexes are not useful in predicting future prices and the Efficient Market Hypothesis by Fama (1970) that argues all information in the market are already priced in to the current stocks and stock indexes prices, hence, past prices are not explanatory to realizations of prices in the future.
3. The projection of the JKSE monthly prices in the testing period is expected to undergo a positive trend, as the author argues that the index's historical price movement patterns and trends can indeed lay out applicable tendencies of its future movements. The supporting arguments for this hypothesis are the overall positive trend of the index during the training period and the index's rebound patterns observed in its price recoveries from the previous noteworthy global stock market downturns, such as the 2020 global pandemic; the great recession of 2008; and the Asian financial crisis of 1997.
4. The projected outcomes of the JKSE monthly prices in the testing period, spanning from January to October 2022, are expected to be a forecast that is also providing an opportunity of capital gains, assuming that investors are planning to invest or have already acquired investment in the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) during the training period, and are looking to increase their portfolios' value through the projected increase of their investments in the testing period.

CHAPTER III

RESEARCH METHOD

3.1. Research Design

The purpose of creating this research is to forecast a ten-month period of the JKSE monthly prices, by analyzing its own historical values which is a time series data of the JKSE monthly prices in a given training period, using the ARIMA model for forecasting time series data. This research tries to pursue a forecast analysis of one selected stock market, that is the Indonesia's stock market or the IDX, with the JKSE index as the focus of study, because the index generally represents performance of the stock market as a whole. That being said, this research employs a univariate time series data of the JKSE prices as the samples, which include the index's monthly prices in a 32-year period of observations, namely from May, 1990, to December, 2021, an equivalent of 380 research observations for the training samples. The predicted JKSE monthly prices of the forecasting model are then compared with the actual JKSE monthly prices' realization in a testing period that spans from January to October, 2022, equaling 10 research observations for the testing samples. Therefore, in total this research utilizes 390 research observations. The hypotheses of this research are examined using a quantitative method of time series forecasting, the Box-Jenkins (ARIMA) method, through one selected best ARIMA model among all other candidate ARIMA models. Whereby the chosen ARIMA model should satisfy the method's measures of identification, parameter estimation, and diagnostic checking, in order to produce adequate and significant forecast results.

To perform the objective of this research, time series regression analysis is carried out whereby it is defined as a method used for predicting future outcomes of a variable based on the variable's outcomes in the past, such that its historical information is processed with predictors of a specific time series analysis approach. In accordance with this research's variable of study that is a stock index price, time series regression analysis is beneficial for dealing with data that contains recurring patterns and trends, so that it can be helpful in analyzing how the data changes over a certain period of time (Gujarati & Porter, 2009). Acknowledging seasonal behavior that is often exhibited by time series data such as stock index prices, an approach to time series regression analysis that is the ARIMA method is performed in this research, as the method is able to eliminate the presence of trends and patterns by applying a differencing process to the series. The differencing process is a crucial part of the ARIMA modeling since it serves the series data to be stationary, meaning that the time series' properties of autocorrelation, mean, and variance that don't vary in time. Similar to this research's usage of ARIMA method, previous studies have also utilized the method's strength in regressing time series data for forecasting analysis (Sadeq, 2008; Eke, 2019; Taneja, 2019; Jansson & Larsson, 2020). Based on this research's background and hypotheses, the research model is formed as follows:

$$JKSE_t = c + \alpha_p JKSE_{t-p} + \beta_q \varepsilon_{t-q} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3.1)$$

Equation 3.1 shows that $JKSE_t$ is a dependent variable of the model which is representing the value of the Jakarta Stock Exchange Composite Index (JKSE) price at time t , whereby t indicates the month period. On the other hand, independent variables of the model are the past values of the dependent variable itself, namely $JKSE_{t-p}$ which is the lagged previous value of $JKSE$ at time $t - p$ and ε_{t-q} which is the error value of $JKSE$ at time $t - q$. In incorporating

future values of the dependent variable, the independent variables predictors are noted with the autoregressive orders indicated by p and the moving average orders indicated by q , respectively. Equation 3.1 is based on the general form of the ARIMA model, as for the comprehensive model to project JKSE monthly prices in this research is;

$$lJKSE_t = c + \alpha_1 lJKSE_{t-1} + \dots + \alpha_p lJKSE_{t-p} + \beta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_q \varepsilon_{t-q} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3.2)$$

Whereby equation 3.2 shows that the price of JKSE index at month t is formulated by the lagged historical monthly prices of the JKSE series at time $t - 1$ to time $t - p$, the lagged error values of the JKSE series at time $t - 1$ to time $t - q$, and the current lagged error values at time t . The formulation of this model is by assuming that the stationary state of the JKSE series was achieved prior to any forecast modeling of the data, such that the series' properties remain constant over time (Tsay, 2005). The transformation of the dependent variable's original series values into logarithmic function is also conducted to de-trend or smooth the data, since the initial series values exhibited significant and continuous growth for the course of the observation period which intuitively high variance and non-normal data distribution.

The author's considerations in modeling time series data that undergo logarithmic transformation for projecting future movements of the JKSE prices using the Box-Jenkins forecasting framework, are elicited from several models performed by previous studies. Yenice & Tekindal (2015) conducted forecasts of five stock market indexes using the ARIMA model in which among them is the JKSE index and proved that logarithmic transformation of the stock indexes' series manages to handle issues of non-normal distribution and unstable variance of all the five indexes data, resulting in ample predictions of the indexes as compared to their actual fluctuations. This design of this research also refers to the work of Pillay (2020) that brought evidence of better model fitting measure results by transforming the

Johannesburg Stock Exchange Index price series into logarithmic values in the ARIMA modeling when compared to processing the model with the series that is in actual values form. Another model modification that this research pursues is the utilization of monthly intervals as the type of data observation that is not found from previous studies, which too conducted ARIMA forecast analysis for the JKSE prices by Wahyudi (2017) and Pardede (2019), because the aforementioned studies employed daily intervals for the observation of the JKSE series. Therefore, the author of this research tries to efficiently handle large fluctuations of the JKSE prices, specifically the price ranges in the 1990s compared with the price ranges in the 2010s as simply shown in Figure 1.1, by modifying the dependent variable through log transformation of the JKSE monthly prices in order to increase the likelihood of producing accurate and satisfactory forecast results.

3.2. Operational Variable Definitions

3.2.1. Dependent Variable

This research tries to formulate out-of-sample projections of the JKSE monthly prices in a given testing period, by utilizing a dependent variable that is a time series data of the past JKSE monthly prices in the observed or training period which is transfigured into logarithmic values to the base 10. Therefore, the inscription of the dependent variable is through the following;

$$lJKSE_t = \log_{10}(JKSE_t) \quad (3.3)$$

Whereby $lJKSE_t$ as the dependent variable of this research's model is described such that every price value in the JKSE series at month t is transformed from actual values into \log_{10} values. The stock index price of JKSE is generally defined as a sum of all

the listed stocks' prices in the IDX calculated by a weighted average of all the shares prices within the index (IDX, 2023). This research utilizes the close price of the JKSE index on every first day of the month throughout the observations, which account for the term monthly intervals of the series. Hence, this research modeling process states the dependent variable in logarithm units, based on transformation from its actual unit prices, Rupiah per share, and the series data are collected from the official website of Yahoo Finance.

3.2.2. Independent Variable

The role of independent variables in the ARIMA forecasting model of this research is accommodated by past information of the dependent variable itself. In applying an ARIMA model to forecast a time series variable, future predictions of the series are basically described by its lagged series values from previous periods and residual errors from current and previous periods (Etuk et al., 2012). It implies that the projected future values of a variable are achieved through a linear function of differenced lagged past observations and stochastic errors of the variable (Pillay, 2020). Hence, the independent variables of this research's model are explained as follows;

$$lJKSE_{t-p} = \{lJKSE_{t-1}, \dots, lJKSE_{t-p}\} \quad (3.4)$$

$$\varepsilon_{t-q} = \{\varepsilon_{t-q}, \dots, \varepsilon_{t-q}\} \quad (3.5)$$

The first independent variable is shown in equation 3.4, that is the lag values of the JKSE series from period $t - 1$ until $t - p$, in which the number of autoregressive (AR) orders used are indicated by p . The independent variable of $JKSE_{t-p}$ is also referred

to as the AR regressor that projects future values by regressing the response variable on its own proportion values in previous observations. The second independent variable is depicted in equation 3.5, that is the error values of the JKSE series from the current period until q number of past periods, in which the number of moving average (MA) orders used are exhibited by q . Hence, the MA regressor or ε_{t-q} , projects future outcomes by regressing the response variable's error terms that simultaneously occur at the current and past observations.

Conclusively, the operational variable definitions for the dependent and independent variables, along with the variables' units and sources are described in the Table 3.1;

Table 3.1. Operational Variable Definitions and Data Source

Variable	Information	Unit	Source
$lJKSE_t$	Time series of the JKSE monthly prices transformed into log_{10} values.	Logarithm	Yahoo Finance
$lJKSE_{t-p}$	Log of the lagged historical JKSE monthly prices in past observations.	Logarithm	Yahoo Finance
ε_{t-q}	Residual errors of the $lJKSE_t$ in current and past observations.	Logarithm	Yahoo Finance

3.3. Population and Sample

The objective of this research is to conduct empirical tests to prove whether the hypotheses apply for the forecast analysis of the JKSE monthly prices. This research uses a population of 32 and a half years of time series observations of the JKSE prices whereby the sample interval selected is the monthly interval. The period of this research's observations is specifically

counted from May, 1990 - October, 2022, amounting a total of 390 monthly observations as listed in Appendix I. In modeling the data, this research divides the population into two categories of samples, that include a training sample and a testing sample. The samples data collected for this research are based on the following criteria;

- i. The time series data chosen as this research's variable is the Jakarta Stock Exchange Composite Index (JKSE) prices since it is the major stock index of the Indonesian Stock Exchange (IDX).
- ii. During the period of this research, the JKSE index contains time series data related to econometrics models from the month of May 1990, until October 2022, and has the fitting of data that is available to be accessed publicly.
- iii. The selection of samples is based on the earliest available data of the JKSE monthly prices in Yahoo Finance's open stock market data, which was the data from May 1990, to the time of this research's writing process, which was in October 2022.
- iv. This research utilizes 380 training samples of the JKSE monthly prices from May 1990 to December 2021 that are going to be processed in the ARIMA model, to produce out-of-sample monthly projections of the index prices.
- v. The forecasted projections of the JKSE monthly prices from the ARIMA model are compared with the testing samples consisting of 10 actual monthly prices of the index from January to October 2022.

The following Table 3.2 presents the sample data classification by period for the modeling of this research;

Table 3.2. Research Samples Periods

JKSE Monthly Prices Time Series

Samples	Periods	Observations
Training Samples	May 1990 - December 2021	380
Testing Samples	January 2022 - October 2022	10
Total Observations		390

3.4. Research Instrument

Research instruments are measures of data collection regarding an idea of research interest (Roberts & Stone, 2003). It is implied that research instruments are tools used to gather quantitative data of a variable to be analyzed in studying certain phenomena. In this research, the instruments used to collect secondary data are credible sources such Yahoo Finance, World Bank, Trading Economics, official website of the IDX, etc. The main secondary data processed in the forecast modeling of this research is the JKSE monthly prices time series collected from Yahoo Finance. As for other secondary data used for discussions in this research regarding the topic of stock market index forecast study are collected from the IDX's official website, Trading Economics, and World Bank.

3.5. Data Collection Technique

In collecting required data for a research, data collection technique is a systematic step that is done according to the subject of interest that a researcher is trying to focus on. This research applies data collection technique of convenient sampling, in which this technique means that a specific data for a certain period is assembled to be analyzed in the research (Soemantri & Setiawan, 2017). Particularly in the field of stock market study, this research collected

secondary data from trustworthy sources including Yahoo Finance, Trading Economics, World Bank, IDX's website, etc. Other than referring to previous studies in selecting and modifying variable of the forecast model, this research employs monthly samples as the author believes utilization of monthly intervals in ARIMA modeling would enable a coverage of longer period of time for both the training and testing samples, for the same number of observations compared to ARIMA models with smaller interval such as daily or hourly. The procedure in collecting data in this research is explained as follows;

- i. Literature study was conducted by reviewing and examining previous studies that relate to this research and afterwards, research modifications were made based on the literature review. This procedure was done so that the author comprehends the literature gap and research problems which lead to solutions of the related issues.
- ii. Field study that involves conducting observations and gathering the quantitative data was pursued through documentation of the secondary data used in this research modeling. After the secondary data was collected from reliable sources, the data was then examined to avoid any false data entry and analyzed according to the methodology used in this research, in order to obtain reliable statistical results.

3.6. Data Analysis Technique

The next step after collecting the data is to conduct data analysis according to the research design and issues that are going to be studied. This research utilizes time series regression for a forecast analysis whereby the regression process revolves around the characteristics of time series data. Referring to the study of Box et al., (2015), time series is a kind of data consisting of an assemblage of observations taken sequentially over a certain period of time. A key

objective in handling time series data is to analyze the dependency of adjacent observations, such that the value of one observation is the direct predecessor of the other consecutive observation. The JKSE index price as the focus variable of this research is categorized as time series data, whereby Baresa et al., (2013) emphasizes that practically stocks and stock indices prices tend to fluctuate from one period to another following the general performance of the specific stock market which gradually create trends and patterns of price movements formed in a certain period. Therefore, in fulfilling this research objective of formulating projection of the JKSE prices, an approach to time series analysis must also accommodate the recurring existence of trends and patterns of the index prices.

A method that has been proved to be precise in projecting future outcomes of a time series variable is the Box-Jenkins method which operates in an autoregressive integrated moving average model, familiarly known as the ARIMA (p,d,q) model (Taneja, 2019). In analyzing time series data, the ARIMA methodology operates on the mechanism of expressing the dependent variable, for instance Y_t , using historical values of the variable Y itself over a certain period of the series. To remove seasonality and trends associated with the series values formulations, the ARIMA (p,d,q) model conducts a differencing process of the concerned series. The differencing process molds the initial non-stationary series into a stationary state which stabilizes the series variances to be constant over different time periods of observation. Thoroughly, according to Gujarati & Porter (2009) the definitions of p , d , q , orders in the ARIMA (p,d,q) model are explained whereby; p represents the number of autoregressive (AR) terms; d indicates the number of differencing orders of the time series before it becomes stationary; and q denotes the number of moving average (MA) terms.

The Box-Jenkins framework of forecasting models operates based on two main assumptions, which are the assumptions of stationarity and invertibility. The former assumption is used for the AR process, requiring the stationarity state of a time series data to be achieved such that the series exhibits values closer to the mean and time-invariant variance (Box et al., 2015). Because on the contrary, a non-stationary time series such as stock index prices often exhibit prices that range further from the mean especially in a longer period of observation and its variance changes over time. The assumption of stationarity is a requisite for constructing a strong basis of time series forecast as the series must be stable over past and future periods, to enable the model to significantly estimate and forecast future realizations (Pardede, 2019). The latter assumption, invertibility, is used for the MA process which is the counterpart to stationarity due to the basic principle of invertibility, that is whether the errors or noises can be inverted into a description of observations in the past (Tsay, 2005). Invertibility of a series is important such that a finite MA order can represent the series and the autocorrelation properties of the series can identify possible ARIMA models to work with (Box et al., 2015). Following the invertibility assumption implies that ARIMA models which consist of both AR and MA components can be expressed as autoregressive models to approximate the series.

By first complying with both assumptions of stationarity and invertibility in performing Box-Jenkins forecasting models, researchers can proceed to further iteratively analyze the time series data and estimate the forecasting results. The Box-Jenkins method performs time series forecast analysis through its four model processes which include (i) the autoregressive model, (ii) the moving average model, (iii) the autoregressive moving average model, and (iv) autoregressive integrated moving average model. Research can pursue time series forecast

modeling by applying either of the autoregressive or moving average processes, or also a combination of both, depending on the different properties of the time series data that is studied. The four models of the Box-Jenkins method are explained in the following sub-chapters.

3.6.1. Autoregressive (AR) Model

Forecasting a series using the AR model describes the present values of a dependent variable which depends on its preceding values and a random shock (Wei, 2006). It is inferred that this model is a result of regression with its own variable. The denotation of an AR model is based on the p order thus, the term AR (p) is created. The general form of the AR (p) model is specified as (Wei, 2006):

$$Y_t = \alpha_1 Y_{t-1} + \dots + \alpha_p Y_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3.6)$$

Where:

- Y_t : value of the series at time t
- α_1 : 1st-order autoregressive parameter
- α_p : p^{th} -order autoregressive parameter
- Y_{t-1} : historical value of the series at time $t - 1$
- Y_{t-p} : historical value of the series at time $t - p$
- p : autoregressive order
- ε_t : value of error at time t

Equation 3.6 states that the value of Y at time t relies on its historical values from the previous period and an error term. For instance, if an AR(1) model or a first-order autoregressive is to be followed, then the forecast value of Y_t is expressed by a proportion of Y_{t-1} or its historical value at time $t - 1$, plus an error term ε_t or shock at

time t , with the integer of $p = 1$ indicating the use of 1st-order AR parameter (Gujarati & Porter, 2009). The model equation for an AR(1) process can therefore be written as Equation 3.7 below:

$$Y_t = \alpha_1 Y_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3.7)$$

Generalizing the AR model, more lags of the series can be included such that the degree of AR parameter or p , indicates the number of significant lags in the dependent variable's series. In essence, an AR(p) model in Equation 3.6 implies that the value of Y at time t is explained by proportion of the series past values with p number of lags; $t - 1, \dots$, until $t - p$, plus a random shock at time t .

3.6.2. Moving Average (MA) Model

Forecasting a series using the MA model relies on the values of white noise stochastic error in the current and previous periods (Haerani & Nugraha, 2022). It can be inferred that if a stationary time series is a linear function of the stochastic error values in the present and past periods consecutively, then forecasting the series operates through the MA model. The denotation of a MA model is MA (q), whereby q is the order of moving average in the model. In this understanding, the general form of the MA (q) model is explained as (Hyndman & Athanasopoulos, 2018):

$$Y_t = \varepsilon + \beta_0 \varepsilon_t + \beta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_q \varepsilon_{t-q} \quad (3.8)$$

Where:

Y_t : value of the series at time t

ε : constant

β_0 : moving average parameter in current period

β_1 : 1st-order moving average parameter

β_q : q^{th} -order moving average parameter

ε_t : value of stochastic error at time t

ε_{t-1} : value of stochastic error at time $t - 1$

ε_{t-q} : value of stochastic error at time $t - q$

q : moving average order

The general approach of MA model as shown in Equation 3.8 describes the value of Y at time t to be equal to a constant which is ε plus the moving average of current error value and a moving average past stochastic error values at time $t - 1$ until time $t - q$. If specifically a MA model consists of two lag error terms, the MA(2) model equation is expressed as follows:

$$Y_t = \varepsilon + \beta_0 \varepsilon_t + \beta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} + \beta_2 \varepsilon_{t-2} \quad (3.9)$$

Equation 3.9 states that the value of Y at time t is explained by the values of moving average stochastic error terms in the first lag $t - 1$ and the second lag $t - 2$, plus a constant that is ε . Concisely, according to the study of Gujarati & Porter (2009) the modeling of a MA process is basically a linear combination of white noise stochastic error terms.

3.6.3. Autoregressive Moving Average (ARMA) Model

The ARMA model explains the behavior of a time series by combining two models' distinct perspectives of AR and MA processes. When a time series has both autoregressive and moving average characteristics, modeling the time series to forecast future outcomes can be suited with the ARMA model. It is denoted by ARMA (p, q)

whereby p and q are the autoregressive and moving average terms, respectively. The ARMA (p,q) model's general form is designated as (Cryer & Chan, 2008):

$$Y_t = \alpha_1 Y_{t-1} + \dots + \alpha_p Y_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t + \beta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_q \varepsilon_{t-q} \quad (3.10)$$

Where:

- Y_t : value of the series at time t
- Y_{t-1} : historical value of the series at time $t - 1$
- Y_{t-p} : historical value of the series at time $t - p$
- α_1 : 1st-order autoregressive parameter
- α_p : p^{th} -order autoregressive parameter
- ε_t : value of error at time t
- ε_{t-1} : value of stochastic error at time $t - 1$
- ε_{t-q} : value of stochastic error at time $t - q$
- β_1 : 1st-order moving average parameter
- β_q : q^{th} -order moving average parameter
- p : autoregressive order
- q : moving average order

The general form of ARMA model shown in Equation 3.10 explains that the value of Y at time t is equal to proportions of the series historical values at time $t - 1$ until $t - p$, plus moving average of the stochastic error values at lag $t - 1$ until lag $t - q$, and plus a stochastic error value at time t . The ARMA model can be utilized to forecast future realizations of a time series that has already achieved stationarity prior to any differencing process, meaning that the movements of the series values are no longer showing any trends, be it an upward or a downward trend (Pohan, 2022). On the

contrary, if the original time series shows indications of trend patterns, a differencing process of the time series must be conducted to achieve stationarity prior to modeling forecasts of the series. Hence, an integrated version of the original ARMA model can be suited to forecast a time series with trends, and such a model is known as the autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) model.

3.6.4. Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) Model

The Box-Jenkins methodology in forms of AR, MA, and ARMA models rely on the assumption that the time series incorporated in the selected model are inherently stationary prior to procession of the model analysis (Pokorny, 1987). The stationary state assumed that the time series has a time-invariant covariance, as well as its mean and variance that are constant (Gujarati & Porter, 2009). Whereas in the real-world situations, time series data tend to exhibit signs of trends and/or seasonal patterns (Sadeq, 2008). Therefore, in producing statistically significant and accurate forecast results of a non-stationary time series, a differencing process can be conducted to obtain stationary time series data, which is required for any Box-Jenkins model in offering a well-grounded basis for forecasting with a stabilized series data. Through this comprehension, the ARIMA model is based on the approach of ARMA model with a time series that has to be differenced as many as d amount of order differencing, in order to remove the trend and seasonality (Haerani & Nugraha, 2022). The denotation of ARIMA model is ARIMA (p,d,q) , whereby p states the the AR model's degree, d states the difference order's degree, and q states the MA model's degree (Chang, Sriboonchitta, & Wiboonpongse, 2009). The general form of the ARIMA (p,d,q) is expressed as (Mashadihasanli, 2022):

$$\Delta dY_t = c + \alpha_1 \Delta dY_{t-1} + \dots + \alpha_p \Delta dY_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t + \beta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_q \varepsilon_{t-q} \quad (3.11)$$

Where:

ΔdY_t : differenced dependent variable value of the series at time t

ΔdY_{t-1} : differenced lagged historical value of the series at time $t - 1$

ΔdY_{t-p} : differenced lagged historical value of the series at time $t - p$

α_1 : 1st-order autoregressive parameter

α_p : p^{th} -order autoregressive parameter

ε_t : value of error at time t

ε_{t-1} : value of stochastic error at time $t - 1$

ε_{t-q} : value of stochastic error at time $t - q$

β_1 : 1st-order moving average parameter

β_q : q^{th} -order moving average parameter

p : autoregressive order

q : moving average order

c : constant

The general form of the ARIMA (p,d,q) model in Equation 3.11 explains that the value of ΔdY at time t is the sum of the differenced lagged series values at time $t - 1$ until $t - p$, moving average of the stochastic error values at lag $t - 1$ until lag $t - q$, a constant, and a stochastic error value at time t . It implies that the future value of a variable is achieved through a linear function of differenced lagged past observations and stochastic errors of the variable (Pillay, 2020). The ARIMA method can be useful especially to model a non-stationary time series by applying the differencing process into the time series of an ARIMA (p,d,q) modeling (Sartono, 2006). Furthermore, the

ARIMA method is most popularly known for forecasting financial models (Pai & Lin, 2005; Meth et al., 2010).

3.7. Model Identification

After understanding the model forms and main assumptions of the Box-Jenkins method in forecasting time series data, this research starts to analyze the series data characteristics in the first step of the method, namely the model identification stage. The identification stage is conducted to figure out suitable values of the model's p , d , and q values such that one model process between the options of AR(p) model; MA(q) model; ARMA(p,q) model; and ARIMA(p,d,q); is selected to process the series. It is pursued by analyzing whether the series has achieved stationarity, if otherwise then the series has to be differenced for a d number of differencing order. Afterwards, the correlogram table of the stationary time series is carefully examined to identify possible significant autocorrelation lags which will indicate the components of AR and MA for the forecasting model.

3.7.1. Stationarity Test

The aim of testing for stationarity of a time series prior to modeling the series using the ARIMA approach, is to ensure that there is time-invariant mean and variances of the series. Achieving stationarity means that the series values are stabilized such that seasonality occurrences of trends and patterns are eliminated and obtaining the assumption of stationarity is in fact required for producing accurate forecasts. To check the stationarity of a series, this research conducts the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test with the hypotheses as follows;

$$H_0 = \text{Series has a unit root}$$

$$H_1 = \text{Series has no unit root}$$

Whereby according to Dickey & Fuller, (1979), if the ADF unit root test results at level indicate P-value < 0.05 and $|\text{critical value}| < |\text{t-statistics}|$, we can reject the null hypothesis meaning that the series does not have a unit root which implies stationarity and random walk state of the series. In this case of stationarity, the series can be directly processed without any series differencing process through either AR model or MA model, or a combination of both that is an ARMA model. Conversely, if the ADF unit root test result at level indicate P-value > 0.05 and $|\text{critical value}| > |\text{t-statistics}|$, we do not reject the null hypothesis meaning that the series has a unit root which implies a non-stationary series that is not a random walk process.

In response to if the ADF unit root test results exhibited conditions of non-stationarity as is the most common case in analyzing time series data, this research will firstly transform the variable's series actual values into logarithm to the base 10 in accordance with Equation 3.3, in order to smooth the impacts of unstable variances in the series' initial actual values. And after that, this research will perform first difference process following the simple stochastic non-stationary model by Brooks, (2014);

$$y_t = \phi y_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3.12)$$

Whereby if $\phi = 1$, the series is assumed to be non-stationary and by assuming that the series reaches stationarity after a first-order differencing;

$$\Delta y_t = y_t - y_{t-1} \quad (3.13)$$

Then, the Equation 3.12 is substituted into the Equation 3.13 to express stationarity;

$$y_t - y_{t-1} = y_{t-1} - y_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t$$

$$\Delta y_t = \varepsilon_t \quad (3.14)$$

As a result, the Equation 3.14 indicates the series is stationary such that its mean, variances, and autocorrelation are constant over time during the observation period (Maddala, 1992).

3.7.2. Autocorrelation Functions Analysis

The correlogram table of a time series in the ARIMA model contains properties of autocorrelation function (ACF) used for determining the orders of MA components, or the values of q , and partial autocorrelation function (PACF) used for determining the orders of AR components, or the values of p . Basically, the correlogram table depicts plots of ACF and PACF in opposition to length of the lags (Gujarati & Porter, 2009). The pre-determination of p and q values in ARIMA(p,d,q) models can also be indicated whereby if the ACF and PACF lags in the correlogram do not tail off such the ACF coefficients remain close to one over various lags, in this regard time series data is non-stationary at level. With a given time series data, the ARIMA methodology responds by taking d number of differencing order until the series is stationary. The model identification is finally concluded by determining the possible components of AR and MA orders based on the statistical significance of the ACF and PACF lags at d level of difference. It can be done in two ways, visually and theoretically as explained below:

- i. Identifying the model visually, the statistical significance of ACF lags determine the possible MA orders such that the ACF lags cross Bartlett's significance line and possible AR orders are exhibited as the PACF lags cross Bartlett's significance line.

I.e., significant ACF lags at lag 1, 3, 5, indicate orders of MA(1), MA(3), and MA(5) that are going to estimate the series data. Same goes for the PACF, i.e., significant PACF lags at lag 1, 2, 5, indicate orders of AR(1), AR(2), AR(5).

- ii. Theoretically, we can figure out the statistical significance ACF and PACF lags for finding out possible AR and MA orders by analyzing if the ACF or PACF sample autocorrelation coefficients values for any true population mean $\hat{\rho}_k$ are smaller and equal to the standard normal distribution, or the autocorrelation coefficients are larger and equal to the standard normal distribution. Gujarati & Porter (2009) explained that the standard error of any true $\hat{\rho}_k$ can assess for its statistical significance through the following;

$$\hat{\rho}_k \cong N \tag{3.15}$$

Where $N = (1/n)$

By assuming the autocorrelation coefficients are normally distributed with zero mean, hence, variance N equals to one divided by the sample size n . The result of Equation 3.15 is the standard error (SE) and we take the root of the SE, to obtain the value of standard error for population distribution \sqrt{SE} . In accordance to the 95 percent confidence interval for any $\hat{\rho}_k$ in a normal distribution we calculate for;

$$\hat{\rho}_k \pm 1.96(\sqrt{SE}) = \hat{\rho}_k \pm x \tag{3.16}$$

Where $x = 1.96(\sqrt{SE})$ and as such, we get the 95 percent confidence interval lower limit and upper limit for $\hat{\rho}_k$;

$$[(\hat{\rho}_k - x), (\hat{\rho}_k + x)] \tag{3.17}$$

Therefore, we are 95 percent confident that the estimated autocorrelation coefficient values for every $\hat{\rho}_k$ are significantly different from zero, meaning that i.e. PACF coefficient value at lag 1 is statistically significant, then we are 95 percent confident that the population mean lies within the confidence interval at lag 1 implying AR(1) as a candidate component in the ARIMA model. The same comprehension applies for the ACF coefficient value at lag k that is possible to accommodate the use of MA(k).

3.8. Parameter Estimation

The parameters estimation stage processes the suitable values of autoregressive components that are AR(p), and moving average components that are MA(q), through the model selection criteria in which a best model would be chosen based on the best statistical information of its components. In choosing the best model among other potential models identified from the values of p and q in the previous stage of Box-Jenkins methodology, this stage of parameters estimation analyzes the significance of AR and MA variables. After that this stage compares; Akaike information criterion (AIC); Schwarz information criterion (SIC) or also abbreviated as (SC) in the statistics software used for this research; and; R-squared statistics of all candidate ARIMA models. In addition to the common approaches of parameter estimation in the ARIMA method, this research conducts error evaluations of all candidate models as another consideration in selecting the best ARIMA model to work with.

3.8.1. Parameter Significance Estimation

In the Box-Jenkins methodology, estimating for parameter significance requires analysis of the P-value from the autoregressive (AR) and moving average (MA)

components. A possible ARIMA (p,d,q) regression produces the P-value for each AR and MA terms used in the model with the parameter significance hypotheses as follows;

$$H_0 = \text{Parameter is not statistically significant}$$

$$H_1 = \text{Parameter is statistically significant}$$

Such that we do not reject the null hypothesis if the variable's P-value > 0.05 , meaning the variable is not statistically significant to explain the data and the particular parameter may not contribute significantly to improve the forecast performance. As a result, the potential ARIMA model with such a statistically insignificant parameter, be it for either the AR or MA terms, or even both insignificant, then that certain model should not be used for forecasting due to the AR and/or MA terms inability to significantly process the data. On the other hand, if the parameter's P-value < 0.05 it indicates that the parameter of AR and/or MA is statistically significant to be used in the model and could help better the predicting power ARIMA forecasting model.

3.8.2. Criterion Information Estimation

Information criterion is a model fit estimation based on likelihood measures which consists of a penalty for model's complexity, wherein ARIMA method such complexity is regarded as the amount of parameters used in the model. The main objective of information criterion specifically in the ARIMA method is to conduct model selection, that requires comparisons of candidate models capability in fitting the time series data. Two information criteria are going to be analyzed in this research, namely the Akaike information criterion (AIC) and the Schwarz information criterion (SC). The point of analyzing the AIC and SC in candidate ARIMA models is to examine which model is

the best fit to the data based on the lowest values of AIC and SC. The Akaike information criterion likelihood function is summed up as follows;

$$AIC = -2L(\sum \hat{a}_t^2) + 2K \quad (3.18)$$

And the Schwarz information criterion (SC) likelihood function is summed up as the following;

$$SC = -2L(\sum \hat{a}_t^2) + K \ln(n) \quad (3.19)$$

Whereby $L(\sum \hat{a}_t^2)$ is the log of the likelihood function of an ARIMA model and also operates as a monotonically decreasing function of the sum of squared residuals (SSR) which means that the larger SSR is, the smaller log likelihood function of the model. K represents the AR and MA parameter regressors, such that $K = p + q + 1$. The residuals of the data at time t for both the log likelihood function and the ARIMA model are represented by \hat{a}_t and the SSR is represented by $\sum \hat{a}_t^2$. As for the number of residuals computed for the model is represented with n . The concern of overfitting the model could be exhibited where if the number of AR or MA coefficients increases, it causes SSR as fit of the model to decrease. As a result of the decreasing SSR, the AIC value will go up, ceteris paribus, which is not preferable in the Box-Jenkins method. Hence, the best fit model with the least AIC is picked among the candidate models by assuming all of them have the same number of regressors (Jansson & Larsson, 2020). In handling the propensity for inserting more coefficients into an ARIMA model in order to have better model fit, the information criterion of AIC and SC employ penalty terms. AIC uses the penalty term of $+2K$ and SC utilizes the penalty term of $+K \ln n$. By imposing the penalty terms, any additional coefficients to the ARIMA model to increase model

fit at the cost of a decrease in SSR, will gradually be equalized by the penalty term from the contrary direction in the equation.

3.8.3. Coefficient of Determination Estimation

Coefficient of determination, also recognized as R-squared, is a statistical measure which accounts for the proportion of the dependent variable that is explained by the independent variables. The value of R-squared ranges from zero to one in which the larger the value of R-squared, the better the regression model is in explaining the observed data. However, in its application in the Box-Jenkins methodology, a more recent study by Li et al., (2023) suggested that the measure of R-squared alone as evaluation for an ARIMA model's goodness is not appropriate because generally R-squared is contingent upon the assumption of identically distributed and independent residuals. Whereby the aforementioned assumption is frequently violated in time series analysis, specifically in ARIMA models that are formulated to apprehend dependencies and trends of the data. This finding aligns with the coefficient of determination results from previous studies that conducted stock market index forecast using ARIMA models, Mashadihasanli (2022) and Pardede (2019) in their studies employed ARIMA models with considerably low R-squared estimates valuing to approximately 0.09 and 0.03 respectively, intuitively indicated only less than 10% of the dependent variables' variances were explained by the independent variables. Nevertheless, their models managed to fulfill diagnostic checking tests as the goodness-of-fit measures in the Box-Jenkins methodology which led to satisfactory forecasts. Typically, one could increase the number of independent variables which could help account for more variances of the dependent variable, but at the same time, using too many variables in an ARIMA

model induces a parsimony and overfitting issues such that regression results could be forecasts that are misleading and inaccurate. In this reasoning, the author of this research purposely utilizes R-squared estimation as one of the bridges to select the best model, together with evaluations of criterion information and forecast errors for a more profound analysis of model selection.

3.8.4. Error Estimation of Candidate ARIMA Models

One of the most important aspects of forecast analysis is how accurate can the projected results be given the availability of data to process and the research limitations. Figuring out the satisfactory accuracy for forecast analysis in this research is performed through evaluation of error estimations from the candidate ARIMA models. The candidate models in this research will process the JKSE price time series data throughout the training period which contains 380 monthly observations to produce predictions of the series in the out-of-sample testing period which consists of 10 monthly observations. Regarding the accuracy of this research's forecast analysis, the projected outcomes from all candidate models will be compared with the actual realizations of the JKSE monthly price in the testing period, which are the index prices in the 10-month period of January - October, 2022. The accuracy of the forecast will be assessed by the error estimations of the candidate models using measures of root mean square error (RMSE), mean absolute error (MAE), and mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) as written in the equations below referring to Chai & Draxler (2014);

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{t=1}^n (A_t - F_t)^2}{n}} \quad (3.20)$$

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n |A_t - F_t| \quad (3.21)$$

$$MAPE = \frac{100\%}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \left| \frac{A_t - F_t}{A_t} \right| \quad (3.21)$$

Where n is the sample size, A_t is the data's actual value at time t , and F_t is the data's forecasted value at time t . RMSE is a forecast validity that measures the square root of the average squared differences between the model's predicted values and the actual values. In finance, RMSE has been widely utilized as a common metrics for stock market forecast analysis to measure the model performance (Reddy, 2019). RMSE enables researchers to objectify the predictive power of a forecasting model based on the error distribution of the data. MAE calculates the average errors of the computed forecasting model in absolute value of the differences between the forecasted and the real data. The acceptable value of both RMSE and MAE depend on each research's data values and number of observations hence, it is inferred that both measures are variable-dependent, the priority is that RMSE and MAE values should be relatively low (Chai & Draxler, 2014). As for MAPE, it is a forecast validity measure of accuracy for a forecasting model that is presented in percentage (Tofallis, 2015). Referring to Tekindal (2008) and Lewis (1982); MAPE value of <10% is considered highly accurate, MAPE value of 10% - 20% is seen as decently accurate, MAPE value of 20% - 50% is viewed as reasonable forecasting, and MAPE value of >50% is evaluated as inaccurate forecasting.

3.9. Diagnostic Checking

After obtaining the best ARIMA model from parameters estimation process, the stage of diagnostic checking is performed to see if the selected model fairly fits the data. First and foremost, diagnostic checking acts through the autocorrelation test by analyzing the chosen model's estimated residuals such that the estimated residuals are white noise. Consequently, if the estimated residuals from the fitted model are not white noise, the steps of the ARIMA modeling must be started all over again to look for another certain ARIMA model that fits the data properly. Once the selected model is cleared from autocorrelation issues, the tests of heteroskedasticity and model's invertibility are performed in order to re-confirm that the concerned model fits the data well to be used for forecasting the JKSE monthly price series. Finally, when the conditions of all the previous stages are satisfied, the chosen ARIMA model can be used for the forecasting stage. Note that there might not be a perfect ARIMA model, however, by following requirements of the benchmark in statistical time series analysis, the Box-Jenkins method can produce forecasts that are more dependable than those of the traditional econometric modeling especially for short-term forecasting (Gujarati & Porter, 2009).

3.9.1. Autocorrelation Test

The selected ARIMA model in this research is examined through an autocorrelation test in order to make sure that there is no autocorrelation detected, whether positive or negative autocorrelation. The objective of this examination is to enhance the forecasting model's goodness of fit to produce forecasts that are as accurate as possible and it is pursued by proving that the residuals are white noise. The term white noise of residuals means that every sample value in the time series has zero correlation with

other samples in the series and that variances of the variables are constant. Testing for autocorrelation, the Ljung-Box test is conducted whereby it is a type of statistical test that examines if any autocorrelations of a time series are different from zero. According to Gujarati & Porter (2009), the Ljung-Box statistic is explained as the following;

$$Ljung-Box = n(n + 2) \sum_{k=1}^m \left(\frac{\hat{\rho}_k^2}{n-k} \right) \quad (3.22)$$

Where $\hat{\rho}_k$ is the autocorrelation at k^{th} lag, n represents the sample size, and m denotes the number of total lags. The interpretation of Ljung-Box statistic is based on its P-value with hypotheses as follows;

$$H_0 = \text{Residuals are white noise}$$

$$H_1 = \text{Residuals are not white noise}$$

Where if the P-value is indicated to be significant, $P\text{-value} < 0.05$, the null hypothesis is rejected implying that the time series data is autocorrelated as residuals are not independently distributed. On the other hand, the desirable outcome of this test is when $P\text{-value} > 0.05$ such that the null hypothesis is not rejected which infers independent distribution of residuals. Achieving the state of residuals are white noise based on this test implies that the model does not indicate lack of fit to be used for forecasting the time series data.

3.9.2. Heteroskedasticity Test

Heteroskedasticity is defined as a condition in which the time series data contains residuals or error terms that vary in variance distribution for any given value of the independent or explanatory variables. For a good forecasting model in the ARIMA

method, the selected model is expected to be homoskedastic which means that error terms have the same variance given any value of the independent variables. This research utilizes the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test for heteroskedasticity in ARIMA models with the following hypotheses;

$$H_0 = \text{Model is Homoskedastic}$$

$$H_1 = \text{Model is Heteroskedastic}$$

Where if the test result indicates P-value < 0.05 the null hypothesis is rejected, meaning that heteroskedasticity is present in the ARIMA model as the residuals are not equally distributed in variance. The Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test results that an adequate forecasting model yearns for is when the P-value > 0.05 such that the null hypothesis of model's homoskedasticity is not rejected. By obtaining the presence of homoskedasticity in the selected ARIMA model, the equal distribution of residuals in the series variance is expected to allow the forecasted outcomes in the testing period to be stable.

3.9.3. ARIMA Process Invertibility Test

The last examination in the diagnostic checking stage is analyzing the roots of autoregressive (AR) and moving average (MA) components to check for the stationarity and invertibility of the selected model. Proving that the ARIMA model is in fact invertible is important because it suggests that the noises in the data can be inverted into the data past observations, in other words the series data can be explained by a finite moving average orders (Tsay, 2005). Checking for invertibility of the selected ARIMA model is done through visual inspection of the unit circle of the

ARIMA model. The required conditions are that all AR and MA roots must lie inside the unit circle and thus, indicating covariance stationarity and invertibility process of the model.

3.10. Forecasting

The final step in the Box-Jenkins method is to perform the forecast using the best ARIMA model of the research that ultimately has fulfilled the necessary assumptions and goodness-of-fit measures of the method. The forecasting procedure will be conducted through the statistical software of EViews 12 Student Version. There are two types of forecast process provided by the software, namely static forecast and dynamic forecast. At first, this research compares the performance of both forecast types and the one with higher accuracy measures will be decided to represent the projection of the JKSE monthly prices. Afterwards, since this research's forecasting model operates in logarithmic form, the predicted JKSE monthly prices in \log_{10} values are transformed back into actual values by calculating 10 to the power of the log values for every projected JKSE monthly price in the testing period, as shown in the following equation;

$$y_t = 10^{(\log_{10})} \quad (3.23)$$

Finally, the forecasted outcomes that would have been re-transformed into actual values will be compared with the actual realizations to analyze how accurate and significant the forecast is, in order to provide empirical results that prove the hypotheses of this research.

CHAPTER IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Descriptive Analysis

This research analyzes a time series data of the JKSE monthly prices with a population of monthly observations from May, 1990 to October, 2022, an equivalent of 390 total sample observations. The data is gathered from a reliable source of stock market data which is Yahoo Finance. This research also follows the rule of thumb proposed by Box & Tiao, (1975), that ARIMA models should work with a time series data containing a minimum of 50 observations, yet above 100 observations within the series is more advantageous. After the selection process of the total samples, this research would then classify them into two sampling periods, as listed in Table 3.2. Specifically, the training sample period consists of 380 monthly observations of the JKSE price from May, 1990 until December, 2021. The training samples are processed in the ARIMA model to produce projections of JKSE monthly prices in January, 2022 to October, 2022, referred to in this research as the testing period that consists of 10 monthly observations. This subchapter discusses the descriptive statistics of the training samples as they are the required historical values of the JKSE price that would explain its future realizations in the testing period. As for the testing period analysis is discussed later on in this research, in the forecast analysis that compares how the predicted projections of the index price produced by the ARIMA model perform against the index's actual realizations in the testing period. The following table and figure describe the descriptive statistics and the distribution plot of the JKSE monthly prices during the training period.

Table 4.1. Descriptive Statistics of JKSE Training Samples Time Series

JKSE Training Samples, May 1990 - December 2021

	Obs.	Mean	Max	Min	Std. Dev.	Skewness	Kurtosis
<i>JKSE</i>	380	2400.776	6605.631	226.6840	2185.733	0.588775	1.720381

Source: Output from EViews 12 Student Version, processed (2023)

Table 4.1 presents the descriptive statistics of JKSE training samples which include 380 monthly observations. The average JKSE monthly price in the training series is 2400.776, with a standard deviation of 2185.733. The highest monthly price of the index during the training period is 6605.631 that was recorded in January, 2018. The lowest monthly price during the training period was recorded in October, 1991 with 226.6840.

Figure 4.1. Distribution Plot of JKSE Training Samples Time Series

Source: Output EViews 12 Student Version, processed (2023)

Table 4.1 indicates the kurtosis statistics of 1.720381, the skewness is indicated to be a positive skewness 0.58877 since it is above the rule of thumb of nearly symmetrical data's skewness which is -0.5 to 0.5. The positive skewness means that the slightly skewed data are asymmetric. The shape of the distribution of the JKSE monthly price during the training period also does not reflect a normal distribution, as shown in Figure 4.1. Based on the

descriptive statistics so far, the JKSE training sample series is still not normal in distribution and thus, a further smoothing of the data is needed.

Figure 4.2. Monthly Price of JKSE Training Samples

Source: Yahoo Finance, processed (2023)

The author also analyzes monthly price of the JKSE training samples for each periodic month from May 1990 – December 2021 to check if there is any specific month of the calendar year in which the JKSE price tends to be higher or lower compared to the index monthly price in the other months. Figure 4.2 shows there was a sideways trend of monthly JKSE price movements from 1990 until 2003 marked by the grey rectangle, whereby monthly price

tended to rebound after declining down to bottoms, or also technically known as support level, at price range of approximately 300 – 450 Rupiah in the year 1991, 1992, 1993, 1998, and 2002. The sideways trend persisted during the 1990s until early 2000s, as after rallying up from prices at support level the JKSE monthly prices tended to correct themselves due to failing to break-out out of the resistance level at price range of approximately 600 – 720 Rupiah in the year 1996, 1997, and 1999. The JKSE price finally succeeded to experience a break-out rally off the sideways trend in January 2004 where monthly price of 752 Rupiah was recorded, signaling a rally of uptrend that lasted until the year 2007. Other significant uptrend rallies of the JKSE monthly prices were indicated from September 2015 until April 2019, a year before the global pandemic affected and temporarily halted economic activities in 2020.

On the other hand, severe downtrends were also experienced by the JKSE prices due to the global recession of 2008 whereby from its peak in December 2007, the JKSE price plummeted until a bottom or support level in November 2008, undergoing a severe contraction of -54.78% as the heavy impact of global crisis hit Indonesian economy. Other notable downtrends that JKSE had to endure was due to the global oil price shocks in 2015 whereby JKSE corrected a -23.46% from a peak in March 2015 to a bottom in September 2015 and the global pandemic of Covid-19 whereby JKSE corrected a -27.95% from a December 2019 to a bottom in March 2020. Visual analysis of the Figure 4.2 also reveals that after breaking out of a 14-year sideways trend in January 2004, the JKSE December prices tended to perform higher returns among other monthly JKSE prices, since four in eight monthly price peaks marked by the black arrows were recorded by JKSE December prices in 2007, 2014, 2017, and 2021, by assuming that peaks is identified right before prices declined way down in a correction phase.

Relating to the illustration of monthly fluctuations of the JKSE series, an example of seasonal behavior of investors is the occurrence of January effect (Pavlov & Yang, 2010) whereby it is a pattern that tends to indicate a greater return to be earned in the first month of the year, as fund and investment manager start implementing their investment strategies at the start of a calendar year, followed by the enthusiasm of individual investors. Behavior of investors such as the January effect, ‘blue Monday on Wall Street’, and ‘sell in May and go away’ etc., are examples of counter arguments to the EMH theory which rejects the presence of existing patterns and trends of stocks price movements. These signs of recurring trends of the JKSE monthly price movements shown in Figure 4.2 further suggests the need for data modification in order to alleviate the impacts of trends and patterns commonly observed in time series data.

To obtain better statistical inference and removal of the trends in the series data (Mashadihasanli, 2022) logarithm transformation of the JKSE actual values into \log_{10} values are conducted. The log-transformed series is then named as *IJKSE* and the full list of monthly prices in \log_{10} values are exhibited in Appendix I. Once the dependent variable of JKSE training samples are transformed into \log_{10} values, *IJKSE*, the descriptive statistics are described in the following table;

Table 4.2. Descriptive Statistics of IJKSE Training Samples Time Series

IJKSE Training Samples, May 1990 - December 2021							
	Obs.	Mean	Max	Min	Std. Dev.	Skewness	Kurtosis
<i>IJKSE</i>	380	3.144297	3.819914	2.355421	0.481536	0.071353	1.360902

Source: Output EViews 12 Student Version, processed (2023)

Table 4.2. shows the descriptive statistics of *IJKSE* monthly prices during the training period. The table shows *IJKSE* training samples with a mean of 3.144297 and standard deviation of 0.481536. The maximum value of the variable is 3.819914 and the minimum value of the variable is 2.355421. The *IJKSE* training samples in log values now are viewed by the author to be more friendly to be analyzed in terms of the price ranges compared to the original JKSE training series in actual values.

Figure 4.3. Distribution Plot of *IJKSE* Training Samples Time Series

Source: Output EViews 12 Student Version, processed (2023)

After the transformation into log values, Figure 4.3 now indicates the *IJKSE* series normal data distribution in which the series is going to be the dependent variable of this research's model. The kurtosis value is indicated to be 1.360902, that is still within the acceptable range of kurtosis value -2 to 2 to prove univariate normal distribution according to examination by George & Mallery (2010). The skewness of *IJKSE* at 0.071353 is also a much-improved statistic compared to the initial JKSE series at 0.588775. Skewness of *IJKSE* indicates the data are normally distributed and that the distribution is symmetric. Therefore, the descriptive

statistics of *IJKSE* indicate that the data used in this research is clear from normality issues, demonstrated by the relatively close to zero skewness and referring to Byrne & Van de Vijver (2010) a kurtosis value that is less than 7.

4.2. Model Identification Results

4.2.1. Stationarity Test Results

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test is conducted on the *IJKSE* series which contains the training samples data that are going to be processed for forecasting. The ADF test is performed for the *IJKSE* at level or before differencing and for the *IJKSE* at first difference as indicated in the following Table 4.3 and Table 4.4.

Table 4.3. Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test of IJKSE at Level

Null Hypothesis: *IJKSE* has a unit root

	t-statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-0.341149	0.9158
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.446992	
5% level	-2.868771	
10% level	-2.570688	

Source: Output EViews 12 Student Version, processed (2023)

Table 4.3 indicates the ADF test results consisting a P-value of 0.9158 that is larger than 0.05 and the absolute of critical values at all significance levels that are larger than the absolute of t-statistic, which means the null hypothesis is not rejected implying that the *IJKSE* series at level is not stationary. The P-value results of the ADF test that

indicated *IJKSE* at level is stationary also implies that the series is not a random walk process and therefore, the formulation of JKSE monthly prices are not random. Through the ADF test for stationarity, empirical result is now provided that historical information can't completely be reflected in current JKSE monthly prices such that by analyzing historical information of JKSE past values, investors have the tendency to earn excess capital gains, counter-arguing the weak form of EMH.

In response, a differencing order d will be imposed on the *IJKSE* series that automatically infers the use of ARIMA(p,d,q) model in this research.

Table 4.4. Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test of IJKSE at First Difference

Null Hypothesis: *IJKSE* has a unit root

	t-statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-16.10696	0.0000
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.446992	
5% level	-2.868771	
10% level	-2.570688	

Source: Output EViews 12 Student Version, processed (2023)

Table 4.4 shows that after applying a first difference order to the *IJKSE* series, the ADF test indicates stationarity of the series. It is explained through the test's P-value of 0.0000 that is smaller than 0.05 as well as the absolute of critical values at all significance levels being smaller than the absolute of t-statistic, which means the null hypothesis of *IJKSE* has a unit root is rejected. The *IJKSE* series is now seen as stable to proceed with further ARIMA model identification processes.

Figure 4.4. IJKSE Series at First Difference

Source: Output EViews 12 Student Version, processed (2023)

Figure 4.4 illustrates the *IJKSE* monthly price series at first difference that does not exhibit significant uptrends and downtrends that are previously discussed through explanation of monthly JKSE prices in Figure 4.2 and illustrations of JKSE annual realizations in Figure 1.1. By achieving stationarity after a first order differencing of the *IJKSE* series, the variable variances are now constant over the observed period of the series data and this is exactly what we would need for a stable and accurate ARIMA forecasting model.

4.2.2. Autocorrelation Functions Results

In identifying the possible components of $AR(p)$ and $MA(q)$ in the ARIMA model, the correlogram consisting of autocorrelation function (ACF) and partial autocorrelation

(PACF) lag plots is analyzed to look for any significant lags which determines the possible orders of p and q .

Figure 4.5. Correlogram of IJKSE at level

Source: Output EViews 12 Student Version, processed (2023)

Figure 4.5 represents the plot of correlogram for ACF and PACF of the *IJKSE* training samples time series from lag 1 to lag 36 before differencing. The PACF plot only crosses the Bartlett's significance line at lag 1 and the ACF plots are all significant by crossing the Bartlett's significance line whilst tailing off slowly from lag 1 to lag 36. Such demonstration of ACF and PACF plots in correlogram table of ARIMA methodology indicates that the *IJKSE* training series at level is indeed not stationary. The plots of autocorrelation functions displayed in Figure 4.5 are commonly observed when analyzing time series data, particularly for a variable of stock market index price and thus, a differencing process is needed to convert the non-stationary series into a stationary one (Reddy, 2019). Significant autocorrelation lags indicated in Figure 4.5 reassures findings from ADF test for stationarity of *IJKSE* at level that the series is not a random walk, hence, providing empirical proofs that the weak form of EMH that states past information of JKSE monthly price can't reflect future prices does not hold

true in this research because the observed *IJKSE* training samples are not randomly formulated.

Figure 4.6 exhibits the plots of ACF and PACF of the *IJKSE* training samples time series from lag 1 to lag 20 after the series achieved stationarity at first difference, whereby we can see a visible difference to that of Figure 4.5. From the ACF plot point of view, the only significant lags are at lag 1 and lag 20 where the ACF spikes through

Figure 4.6. Correlogram of IJKSE at First Difference

Source: Output EViews 12 Student Version, processed (2023)

the Bartlett's significance barrier as such indicating the possible use of $MA(1)$ and $MA(20)$ moving average orders in the research's model. From the PACF perspective, significant lags are also observed at lag 1 and lag 20 where the PACF spikes cross Bartlett's significance line, suggesting the utilization of $AR(1)$ and $AR(20)$ autoregressive orders.

Table 4.5. Sample Autocorrelation Coefficients of Significant Lags at 95% Confidence Interval

Sample Size, $n = 379$

Standard Error, $SE = 0.002638$

Square Root of Standard Error, $\sqrt{SE} = 0.051366$

Standard Error for Population Distribution at 95% CI, $1.96\sqrt{SE} = 0.100678$

	Lag	Coefficients	Bartlett's Line Crossing	Information
ACF	Lag 1	0.196		Significant
	Lag 20	-0.104		Significant
PACF	Lag 1	0.196		Significant
	Lag 20	-0.122		Significant

Source: Output EViews 12 Student Version, processed (2023)

Table 4.5 shows sample autocorrelation coefficients of the significant lags at 95% confidence interval based on the *IJKSE* training samples time series at first difference. The sample size in correlogram plots n , that is 379 observations differs when compared to the *IJKSE* training series total of 380 observations, is due to the first difference estimation applied to stationarize the series. Based on the calculations of the sample autocorrelations at 95% confidence intervals, the standard error (SE) is indicated to be 0.002638, with a square root of the SE of 0.051366. As a result, the standard error for sampling or population distribution is computed to be 0.100678. In this regard, residuals of the *IJKSE* training series at first difference is still yet to be white noise because there remain significant autocorrelation lags, namely ACF and PACF coefficients that are all statistically different from zero at lag 1 and lag 20, respectively.

4.2.3. Candidate ARIMA Models

In response to residuals that are not yet white noise based on the correlogram plots of autocorrelation and partial autocorrelations functions of the *IJKSE* training samples at first difference, the $ARIMA(p,d,q)$ is going to be estimated using autoregressive and moving average parameters that are fit to use. The possible ARIMA model parameters are indicated from the significant ACF lags for $MA(q)$ components and from the significant PACF lags for $AR(p)$ components. In figuring out the ARIMA model's components of p and q , Nau (2014) suggested that it is commonly preferable to work with models with at least one of the AR and MA components is no greater than 1, i.e., fitting an ARIMA (2,1,2) model to the data is not advised. This is due to the worrying issues that are commonly associated with ARIMA modeling of time series data, which is overfitting data that could induce less accurate forecasts. Therefore, this research will try to estimate all candidate ARIMA models in order to find the best fitting ARIMA model to forecast the subject of study. The candidate ARIMA models are formed based on the following table;

Table 4.6. Candidate ARIMA Models

		Significant ACF Lags	
		MA(1)	MA(20)
Significant PACF Lags	AR(1)	ARIMA(1,1,1)	ARIMA(1,1,20)
	AR(20)	ARIMA(20,1,1)	ARIMA(20,1,20)

Source: Output EViews 12 Student Version, processed (2023)

Table 4.6 presents the four candidate ARIMA(p,d,q) models which will be estimated in the next stage of the Box-Jenkins method, that is the parameter estimation. Among the four candidate models; ARIMA(1,1,1); ARIMA(1,1,20); ARIMA(20,1,1); ARIMA(20,1,20); only one model will be selected to forecast the *IJKSE* series by becoming the best fitted model to the data through several evaluations and examinations explained in the upcoming chapter.

4.3. Parameter Estimation Results

4.3.1. Parameter Significance Estimation Results

The results of parameter significance for each candidate models is described in the following table;

Table 4.7. Results of Candidate Models Parameter Significance

Null Hypothesis = Parameter is not statistically significant

Model	Parameter	P-value	Parameter Significance
ARIMA(1,1,1)	AR(1)	0.5788	Insignificant
	MA(1)	0.0797	Insignificant
ARIMA(1,1,20)	AR(1)	0.0000	Significant
	MA(20)	0.0037	Significant
ARIMA(20,1,1)	AR(20)	0.0020	Significant
	MA(1)	0.0000	Significant
ARIMA(20,1,20)	AR(20)	0.0011	Significant

MA(20)	0.0065	Significant
--------	--------	-------------

Source: Output EViews 12 Student Version, processed (2023)

Table 4.7 tells the parameter significance of each candidate ARIMA model in this research based on the null hypothesis that the parameter is not statistically significant if the P-value is larger than 5% significance level. The results indicate that both parameters of AR(1) and MA(1) in ARIMA(1,1,1), with P-value of 0.5788 and 0.0797 respectively, are not significant at the 5% significance level and therefore, this candidate model is now canceled out of considerations for forecast use. As for the remaining three candidate models; ARIMA(1,1,20); ARIMA(20,1,1); ARIMA(20,1,20); parameter significance results of the aforementioned models are indicating the rejection of null hypothesis because all the parameters within the models have P-value that are less than 5% significance level, as such the parameters are statistically significant and able to be utilized for forecasting. Based on the parameter significance results explained, there are only three remaining candidate models that are going to be further estimated since ARIMA(1,1,1) has been eliminated due to the model's parameters insignificance.

4.3.2. Criterion Information Estimation Results

The following table provides the criterion information estimation results for the candidate models with significant parameters;

Table 4.8. Results of Candidate Models Criterion Information

Candidate Models

	ARIMA(20,1,1)	ARIMA(1,1,20)	ARIMA(20,1,20)
Akaike information criterion (AIC)	-4.082765	-4.076011	-4.036328
Schwarz information criterion (SC)	-4.042008	-4.035255	-3.995571

Source: Output EViews 12 Student Version, processed (2023)

Table 4.8 exhibits the estimation results of Akaike information criterion (AIC) and Schwarz information criterion (SC) for the three candidate models. In the ARIMA forecasting method, the ideal and optimal information criterion for a best ARIMA model among other possible ones is the one with the least AIC and SC values, where negative values also mean lower values that are preferable. As Voss & Feng (2002) suggested that AIC helps to improve the forecasting power of ARIMA model by measuring the expected relative differences between the suited ARIMA model and the true instrument or mechanism which literally formulated the observed time series data. Based on the results in Table 4.8, criterion information estimation indicates that the ARIMA(20,1,1) model is preferable compared to ARIMA(1,1,20) and ARIMA(20,1,20) models, due to its lowest AIC of -4.082765 and lowest SC of -4.042008 among the AIC and SC values of all the candidate models. The second lowest AIC and SC are owned by ARIMA(1,1,20) with values of -4.076011 and -4.035255, respectively. And the least preferable model is ARIMA(20,1,20) with AIC and SC values of -4.036328 and -3.995571, respectively.

4.3.3. Coefficient of Determination Estimation Results

The following table shows the coefficient of determination, or R-squared, of the candidate models that process the *IJKSE* training samples time series data;

Table 4.9. Results of Candidate Models R-squared Estimations

	Candidate Models		
	ARIMA(20,1,1)	ARIMA(1,1,20)	ARIMA(20,1,20)
R-squared	0.058283	0.051780	0.013849

Source: Output EViews 12 Student Version, processed (2023)

Table 4.9 exhibits the values of R-squared for the three candidate models in which a best fit and preferable model should have the largest R-squared among the others. Similar to the findings in criterion information estimations, the ARIMA(20,1,1) model has proven again to be the preferable model among the others based on its largest R-squared value. Based on results in Table 4.9, the ARIMA(20,1,1) model is preferred because of its 0.058283 R-squared value is larger than those of ARIMA(1,1,20) model at 0.051780 and ARIMA(20,1,20) at 0.013849. It is inferred that the preferred ARIMA(20,1,1) model has variances of the independent variables that are able to explain the dependent variable, $IJKSE_t$, by 5.83%. This result seems quite small, however, it still accords with previous studies by Mashsadihasanli (2022) that used ARIMA(3,1,5) model with 0.09 R-squared value and Pardede (2019) that utilized ARIMA(2,1,2) model with 0.03 R-squared value, and both studies successfully managed to produce forecasts with significant goodness-of-fit measures.

4.3.4. Error Estimation Results of Candidate ARIMA Models

Results of the error estimation of candidate ARIMA models are exhibited in the following table;

Table 4.10. Results of Candidate Models Error Estimation

Actual Data	<i>IJKSE</i>		
Testing Sample	2022M01 - 2022M10		
Training Sample	1990M05 - 2021M12		
	Candidate Models		
	ARIMA(20,1,1)	ARIMA(1,1,20)	ARIMA(20,1,20)
RMSE	0.018173	0.018811	0.020929
MAE	0.015716	0.016281	0.018627
MAPE	0.408088	0.422759	0.483744

Source: Output EViews 12 Student Version, processed (2023)

Table 4.10 describes the error estimations of candidate models that performed forecasts for 10-month *IJKSE* monthly projections in testing period from 2022M01 to 2022M10 using the actual *IJKSE* data in training period from 1990M05 to 2021M12. Analyzing the results, ARIMA(20,1,1) model performed the highest predictive power among other candidate models in terms of root mean squared error (RMSE) with 0.018173 that is smaller than RMSE value of ARIMA(1,1,20) that is 0.018811 and RMSE value of ARIMA(20,1,20) that is 0.020929. In terms of mean absolute error (MAE), the ARIMA(20,1,1) has once again proved that the model is able to produce the least mean absolute differences between the predicted and the actual values among the candidate models. The MAE values of the candidate models ranked from lowest to highest include; ARIMA(20,1,1) with 0.015716; ARIMA(1,1,20) with 0.016281; and

ARIMA(20,1,20) with 0.018627. The mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) values are inferred whereby on average, the ARIMA(20,1,1) produced forecasted values that differ 0.408088% from the actual *IJKSE* data in logarithm values. Since the MAPE results of ARIMA(1,1,20) and ARIMA(20,1,20) at 0.422759% and 0.483744%, respectively, are not indicating the best accuracy measures among the candidate models, these two models are consequently not selected as the best ARIMA model in this research. Therefore, the ARIMA(20,1,1) model that has provided the best accuracy performance based on the errors measures of RMSE, MAE, and MAPE, will be proceeded to the next stage of the Box-Jenkins method, that is the diagnostic checking to see the model suitability given the *IJKSE* time series data.

4.4. Diagnostic Checking Results

Based on the results from the parameter estimation stage in the ARIMA method of the research, the model selection process has concluded that the ARIMA(20,1,1) is the best model to forecast the *IJKSE* series data through the candidate models evaluations of parameter significance, coefficient of determination, information criterion, and forecast errors. However, ARIMA(20,1,1) must go through tests in the diagnostic checking stage and if the model is indicated to be a good fit to the data, the model will proceed to perform the forecast.

4.4.1. Autocorrelation Test Results

The following figure shows the autocorrelation test results of the ARIMA(20,1,1) model;

Figure 4.7. Correlogram of ARIMA(20,1,1) Model Ljung-Box Test

Source: Output EViews 12 Student Version, processed (2023)

The Ljung-Box test is conducted to detect any autocorrelations within the ARIMA(20,1,1) model that has been chosen as the model to forecast within this research. The Ljung-Box test requires all the plots of autocorrelations at any lag to be inside the Bartlett's significance lines and P-value > 0.05 to prove the residuals are indeed white noise. Figure 4.7 indicates that the ARIMA(20,1,1) model does not exhibit any lack of fit to forecast the *IJKSE* data, based on the autocorrelation test results of all ACF and PACF plots that stay within the barriers of Bartlett's significance line, as well as all the P-value that are larger than 0.05. Therefore, autocorrelation test results of the ARIMA(20,1,1) indicate that the null hypothesis is not rejected, meaning the residuals are white noise and the model does not suffer from autocorrelation issues.

4.4.2. Heteroskedasticity Test Results

The following table indicates results of the ARIMA(20,1,1) model heteroskedasticity test;

Table 4.11. Results of ARIMA(20,1,1) Model Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Test

Null Hypothesis = Model is homoskedastic

ARIMA(20,1,1)	
Prob. F(2,376)	0.5893
Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.4960
Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.9975

Source: Output EViews 12 Student Version, processed (2023)

Table 4.11 indicates the results of Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey heteroskedasticity test on the ARIMA(20,1,1) model. Whereby probability Chi-Square value of 0.4960 is larger than the threshold value 0.05 such that the null hypothesis is not rejected, implying that the model is assumed to be homoskedastic.

Figure 4.8. Quantiles Plots of ARIMA(20,1,1) Residuals

Source: Output EViews 12 Student Version, processed (2023)

By achieving homoskedasticity, the ARIMA(20,1,1) model has the property of equal distribution of residuals in the data variance. As also illustrated in Figure 4.8, the residuals are not widely dispersed as the values of regressor variable in the ARIMA(20,1,1) model changes, such that the residuals closely follow the fitted distribution line.

4.4.3. ARIMA Process Invertibility Test Results

Result of the ARIMA process invertibility test for the ARIMA(20,1,1) model is shown in the following figure;

Figure 4.9. Result of ARIMA(20,1,1) Model Invertibility Test

Source: Output EViews 12 Student Version, processed (2023)

Figure 4.9 depicts the inverse roots of the autoregressive (AR) and moving average (MA) roots of the ARIMA(20,1,1) model. The result indicates that all AR roots lie inside the unit circle implying that the ARIMA(20,1,1) model is stationary. The MA

root is also positioned inside the unit circle implying that the $ARIMA(20,1,1)$ model is in fact invertible such that the moving average regressor in the model is able to invert the noises in the data into observed past values in the *IJKSE* time series, implying that the $MA(1)$ order is capable of explaining the series data.

4.5. Forecasting Results

After surpassing the required assumptions and tests of the Box-Jenkins method, the $ARIMA(20,1,1)$ is finally utilized to forecast the *IJKSE* data for the testing period based on historical observations in the training period. The two types of time series forecast in the EViews 12 Student Version, namely the dynamic and static forecasts are both conducted and the accuracy of the forecasts are described in the following table;

Table 4.12. Dynamic and Static Forecasts Performance Comparison of ARIMA (20,1,1) Model

Actual Data	<i>IJKSE</i>		
Testing Sample	2022M01 - 2022M10		
Training Sample	1990M05 - 2021M12		
	RMSE	MAE	MAPE
Dynamic Forecast	0.018173	0.015716	0.408088
Static Forecast	0.010696	0.009704	0.252220

Source: Output EViews 12 Student Version, processed (2023)

Table 4.12 describes the forecast performance results of the $ARIMA(20,1,1)$ which indicate that the static forecast outperforms the dynamic forecast based on the accuracy

measures of root mean square error (RMSE), mean absolute error (MAE), and mean absolute percentage error (MAPE). The static forecast of ARIMA(20,1,1) model results in RMSE values of 0.010696, MAE values of 0.009704, and MAPE values of 0.252220, which are all smaller than the dynamic forecast's error measures aforementioned. This is generally because the static forecast utilizes actual outcomes for each successive or consecutive forecast, whereas the dynamic forecast takes into account the previous lagged forecasted values for each forecast value. In this regard, the projected outcomes of *IJKSE* in the testing period will be represented by the predictions produced by static forecast of the ARIMA(20,1,1) since the static forecast is proven to be more accurate.

The projected outcomes of the *IJKSE* monthly price in January 2022 - October 2022 from the ARIMA(20,1,1) static forecast are still expressed in logarithm values, thus, transformation of the projected outcomes from \log_{10} values into actual values is done by the author in order to do a comprehensible price comparison between the predicted and actual values of the Jakarta Stock Exchange Composite Index (JKSE) during the testing period, as tabulated in the following table;

Table 4.13. Comparison of the Projected IJKSE Monthly Prices from ARIMA(20,1,1) Static Forecast and the Actual JKSE Monthly Prices, January - October 2022

Month	ARIMA(20,1,1) Static Forecast Projections		Actual JKSE Prices		Absolute Error (in Normal)	Absolute Percentage Error (%)
	Log	Normal	Log	Normal		
January	3.822591	6646.4724	3.821589	6631.1508	15.3215	0.23%
February	3.822814	6649.8899	3.838104	6888.1708	238.2809	3.46%
March	3.842173	6953.0048	3.849508	7071.4418	118.4370	1.67%
April	3.853438	7135.7255	3.859073	7228.9140	93.1885	1.29%
May	3.867480	7370.2083	3.854243	7148.9702	221.2380	3.09%
June	3.851542	7104.6432	3.839577	6911.5820	193.0612	2.79%
July	3.835085	6840.4502	3.842055	6951.1230	110.6728	1.59%
August	3.843403	6972.7316	3.856039	7178.5898	205.8582	2.87%
September	3.863188	7297.7311	3.847622	7040.7978	256.9333	3.65%
October	3.843784	6978.8512	3.851190	7098.8901	120.0390	1.69%
Mean Absolute Percentage Error						2.23%

Source: Output EViews 12 Student Version & Yahoo Finance, processed (2023)

Table 4.13 describes the comparison between the projected *IJKSE* monthly prices from ARIMA(20,1,1) static forecast model and the actual JKSE monthly prices, in both log values and actual values after re-transformation, from January to October, 2022. At the start of the training period that is on the month of January, this research's model predicted the JKSE price on January, 2022, to be 6646.4724 and was actually realized to be 6631.1508 in the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX), indicating a difference of 0.23% which is the lowest recorded forecast error in the testing period. The largest forecast error is recorded for the JKSE price in

September, 2022, a difference of 3.65% whereby the forecasting model estimated a price of 7297.7311 and the actual price stood at 7040.7978. Based on the prices that are already transformed back into actual values, this research has formulated projections of the JKSE monthly prices for January until October, 2022, which on average differ from the actual JKSE monthly realizations by only 2.23%.

4.6. Discussion

Estimation results of the selected ARIMA(20,1,1) model based on the thorough analyses in previous chapters following in the steps of the Box-Jenkins methodology are presented in the following table;

Table 4.14. Estimation Results of the ARIMA(20,1,1) Model

Dependent Variable: D(JKSE)

Method: ARMA Maximum Likelihood

Sample (Adjusted): 1990M06 - 2021M12

Included Observations: 379

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.002808	0.001922	1.461128	0.1448
AR(20)	-0.124547	0.040067	-3.108475	0.0020
MA(1)	0.231479	0.034751	6.661095	0.0000
SIGMASQ	0.000966	4.27E-05	22.60361	0.0000
R-squared	0.058283	Mean Dependent Variable		0.002693
Adj. R-squared	0.050945	Akaike Information Criterion		-4.082765

S.E. of Regression	0.031245	Schwarz Criterion	-4.042008
Sum Squared Residuals	0.375847	Hannan-Quinn Criterion	-4.066607
Log Likelihood	798.0978	Durbin-Watson Stat	2.018390

Source: Output EViews 12 Student Version, processed (2023)

Table 4.14 describes the model estimation of ARIMA(20,1,1), whereby the model estimation has proven the first hypothesis of this research regarding the capability of autoregressive (AR) and moving average (MA) indicators to significantly affect the formulations of JKSE monthly values. The hypothesis of this research is satisfied through the parameter estimation results of ARIMA(20,1,1) model with significant AR(20) and MA(1) parameters at 5% significance level, the highest R-squared value among other candidate models, the lowest AIC and SC criterion information among other candidate models, along with the Durbin-Watson statistic of 2.018390 that indicates no autocorrelation is detected in the model according to Brooks (2014).

The selection of ARIMA(20,1,1) to forecast the formulations of JKSE monthly prices in the testing period after establishing that; (i) the residuals are white noise based on Ljung-Box test; (ii) the presence of homoskedasticity in the model based on the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test; (iii) and the invertibility of the model based on all the roots of AR and MA orders which lie inside the unit circle; have also provide the empirical evidences to back this research's second hypothesis of ARIMA model's capability in explaining future realizations of the JKSE prices using the historical prices of the index itself.

Based on the ARIMA(20,1,1) model estimation, the equation 3.2 can now be rewritten as the following;

$$\begin{aligned}
IJKSE_t = & 0.002808 - 0.2917IJKSE_{t-1} + 0.0223IJKSE_{t-2} - 0.0091IJKSE_{t-3} \\
& + 0.0484IJKSE_{t-4} - 0.0226IJKSE_{t-5} + 0.0182IJKSE_{t-6} - 0.0690IJKSE_{t-7} \\
& - 0.0258IJKSE_{t-8} - 0.0622IJKSE_{t-9} + 0.0488IJKSE_{t-10} - 0.0260IJKSE_{t-11} \\
& - 0.0079IJKSE_{t-12} + 0.0297IJKSE_{t-13} + 0.0129IJKSE_{t-14} - 0.0724IJKSE_{t-15} \\
& + 0.0702IJKSE_{t-16} + 0.0227IJKSE_{t-17} - 0.0409IJKSE_{t-18} - 0.0281IJKSE_{t-19} \\
& - 0.1241IJKSE_{t-20} - 0.1245IJKSE_{t-21} + 0.2315\varepsilon_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t
\end{aligned} \tag{4.1}$$

Equation 4.1 describes the forecasting equation of this research whereby it is indicated that an increase of 1% in the lagged *IJKSE* price at period $t - 1$ decreases the *IJKSE* price by 0.2917% in the subsequent month, *ceteris paribus*. The same interpretation of the autoregressive coefficient is inferred for all lagged *IJKSE* prices until period $t - 21$, whereby 1% increases for each lagged values of the *IJKSE* variable in each lagged period will increase or decrease the *IJKSE* prices in the successive month depending on the coefficient values of the lagged *IJKSE* variables, *ceteris paribus*. As for the moving average coefficient, it is interpreted as a 1% increase in the errors at lag $t - 1$ increases the *IJKSE* price in the subsequent month by 0.2315%, *ceteris paribus*. The estimation results of the forecasting model in this research have provided empirical proof that the ARIMA model is adequately significant in formulating stock market index prices, especially JKSE prices, for a specified time-ahead by utilizing historical observations of the dependent variable.

Figure 4.10. Static Forecasted and Actual JKSE Monthly Price Movements

Source: Output EViews 12 Student Version & Yahoo Finance, processed (2023)

Figure 4.10 depicts the fluctuation of the static forecasted JKSE monthly prices indicated by a red curve and the actual JKSE monthly prices indicated by a blue curve, in actual values from January until October, 2022. The third hypothesis of this research saying that the model-projected JKSE prices are expected to undergo a positive trend in the testing period are then demonstrated to stand true whereby the forecasted JKSE monthly prices increase by 5.00% throughout the testing period, specifically from 6646.4724 in January to 6978.8512 in October, 2022. On the other hand, the growth of the actual JKSE monthly prices in the IDX market realizations during the testing period, reached 7.05% from 6631.1509 in January to 7098.8901. It can be inferred that the forecasted earnings of 5.00% by investing in JKSE index from January until October, 2022, is guaranteed as the actual earnings of 7.05% exceeded the model-projected growth by approximately 2.05%, which is also quite similar to the

forecasting model's MAPE of 2.23%. Despite the non-existent of a sole JKSE index product currently in the market operations of the IDX, investors can always decide to make investments on stocks or mutual funds that relate closely to the movements of the JKSE index prices. Therefore, the final research hypothesis of this research regarding ARIMA forecasting model that is able to help investors in pursuing capital gains with respect to JKSE monthly price movements is shown to be true as the forecasted outcomes follow the actual realizations closely with a margin of mean absolute percentage error at 2.23%.

Figure 4.11. Growth of IDX Indicators and JKSE Price, December 2018 – December 2021 & October 2022

Source: Indonesia Central Securities Depository (KSEI), processed (2024)

Figure 4.11 depicts a more recent growth of IDX indicators namely the number of investors in the IDX, the IDX market capitalization, the domestic ownership of traded equities in the IDX, and the foreign ownership of traded equities in the IDX, that seems to be aligning with the growth of JKSE price from 2018 until the end of testing period of this research that is the month of October 2022. The growth for each year is based on YoY growth calculated at the end of the full year, bar for the growth in October 2022 that was compared with the indicators' statistics at full year 2021. Unlike the other indicators, the growth of number of investors is significantly larger in percentage size due to the IDX's success in attracting increasing participation of investors whereby according to Indonesia Central Securities Depository (KSEI, 2022) the number of investors in the IDX splendidly increase from 1,619,372 investors in 2018 to 9,975,261 investors in October 2022.

The growing number of investors have contributed to the rising ownership of investments in the IDX for both domestic and foreign investors, whereby domestic investors accounted for 3,843.34 trillion Rupiah and foreign investors accounted for 3,173.44 trillion Rupiah in 2018. After enduring the sudden impacts of global pandemic in 2020, the market capitalization of IDX grew in 2021 YoY at 18.45% and 2021 – October/2022 at 14.10%. This growth of IDX's market capitalization is supported by the increasing money invested into the stock exchange as capitals, with domestic investments contributing to 5,454.18 trillion Rupiah and foreign investments contributing to 3,965.82 trillion Rupiah per October 2022. Based on the growth of the IDX indicators shown in Figure 4.11, the author of this research emphasizes that accurate and viable ARIMA forecasting model's predictions of the JKSE price must be in accordance with the actual growth of the JKSE price along with other indicators outside of the ARIMA model which may also affect the price formulations of monthly JKSE such as number

of investors, market capitalization, and domestic and foreign investments. The estimated forecast earnings from this research's ARIMA(20,1,1) model at 5% from testing period of January – October 2022 corresponds positively with the growth indicators listed in Figure 4.11 in period of 2021 – October/2022.

CHAPTER V

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1. Conclusion

The primary objective of this research is to formulate projections of the JKSE monthly prices from January to October, 2022, using the past observations of the index from May, 1990, to December, 2021, through the ARIMA forecast modeling approach. The main assumption of the ARIMA method that is the stationarity of the time series data, is achieved through transformation of the actual JKSE values into logarithm to the base 10, resulting a log-transformed series that is the *IJKSE* and a first difference order imposed on the *IJKSE* series such that the properties of the series indicate constant variance over time and normal distribution of the data. In obtaining stationarity of the *IJKSE* series, empirical results against the weak form of efficient market hypothesis (EMH) are also provided such that ADF test results at level indicate stationarity is not yet achieved by the *IJKSE* series and that Ljung-Box test of correlogram plots infer significant lags on ACF and PACF plots at level, implying that *IJKSE* series is not a random walk. These results of non-stationarity of the *IJKSE* series data observed in training period from 1990 to 2021 produced from ADF unit root and Ljung-Box autocorrelation tests at level, imply that the Indonesia's stock market is not efficient and that the formulation of prices were not random. Empirical results from this research agree with findings from Utami (2018), Gunarso et al., (2017), and Kim & Shamsuddin (2007) that also provided proofs of counter-arguments against the efficient market hypothesis in the analysis of the Jakarta Stock Exchange Composite Index (JKSE), such that past information of the series data can predict the formulations of prices in the future.

The next modelling step after achieving stationarity of the *IJKSE* series is identifying possible ARIMA models to work with is pursued through analysis of plots of autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation functions at lag 1 until lag 36. After careful calculations and parameter estimations based on the least evaluations of errors among candidate models, parameter significance, the largest coefficient of determination among candidate models, and the least information criterion among candidate models, the ARIMA(20,1,1) model is selected as the best fit model for the *IJKSE* data. The selected model is then processed through diagnostic checking where it successfully achieved homoskedasticity based on the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test, state of white noise residuals based on the Ljung-Box test, and invertibility of the model based on the ARMA structure analysis, which significantly indicate that the selected model fits the data well and is appropriate for forecasting use.

The forecasting procedure is finally performed using the selected ARIMA(20,1,1) model where the static forecasts results are superior compared to the dynamic forecast results in terms of RMSE, MAE, and MAPE error measures. The projected outcomes from the selected model's static forecast are then representing the projected outcomes for the *IJKSE* monthly prices in the testing period. The projected *IJKSE* monthly values are consequently transformed back into actual forecasted monthly values to be compared with the actual JKSE monthly prices in January to October, 2022. The forecasting ARIMA(20,1,1) model of this research processes 380 monthly testing observations that provides a forecast of the JKSE monthly prices that differs by 2.23% on average absolute value compared to the actual JKSE monthly prices realizations in the concerned 10 monthly testing observations, indicating a high accuracy of forecast results which is in the range of MAPE less than 10% (Tekindal, 2008). The results of this research concur with previous findings as briefly listed in the followings:

- i. Haerani & Nugraha (2022) that forecasted the JKSE prices using 130 daily observations through ARIMA(2,1,2) model which produced high accuracy of predictions with MAPE at 0.72%
- ii. Pardede (2019) that utilized 226 daily observations processed by ARIMA(2,1,2) , model which forecasted JKSE prices with high accuracy of MAPE at 0.87% despite the relatively low R-squared at 3% that is similar to this research ARIMA(20,1,1) model's R-squared at 5.82%
- iii. Nachrowi (2007) that forecasted JKSE daily prices using 746 daily observations through ARIMA(1,1,0) model with absolute error between the predicted and actual values at only 0.9%
- iv. Mashadihasanli (2022) that forecasted the monthly Istanbul Stock Exchange Composite Index using 147 monthly observations through ARIMA(3,1,5) model with impressive accuracy of MAPE at 1.43% despite having a relatively low ARIMA model's R-squared statistics at 9%
- v. Li et al., (2017) that utilized 142 monthly observations over a span of 12 years period of Shanghai Stock Exchange Composite Index using ARIMA(4,1,4) with high accuracy of MAPE at 2.46%
- vi. Reddy (2019) that forecasted weekly National Stock Exchange of India (NSE) using 187 weekly observations in ARIMA(0,1,0) model with satisfactory accuracy of MAPE at 3.09%
- vii. Jansson & Larsson (2020) that utilized 384 monthly observations over a span of 32 years observation period of Stockholm Composite Index processed in ARIMA(0,1,1) model with satisfactory accuracy of MAPE at 6.00%

- viii. Pillay (2020) that forecasted the Johannesburg Stock Exchange Composite Index with 251 monthly observations through $ARIMA(4,1,4)$ with sufficient accuracy of MAPE at 24.28%

The resolution of using monthly intervals for the time series data also concurs with Mashadihasanli (2022), Jansson & Larsson (2020), Pillay (2020), and Li et al., (2017), such that the 380 monthly observations taken as training samples in this research are not resulting in any autocorrelation or heteroskedasticity or unequal residuals distribution issues in the data after being processed by the selected $ARIMA(20,1,1)$ model. As for the log-transformation conducted to the initial JKSE training samples time series, this research accords with Pillay (2020) and Yenice & Tekindal (2015) whereby a transformation of the series into logarithm values induces better statistical inference of the data, especially in obtaining normal distribution of stock index prices which commonly have high and unstable variances over longer period of time.

5.2. Research Limitation

This research has provided empirical evidence to back the claims of ARIMA method's ability in producing forecast outcomes in a certain period outside of the observation period of the data, through the modeling of the data's own past observed values. Nevertheless, this research is restricted to the analysis of Jakarta Stock Exchange Composite Index (JKSE) prices in the stock market of Indonesia. The forecasting model used in this research is also utilizing a time series data that is modified into logarithm time series values since the original JKSE monthly prices observed throughout the training period did not exhibit normal distribution. Therefore, this research's results are limited to analyzing how the time series forecasting approach of the ARIMA method produces projections of the JKSE monthly prices, with respect to the index's

actual price values for the accuracy estimation of the forecasting model predictive performance.

The coefficient of determination or R-squared value from the best ARIMA model in this research is also relatively low, at 0.058283, implying the independent variables used in the ARIMA modeling which are the lagged values of the dependent variable itself and errors of the dependent variable across the specified training period is only able to explain 5.83% of the variance in the dependent variable. The author of this research realizes the constraints of the relatively low R-squared of 5.83%, however, this research tries to analyze a time series model that focuses more on how well the model predicts future values, instead of how well the model fits past values. The concentration of R-squared in time series forecasting analysis majorly reflects the fitness with past values and not the precision with future values. Therefore, the author of this research realizes a trade-off of a high fit to the past values by constantly increasing regressor into the ARIMA model, but consequently, a higher fit of R-squared might lead astray the accuracy of the forecasting models and overfitting of ARIMA parameters. As a result, this research persists with accuracy measurement of RMSE, MAE, and MAPE that produces the best ARIMA model to predict the *IJKSE* series. In this regard, there remains a room for improvement in the application of ARIMA model to forecast the monthly JKSE prices with better R-squared value than that of this research regression model without any exorbitant and immoderate utilization of independent variables following the methodology of the Box-Jenkins framework.

5.3. Implications

As for relating the movements of a stock market's index with the general conditions of a country's economy, fluctuations of the stock market index can be a benchmark of the

occurring economic situations, in a sense that the index price tends to increase hand-in-hand with a better economic performance of the country - conversely, the index price tends to decrease as the country's economy shrinks (Grestandhi et al., 2011). The time series forecasting analysis of the JKSE monthly prices is also expected by the author to be of useful contribution for investors decision making on investing in any stock market across the globe in general and particularly in the Indonesia's stock market, through the iterative and thorough forecasting analysis of the Box-Jenkins methodology studied in this research.

In the macroeconomic regulatory stand of view, the analytical process that has been undertaken by this research in producing empirical results which show the ARIMA model's strength to predict JKSE prices, can be implied as an insightful line of thought in the policy making of a macroeconomic variable. This policy implication concurs with Jamal et al., (2018), whereby the study came up with a negative and significant effect of the Bank Indonesia 7-Day Reverse Repo Rate (BI7DRR) on the fluctuations of JKSE prices based on monthly observations from June, 2005, to June, 2016.

Another macroeconomic variable that can be relevant to the subject of this research's policy implications is the exchange rate whereby Novita & Nachrowi (2005) suggested that fluctuations of domestic and foreign exchange rates affect global market competition and trade balance which would eventually influence economic output of a country, whilst affecting companies' current and future cash flows such that the companies' stocks prices would also be impacted. This policy implication is based on the analogy where a company that also operates internationally will benefit from depreciation of domestic currency because export revenue incurred in foreign currencies will have larger value when exchanged back into domestic currency. The depreciation of domestic currency too infers domestic goods

being valued cheaper to similar goods in foreign countries that don't experience a depreciation as such the domestic goods can be competitively priced in the global market *ceteris paribus*. On the other hand, an appreciation of domestic currency will benefit companies oriented in importing foreign goods as the domestic currency will be more valuable when exchanged to foreign currency. Whichever the exchange rates scenario taking place in the domestic country, the domestic companies reaping its benefits would theoretically obtain larger revenue that can improve their financial reports (Novita & Nachrowi, 2005) and thus, provide good sentiments for the companies' stocks prices.

In this reasoning, an adequate forecast of the JKSE index for a given future period based on its previous trends such as the one pursued in this research, is helpful for policymakers to adjust and/or establish economic factors that can affect the changes in macroeconomic variables such as gross domestic product, lending rates, exchange rates, etc. Specifically for the lending rate benchmark in Indonesian economy, that is the BI7DRR or also generally perceived as the BI rate, in which its changes can significantly affect individuals and businesses ability of performing business activities through investments funded by loans (Jamal et al., 2018), this research provides an analytical procedure and empirical results that can help policymakers to foresee stock market's performance in a particular time ahead - by acknowledging the BI rate's negative and significant effect on the JKSE index, implying a decrease in the JKSE price movements as the BI rate increases (Hanitha et al., 2023; Febriaty, 2019).

5.4. Recommendation

Based on the procedure undertaken and results estimated from the ARIMA forecast modeling in this research, the author suggests that the analysis of stock market index price formulations,

especially for the JKSE price, can be furthermore studied in order to determine better forecasting approaches as technology continuously advances. The topic of stock market index forecasting analysis is insightful both for educational purposes and occupational research for professionals that relate with the fields of investments and capital markets. The nature of price movements for stocks and stock index prices are unpredictable as well as volatile during irregular times of global and local economic uncertainty.

Therefore, the author of this research believes a provision of statistically significant forecasting method can efficiently help investors, policymakers, etc., to navigate through the uncertainty of stock market realizations, in their pursuit of capital gains from investments and regulation establishments in a country as a macroeconomic variable like investment can positively affect the economy's condition and individuals' well-being when regulated accordingly. The author also acknowledges that further studies can employ different sets of JKSE time series data to obtain better model estimations which affect the forecast results, using the Box-Jenkins methodology or other possible methods that are viable in processing univariate time series data such as a stock market index price.

REFERENCE

- Ackert, L. F., & Deaves, R. (2010). *Behavioral Finance: Psychology, Decision-Making and Markets*. Mason: South-Wester Cengage Learning.
- Agustin, I. N. (2019). Testing Weak Form of Stock Market Efficiency at the Indonesia Sharia Stock Index. *Muqtasid: Jurnal Ekonomi dan Perbankan Syariah*, 10(1), 17-29.
- Al Arif, N. R. M. (2012). *Dasar-Dasar Pemasaran Bank Syariah*. Alfabeta.
- Almazan, A., Brown, K. C., Carlson, M., & Chapman, D. A. (2004). Why Constrain Your Mutual Fund Manager? *Journal of Financial Economics*, 73(2), 289-321.
- Babbie, E. (2007). *Tile Practice of Social Research*. *Istanbul Bilgi University Library*.
- Baker, S. R., Bloom, N., Davis, S. J., Kost, K. J., Sammon, M. C., & Viratyosin, T. (2021). The Unprecedented Stock Market Reaction to COVID-19. *The Review of Asset Pricing Studies*, 11(4), 742-758.
- Barber, B. M., & Odean, T. (2008). All that Glitters: The Effect of Attention and News on the Buying Behavior of Individual and Institutional Investors. *The Review of Financial Studies*, 21(2), 758-818.
- Barber, B. M., Lee, Y. T., Liu, Y. J., & Odean, T. (2009). Just How Much Do Individual Investors Lose by Trading? *The Review of Financial Studies*, 22(2), 609-632.
- Bareksa. (2023, July 18). Capped Adjusted Free Float Market Capitalization Weighted Average. Retrieved from Bareksa.com: <https://www.bareksa.com/berita/tag/capped-adjusted-free-float-market-capitalization-weighted-average>.
- Baresa, S., Bogdan, S., & Ivanovic, Z. (2013). Strategy of Stock Valuation by Fundamental Analysis. *UTMS Journal of Economics*, 4(1), 45-51.
- Box, G. E. P., & Jenkins, G. M. (1970). *Time Series Analysis, Forecasting, and Control*. San Fransisco: Holden Bay.
- Box, G. E. P., Jenkins, G. W., Reinsel, G. C., & Ljung, G. M. (1976). *Time Series Analysis: Forecasting and Control*. San Francisco: Holden Bay.
- Box, G. E., Jenkins, G. M., Reinsel, G. C., & Ljung, G. M. (2015). *Time Series Analysis: Forecasting and Control*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Brooks, C. (2014). Modeling Long-run Relationships in Finance. *Introductory Econometrics for Finance (3rd Edition)*. Cambridge University Press.
- Brown, R. G. (1963). Smoothing. *Forecasting and Prediction of Discrete Time Series*, 127.

- Byrne, B. M., & Van de Vijver, F. J. (2010). Testing for Measurement and Structural Equivalence in Large-Scale Cross-Cultural Studies: Addressing the Issue of Nonequivalence. *International Journal of Testing*, 10(2), 107-132.
- Central Bureau of Statistics of Indonesia, (2022, December 11). Transaksi dan Indeks Saham di Bursa Efek 2019-2022. Retrieved from Bps.go.id: <https://www.bps.go.id/indicator/13/125/2/transaksi-dan-indeks-saham-di-bursa-efek.html>.
- Chai, T., & Draxler, R. R. (2014). Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) or Mean Absolute Error (MAE)? Arguments Against Avoiding RMSE in the Literature. *Geoscientific model development*, 7(3), 1247-1250.
- Chang, C. L., Sriboonchitta, S., & Wiboonpongse, A. (2009). Modeling and Forecasting Tourism from East Asia to Thailand under Temporal and Spatial Aggregation. *Mathematics and Computers in Simulation*, 79(5), 1730-1744.
- Chatfield, C., & Prothero, D. L. (1973). Box-Jenkins Seasonal Forecasting: Problems in a Case-Study. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series A (General)*, 136(3), 293-315.
- Chen, Y. J., Chen, Y. M., Tsao, S. T., & Hsieh, S. F. (2018). A Novel Technical Analysis-based Method for Stock Market Forecasting. *Soft Computing*, 22, 1295-1312.
- Cryer, J. D., & Chan, K. S. (2008). Model for Stationary Time Series. *Time Series Analysis: With Applications in R*, 66-77.
- Dadhich, M., Pahwa, M. S., Jain, V., & Doshi, R. (2021). Predictive Models for Stock Market Index using Stochastic Time Series ARIMA Modeling in Emerging Economy. In *Advances in Mechanical Engineering: Select Proceedings of CAMSE 2020*, 281-290. Springer Singapore.
- Dickey, D. A., & Fuller, W. A. (1979). Distribution of the Estimators for Autoregressive Time Series with a Unit Root. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 427-431.
- Eke, C. N. (2019). Time Series Analysis on Monthly Stock Market Returns of the Nigerian Stock Exchange. An ARIMA Modeling Approach. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 11(4), 1-9.
- Etuk, H. E., Uchendu, B., & Udo, E. O. (2012). Box-Jenkins Modeling of Nigerian Stock Prices Data. *Greener Journal of Science Engineering and Technological Research*, 2(2), 32-38.
- Fama, E. F. (1970). Efficient Capital Markets: A Review of Theory and Empirical Work. *The Journal of Finance*, 25(2), 383-417.
- Febriaty, H. (2019). The Effect of Economic Indicators on Movement of Composite Stock Price Index in Indonesia Stock Exchange. *Journal of International Conference Proceedings*, 2(1), 43.
- Forbes, W. (2009). Behavioral Finance. John Wiley & Sons.

- George, D., & Mallery, P. (2010). *SPSS for Windows Step by Step. A Simple Guide and Reference 17.0 Update 10th Edition*. Pearson.
- Gujarati, D. N., & Porter, D. (2009). *Basic Econometrics Fifth Edition*. McGraw-Hill.
- Gunarso, A., Siregar, H., & Irawan, T. (2017). The Stock Market of Infrastructure Sector: A Weak-Form EMH Test. *International Journal of Science and Research*, 6(2), 2015-2018.
- Grestandhi, J., Susanto, B., & Mahatma, T. (2011). Analisis Perbandingan Metode Peramalan Indeks Harga Saham Gabungan (IHSG) dengan Metode OLS-ARCH/GARCH dan ARIMA.
- Haerani, S. L. S., & Nugraha, E. S. (2022). ARIMA Model in Predicting Jakarta Composite Index. *Journal of Actuarial, Finance, and Risk Management*, 1(1), 27-35.
- Hanitha, V., Yoyo, T., & Silaswara, D. (2023). Analysis Effect of BI Rates, Inflation and Exchange Rates on the Composite Stock Price Index on the Indonesia Stock Exchange 2016-2021.
- Harvey, A. C. (1990). *The Econometric Analysis of Time Series*. MIT Press.
- Harrison, P. J. (1965). Short-Term Sales Forecasting. *Appl. Statist.*, 14, 102-139.
- Hunt, S. D. (2007). Economic Growth: Should Policy Focus on Investment or Dynamic Competition? *European Business Review*, 19(4), 274-291.
- Hurst, B., Ooi, Y. H., & Pedersen, L. H. (2017). A Century of Evidence on Trend-Following Investing. *The Journal of Portfolio Management*, 44(1), 15-29.
- Hyndman, R. J., & Athanasopoulos, G. (2018). *Forecasting: Principles and Practice*. OTexts.
- IDX. (2022, July 18). Data Pasar: Daftar Saham. Retrieved from [Idx.co.id: https://www.idx.co.id/id/data-pasar/data-saham/daftar-saham](https://www.idx.co.id/id/data-pasar/data-saham/daftar-saham).
- IDX. (2023, July 18). Indeks Saham: Daftar Indeks-Indeks di BEI beserta Tanggal Peluncuran, Tanggal Dasar, dan Nilai Awal; Daftar Indeks berdasarkan Metode Perhitungannya. Retrieved from [Idx.co.id: https://www.idx.co.id/id/produk/indeks](https://www.idx.co.id/id/produk/indeks).
- Indonesia Central Securities Depository. (2022, December 11). Statistik Pasar Modal Indonesia: Oktober 2022. Kustodian Sentral Efek Indonesia. Retrieved from [Ksei.co.id: https://www.ksei.co.id/files/Statistik_Publik_-_Oktober_2022_v2.pdf](https://www.ksei.co.id/files/Statistik_Publik_-_Oktober_2022_v2.pdf)
- Indonesia Central Securities Depository. (2022, December 11). Statistik Pasar Modal Indonesia: Desember 2021. Kustodian Sentral Efek Indonesia. Retrieved from [Ksei.co.id: https://www.ksei.co.id/files/Statistik_Publik_Desember_2021.pdf](https://www.ksei.co.id/files/Statistik_Publik_Desember_2021.pdf)
- Indonesia Central Securities Depository. (2022, December 11). Statistik Pasar Modal Indonesia: Desember 2020. Kustodian Sentral Efek Indonesia. Retrieved from [Ksei.co.id: https://www.ksei.co.id/files/Statistik_Web_-_Desember_20202.pdf](https://www.ksei.co.id/files/Statistik_Web_-_Desember_20202.pdf)
- International Monetary Fund. (2019). Indonesia: 2019 Article IV Consultation. International Monetary Fund, Country Report No. 19/285.

- Jamal, A., Salim, J., Seftarita, C., Mahmud, M. S., Daud, W. M. N. W., Ghazali, P. L., & Rashid, N. (2018). Does Monetary Policy and ASEAN Stock Market Affect Jakarta Composite Index (IHSG)? *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 8(12), 1236-1248.
- Jansson, P., & Larsson, H. (2020). ARIMA Modeling: Forecasting Indices on the Stockholm Stock Exchange.
- Karanikola, A., Liapis, C. M., & Kotsiantis, S. (2021). A Comparison of Contemporary Methods on Univariate Time Series Forecasting. *Learning and Analytics in Intelligent Systems*, 143-168.
- Kim, J. H., & Shamsuddin, A. (2007). Are Asian Stock Markets Efficient? Evidence from New Multiple Variance Ratio Tests. *Journal of Empirical Finance*, 15, 528-523.
- Kim, W., & Wei, S. J. (2002). Foreign Portfolio Investors before and during a Crisis. *Journal of international economics*, 56(1), 77-96.
- Krugman, P. (1995). Dutch Tulips and Emerging Markets. *Foreign Aff.*, 74, 28.
- Krugman, P. (2009). How Did Economists Get It So Wrong?. *New York Times*, 2(9).
- Laeven, M. L., & Valencia, M. F. (2012). Systemic Banking Crises Database; An update. International Monetary Fund.
- Li, C., Yang, B., & Li, M. (2017). Forecasting Analysis of Shanghai Stock Index based on ARIMA model. In *MATEC Web of Conferences*, 100, 02029. EDP Sciences.
- Li, Y., Wu, K., & Liu, J. (2023). Self-paced ARIMA for Robust Time Series Prediction. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 269, 110489.
- Lucas Jr, R. E. (1976). Econometric Policy Evaluation: A Critique, in K Brunner and A Meltzer (eds), *The Phillips Curve and Labour Markets*, *Carnegie-Rochester Conference Series on Public Policy*, 1.
- Maddala, G. (1992). *Introduction to Econometrics, Second Edition*. Macmillan Publishing Company.
- Makridakis, S., Wheelwright, S. C., & Hyndman, R. J. (2008). *Forecasting Methods and Applications*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Malkiel, B. G. (1973). *A Random Walk Down Wall Street [by] Burton G. Malkiel*. Norton.
- Malkiel, B. G. (2019). *A Random Walk down Wall Street: The Time-Tested Strategy for Successful Investing*. WW Norton & Company.
- Mashadihasanli, T. (2022). Stock Market Price Forecasting using the ARIMA Model: An Application to Istanbul, Turkiye. *Iktisat Politikasi Arastirmalan Dergisi - Journal of Economic Policy Researches*, 9(2), 439-454.

- Merh, N., Saxena, V. P., & Pardasani, K. R. (2010). A Comparison between Hybrid Approaches of ANN and ARIMA for Indian Stock Trend Forecasting. *Business Intelligence Journal*, 3(2), 23-43.
- Meyler, A., Kenny, G., & Quinn, T. (1998). Forecasting Irish Inflation using ARIMA Models. *Research Technical Papers 3/RT/98, Central Bank of Ireland*.
- Miswan, N. H., Ngatiman, N. A., Hamzah, K., & Zamzamin, Z. Z. (2014). Comparative Performance of ARIMA and GARCH Models in Modelling and Forecasting Volatility of Malaysia Market Properties and Shares. *Applied Mathematical Sciences*, 8(140), 7001-7012.
- Montgomery, D. C., Jennings, C. L., & Kulahci, M. (2015). *Introduction to Time Series Analysis and Forecasting*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Mulyono, S. (2000). Peramalan Harga Saham dan Nilai Tukar: Teknik Box-Jenkins. *Ekonomi dan Keuangan Indonesia*, 48(2), 125-141.
- Murwaningsari, E. (2008). Pengaruh Volume Perdagangan Saham, Deposito, dan Kurs terhadap IHSB beserta Prediksi IHSB (Model GARCH dan ARIMA). *Journal of Indonesian Economy and Business (JIEB)*, 23(2), 178-195.
- Muschilati, E., & Irsalinda, N. (2020). Forecasting Tourist Visit using the Vector Autoregressive Exogenous Method (VARX). *Jurnal Ilmiah Matematika*, 7(2), 81.
- Novita, M., & Nachrowi, N. D. (2005). Dynamic Analysis of the Stock Price Index and the Exchange Rate using Vector Auto Regression (VAR): An Empirical Study in Jakarta Stock Exchange 2001-2004. *Journal of Economics and Finance in Indonesia*, 53(3), 263-278.
- Nachrowi, N. D., & Usman, H. (2007). Prediksi IHSB dengan Model GARCH dan Model ARIMA. *Jurnal Ekonomi dan Pembangunan Indonesia*, 7(2), 199-217.
- NGX Group. (2022, July 28). NGX Market Data Price List. Retrieved from [Ngxgroup.com: https://ngxgroup.com/exchange/data/historical-data/](https://ngxgroup.com/exchange/data/historical-data/)
- Pai, P. F., & Lin, C. S. (2005). A Hybrid ARIMA and Support Vector Machines Model in Stock Price Forecasting. *Omega*, 33(6), 497-505.
- Pankratz, A. (2012). *Forecasting with Dynamic Regression Models*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Pavlov, O., & Yang, J. (2010). Stock Market Efficiency of Ukraine, China and Russia in Comparison to USA.
- Pardede, P. (2019). Penerapan Model ARIMA dalam Memprediksi Indeks Harga Saham Gabungan Bursa Efek Indonesia-Jakarta. *MPU Procuratio*, 1(1 April), 92-103.
- Parvin, S., & Khanam, M. (2018). Comparison between ARIMA and VAR Model regarding the Forecasting of the Price of Jute Goods in Bangladesh. *Dhaka University Journal of Science*, 66(2), 91-94.

- Pianda, D. (2018). Optimasi Perencanaan Produksi pada Kombinasi Produk dengan Metode Linear Programming. CV Jejak.
- Pillay, S. (2020). Determining the Optimal ARIMA Model for Forecasting the Share Price Index of the Johannesburg Stock Exchange. *Journal of Management Information and Decision Sciences*, 23(5), 527-528.
- Pohan, F. A. (2022). Forecasting Harga Saham pada PT Astra International Tbk. Menggunakan Metode ARIMA.
- Pokorny, M. (1987). *An Introduction to Econometrics*. B. Blackwell, 343.
- Putri, R., & Manurung, A. H. P. (2021). Determinants of Investors Behavior in Indonesian Capital Market. *Journal of Economics, Business, and Accountancy Ventura*, 24(3), 497-512.
- Reddy, C. V. (2019). Predicting the Stock Market Index using Stochastic Time Series ARIMA Modeling. The Sample of BSE and NSE. *Indian Journal of Finance*, 13(8), 7-25.
- Reid, D. J. (1971). A Comparison of Forecasting Techniques on Economic Time-Series. *Paper of the Operational Research Society*.
- Reinhart, C. M., & Rogoff, K. S. (2011). From Financial Crash to Debt Crisis. *American Economic Review*, 101(5), 1676-1706.
- Nau, R. (2014). The Mathematical Structure of Arima Models. *Duke University Online Article*. 1(1), 1-8.
- Robert, S. P., & Daniel, L. R. (1998). *Econometric Models and Economic Forecasts*. Irwin and Mcgraw-Hill.
- Roberts, W. D., & Stone, P. W. (2003). How to Choose and Evaluate a Research Instrument. *Applied Nursing Research*, 16(1), 70-72.
- Rode, D., Parikh, S., Friedman, Y., & Kane, J. (1995). An Evolutionary Approach to Technical Trading and Capital Market Efficiency. *The Wharton School University of Pennsylvania*, 1.
- Rounaghi, M. M., & Zadeh, F. N. (2016). Investigation of Market Efficiency and Financial Stability between S&P 500 and London Stock Exchange: Monthly and Yearly Forecasting of Time Series Stock Returns using ARMA Model. *Physica A: Statistical Mechanics and its Applications*, 456, 10-21.
- Sadeq, A. (2008). Analisis Prediksi Indeks Harga Saham Gabungan dengan Metode ARIMA (Studi pada IHSG di Bursa Efek Jakarta). University of Stuttgart.
- Sartono, B. (2006). *Pelatihan Time Series Analysis*. Institut Pertanian Bogor.
- Sims, C. A. (1980). Macroeconomics and Reality. *Econometrica: Journal of The Econometric Society*, 1-48.

- Soemantri, Y., & Setiawan, K. (2017). The Presence of Structural Breaks in the Indonesian Capital Market as a result of the Second Cabinet Reshuffle Announcement. Gadjah Mada University.
- Solow, R. M. (1956). A Contribution to the Theory of Economic Growth. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 70(1), 65-94.
- Solow, R. M. (1957). Technical Change and the Aggregate Production Function. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 39(3), 312-320.
- Statista. (2021, July 1). Leading Stock Exchanges in the Asia Pacific Region 2021, by Domestic Market Capitalization. Retrieved from Statista.com: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/265236/domestic-market-capitalization-in-the-asia-pacific-region/>.
- Stiglitz, J. E., Orszag, J. M. & Orszag, P. R. (2002). Implications of the New Fannie Mae and Freddie Mac Risk-Based Capital Standard. *Fannie Mae Papers*.
- Taneja, A. (2019). To Predict Accurate Silver MCX Trend in Indian Stock Market using Box-Jenkins Method (Doctoral Dissertation).
- Tekindal, M. A. (2008). Modeling the Stock Indexes of the European Union Countries and Turkey and Evaluating Forecasts for the Future. Proceedings of 17th Statistics Research Symposium of Turk Stat, 135-153.
- Tofallis, C. (2015). A Better Measure of Relative Prediction Accuracy for Model Selection and Model Estimation. *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 66, 1352-1362.
- Trading Economics. (2023, July 1). Malaysia Stock Market (FBM KLCI). Retrieved from Tradingeconomics.com: <https://tradingeconomics.com/malaysia/stock-market>.
- Trading Economics. (2023, July 1). Philippines Stock Market (PSEi). Retrieved from Tradingeconomics.com: <https://tradingeconomics.com/philippines/stock-market>.
- Trading Economics. (2023, July 1). Singapore Stock Market (STI). Retrieved from Tradingeconomics.com: <https://tradingeconomics.com/singapore/stock-market>.
- Trading Economics. (2023, July 1). Thailand Stock Market (SET). Retrieved from Tradingeconomics.com: <https://tradingeconomics.com/thailand/stock-market>.
- Tsay, R. S. (2005). *Analysis of Financial Time Series*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Utami, A. T. (2018). Efisiensi Pasar Bentuk Lemah Pada Pasar Modal Indonesia, Malaysia, dan Korea Selatan Periode Krisis Ekonomi Global 2008. *Jurnal Inspirasi Bisnis dan Manajemen*, 2(2), 101-116.
- Voss, M. S., & Feng, X. (2002). ARMA Model Selection Using Particle Swarm Optimization and AIC Criteria. *IFAC Proceedings Volumes*, 35(1), 349-354.
- Wahyudi, S. T. (2017). The ARIMA Model for the Indonesia Stock Price. *International Journal of Economics & Management*, 11.

- Wei, W. W. S. (2006). *Time Series Analysis: Univariate and Multivariate Methods*. Pearson Addison Wesley.
- Wei, W. W. S. (2018). *Multivariate Time Series Analysis and Applications*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Winters, P. R. (1960). Forecasting Sales by Exponentially Weighted Moving Averages. *Man. Sci.* 6, 324-342.
- World Bank. (2010). Indonesia: Managing the Transition from Recovery to Sustainable Growth. World Bank Report.
- World Bank. (2021). Indonesia Economic Prospects: January 2021. World Bank Report.
- World Bank. (2023, July 1). GDP (Constant LCU) - Indonesia. Retrieved from Data.worldbank.org:
<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.KN?locations=ID>.
- Yahoo Finance. (2022, October 10). Jakarta Composite Index. Retrieved from Finance.yahoo.com:
<https://finance.yahoo.com/quote/%5EJKSE/history?period1=639446400&period2=1667174400&interval=1mo&filter=history&frequency=1mo&includeAdjustedClose=true>.
- Yenice, S. & Tekindal, M. A. (2015). Forecasting the Stock Indexes of Fragile Five Countries through Box-Jenkins Methods. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 6(8), 180-191.

APPENDIX I

JKSE MONTHLY PRICE TIME SERIES

Date DD/MM/YYYY	Monthly Close Price of JKSE	Log(base10) of JKSE	Date DD/MM/YYYY	Monthly Close Price of JKSE	Log(base10) of JKSE	Date DD/MM/YYYY	Monthly Close Price of JKSE	Log(base10) of JKSE	Date DD/MM/YYYY	Monthly Close Price of JKSE	Log(base10) of JKSE	Date DD/MM/YYYY	Monthly Close Price of JKSE	Log(base10) of JKSE
01/05/1990	636,400024	2,803730	01/09/1996	573,939026	2,758866	01/01/2003	388,442993	2,589327	01/05/2009	1916,831055	3,282584	01/09/2015	4223,908203	3,625714
01/06/1990	624,320007	2,795407	01/10/1996	568,028992	2,754371	01/02/2003	399,220001	2,601212	01/06/2009	2026,780029	3,306807	01/10/2015	4455,180176	3,648865
01/07/1990	614,406006	2,788455	01/11/1996	613,013000	2,787470	01/03/2003	398,003998	2,599887	01/07/2009	2323,236084	3,366903	01/11/2015	4446,458008	3,648014
01/08/1990	571,020020	2,756651	01/12/1996	637,432007	2,804434	01/04/2003	450,860992	2,654043	01/08/2009	2341,537109	3,369501	01/12/2015	4593,007813	3,662097
01/09/1990	468,509003	2,670718	01/01/1997	691,116028	2,839551	01/05/2003	494,776001	2,694409	01/09/2009	2467,591064	3,392723	01/01/2016	4615,163086	3,664187
01/10/1990	416,489014	2,619604	01/02/1997	705,374023	2,848419	01/06/2003	505,948993	2,703720	01/10/2009	2367,700928	3,374327	01/02/2016	4770,956055	3,678605
01/11/1990	382,203003	2,582294	01/03/1997	662,236023	2,821013	01/07/2003	507,984985	2,705851	01/11/2009	2415,836914	3,383068	01/03/2016	4845,371094	3,685327
01/12/1990	417,787994	2,620956	01/04/1997	652,049011	2,814280	01/08/2003	529,674988	2,724009	01/12/2009	2534,355957	3,403868	01/04/2016	4838,583008	3,684718
01/01/1991	383,018005	2,582519	01/05/1997	696,028015	2,842627	01/09/2003	597,952178	2,776448	01/01/2010	2610,795898	3,416773	01/05/2016	4796,869141	3,680958
01/02/1991	391,329987	2,592543	01/06/1997	724,556030	2,860072	01/10/2003	625,546021	2,796259	01/02/2010	2549,032959	3,406375	01/06/2016	5016,646973	3,700414
01/03/1991	408,109985	2,610777	01/07/1997	721,270020	2,858098	01/11/2003	617,083984	2,790344	01/03/2010	2777,301025	3,443623	01/07/2016	5215,994141	3,717337
01/04/1991	413,713013	2,616699	01/08/1997	493,962006	2,693694	01/12/2003	860,895020	2,840404	01/04/2010	2971,251953	3,472999	01/08/2016	5386,082031	3,731273
01/05/1991	397,600006	2,599446	01/09/1997	546,687988	2,737740	01/01/2004	752,932007	2,876756	01/05/2010	2796,957031	3,446886	01/09/2016	5364,804199	3,729554
01/06/1991	346,265991	2,539410	01/10/1997	500,417999	2,699333	01/02/2004	761,080994	2,881431	01/06/2010	2913,684082	3,464442	01/10/2016	5422,541992	3,734203
01/07/1991	339,958008	2,531425	01/11/1997	401,708008	2,603910	01/03/2004	735,677002	2,866687	01/07/2010	3069,280029	3,487037	01/11/2016	5148,910156	3,711715
01/08/1991	300,980011	2,478538	01/12/1997	401,712006	2,603915	01/04/2004	783,413025	2,893991	01/08/2010	3081,884033	3,488816	01/12/2016	5296,710938	3,724006
01/09/1991	249,186996	2,386255	01/01/1998	485,937988	2,686581	01/05/2004	860,152991	2,864817	01/09/2010	3501,295898	3,544229	01/01/2017	5294,030207	3,723792
01/10/1991	226,684006	2,355421	01/02/1998	482,377991	2,683387	01/06/2004	732,401001	2,864749	01/10/2010	3635,323975	3,560543	01/02/2017	5386,691895	3,731322
01/11/1991	241,317993	2,382590	01/03/1998	541,424988	2,733538	01/07/2004	597,952178	2,776448	01/11/2010	3531,210998	3,547924	01/03/2017	5668,105957	3,745707
01/12/1991	247,389999	2,393382	01/04/1998	460,135010	2,662885	01/08/2004	754,703979	2,877777	01/12/2010	3703,511963	3,568614	01/04/2017	5685,297852	3,754573
01/01/1992	282,240997	2,450620	01/05/1998	420,464996	2,623730	01/09/2004	820,133972	2,913885	01/01/2011	3409,166992	3,532648	01/05/2017	5738,154785	3,758772
01/02/1992	280,994995	2,448699	01/06/1998	449,920013	2,649257	01/10/2004	860,895020	2,934744	01/02/2011	3470,347900	3,540373	01/06/2017	5829,708008	3,765647
01/03/1992	278,687988	2,445118	01/07/1998	481,717010	2,682792	01/11/2004	977,670209	2,990235	01/03/2011	3678,674072	3,565691	01/07/2017	5840,938965	3,766483
01/04/1992	277,235977	2,442909	01/08/1998	342,436005	2,534759	01/12/2004	1000,232971	3,000101	01/04/2011	3819,617920	3,582020	01/08/2017	5864,059082	3,768198
01/05/1992	299,220001	2,475991	01/09/1998	276,149994	2,441145	01/01/2005	1045,435059	3,019297	01/05/2011	3836,967041	3,583988	01/09/2017	5900,854004	3,770915
01/06/1992	313,559998	2,496321	01/10/1998	300,769989	2,478234	01/02/2005	1073,828003	3,030935	01/06/2011	3888,569092	3,589790	01/10/2017	6005,784180	3,778570
01/07/1992	317,190002	2,501319	01/11/1998	386,270996	2,586892	01/03/2005	1080,165039	3,033490	01/07/2011	4130,798005	3,616034	01/11/2017	5952,138184	3,774673
01/08/1992	301,279999	2,478780	01/12/1998	398,037994	2,599925	01/04/2005	1029,613037	3,012674	01/08/2011	3841,730957	3,584527	01/12/2017	6355,653809	3,803160
01/09/1992	298,390015	2,474784	01/01/1999	411,932007	2,614826	01/05/2005	1088,168945	3,036696	01/09/2011	3549,031982	3,550110	01/01/2018	6065,630859	3,819914
01/10/1992	307,579987	2,487958	01/02/1999	396,088989	2,597793	01/06/2005	1122,375977	3,050138	01/10/2011	3790,846924	3,578736	01/02/2018	6597,217773	3,819361
01/11/1992	285,600006	2,455758	01/03/1999	393,625000	2,595083	01/07/2005	1182,301025	3,072728	01/11/2011	3715,080078	3,569968	01/03/2018	6188,986816	3,791620
01/12/1992	274,339996	2,438289	01/04/1999	495,221985	2,694800	01/08/2005	1050,089966	3,021227	01/12/2011	3821,991943	3,582290	01/04/2018	5994,595215	3,777760
01/01/1993	280,149994	2,447791	01/05/1999	585,242004	2,767335	01/09/2005	1079,275024	3,033132	01/01/2012	3941,693115	3,595683	01/05/2018	5983,586914	3,776362
01/02/1993	300,380005	2,476761	01/06/1999	662,025024	2,820874	01/10/2005	1066,223999	3,027848	01/02/2012	3985,209961	3,600451	01/06/2018	5799,236816	3,763371
01/03/1993	310,760010	2,492425	01/07/1999	597,874023	2,776610	01/11/2005	1096,640991	3,040064	01/03/2012	4121,550781	3,615061	01/07/2018	5936,442871	3,773526
01/04/1993	314,100006	2,497068	01/08/1999	567,026001	2,753603	01/12/2005	1162,635010	3,065443	01/04/2012	4180,731934	3,621252	01/08/2018	6018,459961	3,779485
01/05/1993	341,850006	2,533836	01/09/1999	547,937012	2,738731	01/01/2006	1232,321045	3,090724	01/05/2012	3832,823975	3,583519	01/09/2018	5976,553223	3,776451
01/06/1993	360,350006	2,556725	01/10/1999	593,869019	2,773691	01/02/2006	1230,663940	3,090139	01/06/2012	3955,576904	3,597210	01/10/2018	5883,649902	3,765791
01/07/1993	350,720001	2,552327	01/11/1999	583,799988	2,766264	01/03/2006	1322,973999	3,121551	01/07/2012	4142,336914	3,617245	01/11/2018	6085,612023	3,812915
01/08/1993	417,299988	2,620448	01/12/1999	676,919006	2,830537	01/04/2006	1464,406006	3,165662	01/08/2012	4060,331055	3,608561	01/12/2018	6194,498047	3,792006
01/09/1993	419,959991	2,623208	01/01/2000	636,372009	2,803711	01/05/2006	1329,995972	3,123850	01/09/2012	4262,561035	3,629671	01/01/2019	6532,969238	3,815111
01/10/1993	466,149994	2,668526	01/02/2000	576,541992	2,760831	01/06/2006	1718,962939	3,171358	01/10/2012	4350,291012	3,638518	01/02/2019	6443,348145	3,809112
01/11/1993	518,780029	2,714983	01/03/2000	583,276001	2,765874	01/07/2006	1351,649048	3,130864	01/11/2012	4276,141113	3,631052	01/03/2019	6468,754883	3,810821
01/12/1993	588,770020	2,769694	01/04/2000	526,737000	2,721594	01/08/2006	1431,261963	3,155719	01/12/2012	4316,687012	3,635151	01/04/2019	6455,352059	3,809920
01/01/1994	592,020020	2,772336	01/05/2000	454,326996	2,657369	01/09/2006	1534,614990	3,185999	01/01/2013	4453,703125	3,648721	01/05/2019	6209,117188	3,793030
01/02/1994	546,229980	2,737376	01/06/2000	515,109985	2,711900	01/10/2006	1582,625977	3,199378	01/02/2013	4795,789063	3,680860	01/06/2019	6358,628906	3,803363
01/03/1994	433,829987	2,637320	01/07/2000	492,192993	2,692135	01/11/2006	1310,961060	3,235266	01/03/2013	4940,985840	3,693814	01/07/2019	6390,504883	3,805535
01/04/1994	462,399994	2,665018	01/08/2000	466,380005	2,668740	01/12/2006	1805,522949	3,256603	01/04/2013	5034,078001	3,701919	01/08/2019	6328,470215	3,801299
01/05/1994	501,790009	2,705222	01/09/2000	421,335999	2,624629	01/01/2007	1757,258005	3,244836	01/05/2013	5068,627930	3,704890	01/09/2019	6169,102051	3,790222
01/06/1994	457,299988	2,660201	01/10/2000	405,346985	2,607827	01/02/2007	1740,970947	3,240792	01/06/2013	4818,895020	3,682947	01/10/2019	6228,316895	3,794371
01/07/1994	451,079987	2,654524	01/11/2000	429,213989	2,632674	01/03/2007	1890,923950	3,262670	01/07/2013	4610,376953	3,663736	01/11/2019	6011,830078	3,779007
01/08/1994	510,260010	2,707792	01/12/2000	416,321014	2,619428	01/04/2007	1939,166992	3,200849	01/08/2013	4195,088867	3,622741	01/12/2019	6299,539063	3,799309
01/09/1994	497,970001	2,697203	01/01/2001	425,614014	2,629016	01/05/2007	2084,323975	3,318965	01/09/2013	4316,175781	3,635099	01/01/2020	5940,047852	3,773790
01/10/1994	523,489990	2,718908	01/02/2001	428,303009	2,631751	01/06/2007	2139,278076	3,330267	01/10/2013	4510,630859	3,654237	01/02/2020	5452,704102	3,736612

APPENDIX I JKSE MONTHLY PRICE TIME SERIES (CONTINUED)

Notes:

1. The JKSE monthly price time series is based on monthly index price data from May 1, 1990, until December 1, 2021. Data are collected from Yahoo Finance and processed by the author using Microsoft Excel for the logarithmic transformation.
2. The JKSE monthly price time series data listed is referred to as the training sample for the forecast modeling of this research.
3. The actual values of the JKSE monthly price time series data are transformed into logarithm to the base 10.

APPENDIX II

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS AND HISTOGRAM OF JKSE SERIES

Source: Author's calculation using EViews 12 Student Version.

APPENDIX III

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS AND HISTOGRAM OF LJKSE SERIES

Source: Author's calculation using EViews 12 Student Version.

APPENDIX IV

AUGMENTED DICKEY-FULLER UNIT ROOT TEST OF IJKSE SERIES BEFORE DIFFERENCING

Null Hypothesis: LJKSE has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 1 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=16)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-0.341149	0.9158
Test critical values: 1% level	-3.446992	
5% level	-2.868771	
10% level	-2.570688	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(LJKSE)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 12/24/22 Time: 02:43
 Sample (adjusted): 1990M07 2021M12
 Included observations: 378 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LJKSE(-1)	-0.001124	0.003295	-0.341149	0.7332
D(LJKSE(-1))	0.197295	0.050053	3.941729	0.0001
C	0.005744	0.010533	0.545359	0.5858
R-squared	0.038815	Mean dependent var		0.002721
Adjusted R-squared	0.033821	S.D. dependent var		0.032109
S.E. of regression	0.031561	Akaike info criterion		-4.066081
Sum squared resid	0.383500	Schwarz criterion		-4.035454
Log likelihood	791.8196	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-4.053938
F-statistic	7.773534	Durbin-Watson stat		1.970553
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000490			

Source: Author's calculation using EViews 12 Student Version.

APPENDIX V

AUGMENTED DICKEY-FULLER UNIT ROOT TEST OF IJKSE SERIES AFTER DIFFERENCING

Null Hypothesis: D(LJKSE) has a unit root
 Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=16)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-16.10696	0.0000
Test critical values: 1% level	-3.446992	
5% level	-2.868771	
10% level	-2.570688	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(LJKSE,2)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 12/24/22 Time: 02:43
 Sample (adjusted): 1990M07 2021M12
 Included observations: 378 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LJKSE(-1))	-0.803754	0.049901	-16.10696	0.0000
C	0.002193	0.001606	1.365518	0.1729
R-squared	0.401953	Mean dependent var		3.06E-05
Adjusted R-squared	0.400404	S.D. dependent var		0.040712
S.E. of regression	0.031525	Akaike info criterion		-4.070933
Sum squared resid	0.383616	Schwarz criterion		-4.050515
Log likelihood	791.7610	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-4.062838
F-statistic	259.4341	Durbin-Watson stat		1.970268
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Author's calculation using EViews 12 Student Version.

APPENDIX VI

CORRELOGRAM OF IJKSE BEFORE DIFFERENCING

Date: 12/24/22 Time: 02:44
 Sample: 1990M05 2021M12
 Included observations: 380

Autocorrelation	Partial Correlation	AC	PAC	Q-Stat	Prob	
		1	0.995	0.995	388.76	0.000
		2	0.988	-0.084	773.59	0.000
		3	0.982	0.006	1154.5	0.000
		4	0.976	-0.012	1531.5	0.000
		5	0.969	-0.052	1904.2	0.000
		6	0.962	-0.021	2272.3	0.000
		7	0.954	-0.024	2635.7	0.000
		8	0.947	0.042	2994.7	0.000
		9	0.940	-0.007	3349.5	0.000
		10	0.934	0.024	3700.1	0.000
		11	0.927	-0.017	4046.5	0.000
		12	0.920	0.008	4388.8	0.000
		13	0.913	-0.019	4727.0	0.000
		14	0.906	-0.032	5060.8	0.000
		15	0.899	0.001	5390.3	0.000
		16	0.892	0.009	5715.6	0.000
		17	0.885	-0.012	6036.6	0.000
		18	0.878	-0.025	6353.2	0.000
		19	0.871	0.013	6665.5	0.000
		20	0.863	-0.008	6973.5	0.000
		21	0.857	0.042	7277.5	0.000
		22	0.850	0.005	7577.6	0.000
		23	0.844	0.009	7874.1	0.000
		24	0.837	0.016	8167.1	0.000
		25	0.831	-0.012	8456.5	0.000
		26	0.825	0.012	8742.6	0.000
		27	0.819	-0.007	9025.3	0.000
		28	0.813	-0.017	9304.6	0.000
		29	0.807	0.032	9580.7	0.000
		30	0.802	-0.006	9853.6	0.000
		31	0.796	-0.021	10123.	0.000
		32	0.790	-0.017	10389.	0.000
		33	0.783	-0.072	10652.	0.000
		34	0.776	-0.011	10910.	0.000
		35	0.768	-0.020	11164.	0.000
		36	0.761	-0.004	11414.	0.000

Source: Author's calculation using EViews 12 Student Version.

APPENDIX VII

CORRELOGRAM OF IJKSE AFTER DIFFERENCING

Date: 12/24/22 Time: 02:45
 Sample: 1990M05 2021M12
 Included observations: 379

Autocorrelation	Partial Correlation	AC	PAC	Q-Stat	Prob	
█	█	1	0.196	0.196	15.097	0.000
		2	-0.035	-0.076	15.577	0.000
		3	0.008	0.031	15.599	0.001
		4	0.045	0.036	16.388	0.003
		5	-0.015	-0.032	16.479	0.006
		6	0.007	0.022	16.498	0.011
		7	-0.062	-0.075	18.031	0.012
		8	-0.026	0.003	18.302	0.019
		9	-0.032	-0.035	18.724	0.028
		10	0.041	0.056	19.410	0.035
		11	-0.028	-0.047	19.722	0.049
		12	-0.002	0.018	19.724	0.072
		13	0.039	0.037	20.335	0.087
		14	0.003	-0.024	20.339	0.120
		15	-0.084	-0.074	23.236	0.079
		16	-0.047	-0.026	24.137	0.087
		17	0.018	0.031	24.272	0.112
		18	-0.017	-0.035	24.394	0.143
		19	0.002	0.027	24.396	0.181
		20	-0.104	-0.122	28.828	0.091
		21	-0.000	0.058	28.828	0.118
		22	-0.061	-0.100	30.352	0.110
		23	-0.017	0.012	30.472	0.136
		24	0.086	0.096	33.546	0.093
		25	0.009	-0.042	33.581	0.117
		26	-0.068	-0.037	35.500	0.101
		27	0.024	0.017	35.732	0.121
		28	-0.063	-0.077	37.412	0.110
		29	0.027	0.053	37.709	0.129
		30	0.020	-0.000	37.871	0.153
		31	0.048	0.039	38.841	0.157
		32	0.032	0.042	39.281	0.176
		33	-0.009	-0.036	39.318	0.208
		34	-0.001	0.008	39.319	0.244
		35	0.049	0.028	40.364	0.245
		36	0.017	0.005	40.486	0.279

Source: Author's calculation using EViews 12 Student Version.

APPENDIX VIII

PARAMETER ESTIMATIONS OF CANDIDATE ARIMA MODELS

Dependent Variable: D(LJKSE)
Method: ARMA Maximum Likelihood (OPG - BHHH)
Date: 12/24/22 Time: 03:52
Sample: 1990M06 2021M12
Included observations: 379
Convergence achieved after 21 iterations
Coefficient covariance computed using outer product of gradients

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.002691	0.002070	1.300154	0.1943
AR(1)	-0.105722	0.190285	-0.555598	0.5788
MA(1)	0.318822	0.181441	1.757164	0.0797
SIGMASQ	0.000981	4.24E-05	23.13340	0.0000
R-squared	0.044114	Mean dependent var		0.002693
Adjusted R-squared	0.036666	S.D. dependent var		0.032072
S.E. of regression	0.031479	Akaike info criterion		-4.068649
Sum squared resid	0.381502	Schwarz criterion		-4.027892
Log likelihood	795.3522	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-4.052491
F-statistic	5.922634	Durbin-Watson stat		2.000912
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000587			
Inverted AR Roots	-.11			
Inverted MA Roots	-.32			

Notes:

1. Autoregressive and moving average components of the ARIMA (1,1,1) model are not significant.
2. Based on the ARIMA (1,1,1) model's parameter estimation results, the model is not suitable to forecast the JKSE monthly price.

Source: Author's calculation using EViews 12 Student Version.

APPENDIX VIII

PARAMETER ESTIMATIONS OF CANDIDATE ARIMA MODELS (CONTINUED)

Dependent Variable: D(LJKSE)
 Method: ARMA Maximum Likelihood (OPG - BHHH)
 Date: 12/24/22 Time: 03:56
 Sample: 1990M06 2021M12
 Included observations: 379
 Convergence achieved after 25 iterations
 Coefficient covariance computed using outer product of gradients

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.002810	0.001960	1.434032	0.1524
AR(1)	0.200906	0.035682	5.630408	0.0000
MA(20)	-0.117189	0.040104	-2.922103	0.0037
SIGMASQ	0.000973	4.24E-05	22.95297	0.0000
R-squared	0.051780	Mean dependent var		0.002693
Adjusted R-squared	0.044391	S.D. dependent var		0.032072
S.E. of regression	0.031352	Akaike info criterion		-4.076011
Sum squared resid	0.378442	Schwarz criterion		-4.035255
Log likelihood	796.7842	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-4.059854
F-statistic	7.007914	Durbin-Watson stat		1.963214
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000134			
Inverted AR Roots	.20			
Inverted MA Roots	.90	.85+.28i	.85-.28i	.73-.53i
	.73+.53i	.53-.73i	.53+.73i	.28+.85i
	.28-.85i	.00-.90i	-.00+.90i	-.28+.85i
	-.28-.85i	-.53+.73i	-.53-.73i	-.73-.53i
	-.73+.53i	-.85-.28i	-.85+.28i	-.90

Notes:

- Autoregressive and moving average components of the ARIMA (1,1,20) model are significant.
- Parameter estimation results indicate that the model is able to forecast the JKSE monthly price. However, the model's statistics of adjusted R-squared and Akaike information criterion are not the most preferable among the candidate models, thus, the model will not be selected for forecast modeling.

Source: Author's calculation using EViews 12 Student Version.

APPENDIX VIII

PARAMETER ESTIMATIONS OF CANDIDATE ARIMA MODELS (CONTINUED)

Dependent Variable: D(LJKSE)
 Method: ARMA Maximum Likelihood (OPG - BHHH)
 Date: 12/24/22 Time: 04:12
 Sample: 1990M06 2021M12
 Included observations: 379
 Convergence achieved after 57 iterations
 Coefficient covariance computed using outer product of gradients

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.002767	0.001736	1.594192	0.1117
AR(20)	-0.755653	0.228957	-3.300411	0.0011
MA(20)	0.679386	0.248285	2.736311	0.0065
SIGMASQ	0.001012	4.50E-05	22.49152	0.0000
R-squared	0.013849	Mean dependent var	0.002693	
Adjusted R-squared	0.006165	S.D. dependent var	0.032072	
S.E. of regression	0.031973	Akaike info criterion	-4.036328	
Sum squared resid	0.393581	Schwarz criterion	-3.995571	
Log likelihood	789.0657	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-4.020170	
F-statistic	1.802295	Durbin-Watson stat	1.601282	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.146232			
Inverted AR Roots	.97-.15i	.97+.15i	.88+.45i	.88-.45i
	.70-.70i	.70+.70i	.45-.88i	.45+.88i
	.15-.97i	.15+.97i	-.15-.97i	-.15+.97i
	-.45-.88i	-.45+.88i	-.70-.70i	-.70+.70i
	-.88-.45i	-.88+.45i	-.97+.15i	-.97-.15i
Inverted MA Roots	.97-.15i	.97+.15i	.87+.45i	.87-.45i
	.69+.69i	.69-.69i	.45-.87i	.45+.87i
	.15-.97i	.15+.97i	-.15+.97i	-.15-.97i
	-.45-.87i	-.45+.87i	-.69-.69i	-.69+.69i
	-.87-.45i	-.87+.45i	-.97+.15i	-.97-.15i

Notes:

1. Autoregressive and moving average components of the ARIMA (20,1,20) model are significant.
2. Parameter estimation results indicate that the model is able to forecast the JKSE monthly price. Nevertheless, the model will not be selected due to its statistics of adjusted R-squared and Akaike information criterion that are not the most preferable among the candidate models.

Source: Author's calculation using EViews 12 Student Version.

APPENDIX VIII

PARAMETER ESTIMATIONS OF CANDIDATE ARIMA MODELS (CONTINUED)

Dependent Variable: D(LJKSE)
 Method: ARMA Maximum Likelihood (OPG - BHHH)
 Date: 12/24/22 Time: 04:02
 Sample: 1990M06 2021M12
 Included observations: 379
 Convergence achieved after 27 iterations
 Coefficient covariance computed using outer product of gradients

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.002808	0.001922	1.461128	0.1448
AR(20)	-0.124547	0.040067	-3.108475	0.0020
MA(1)	0.231479	0.034751	6.661095	0.0000
SIGMASQ	0.000966	4.27E-05	22.60361	0.0000
R-squared	0.058283	Mean dependent var		0.002693
Adjusted R-squared	0.050945	S.D. dependent var		0.032072
S.E. of regression	0.031245	Akaike info criterion		-4.082765
Sum squared resid	0.375847	Schwarz criterion		-4.042008
Log likelihood	798.0978	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-4.066607
F-statistic	7.942523	Durbin-Watson stat		2.018390
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000038			
Inverted AR Roots	.89+.14i .64-.64i .14-.89i -.41-.80i -.80-.41i	.89-.14i .64+.64i .14+.89i -.41+.80i -.80+.41i	.80-.41i .41-.80i -.14-.89i -.64-.64i -.89+.14i	.80+.41i .41+.80i -.14+.89i -.64+.64i -.89-.14i
Inverted MA Roots	-.23			

Notes:

1. Autoregressive and moving average components of the ARIMA (20,1,1) model are significant.
2. Parameter estimation results indicate that the model is most fitting to the data. The model will be selected to forecast the JKSE monthly price due to its; adjusted R-squared statistics that is the largest; and Akaike information criterion that is the least; among all candidate models.

Source: Author's calculation using EViews 12 Student Version.

APPENDIX IX

FORECAST PERFORMANCE OF CANDIDATE ARIMA MODELS

Notes:

1. The results of forecast errors are based on the ARIMA (1,1,20) modeling of the training samples to produce forecast samples in the testing period.
2. The model is not selected to project forecasts of JKSE monthly price due to the mean absolute error (MAE) and mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) values that are not the smallest compared to other candidate models.

Source: Author's calculation using EViews 12 Student Version.

APPENDIX IX

FORECAST PERFORMANCE OF CANDIDATE ARIMA MODELS (CONTINUED)

Notes:

1. The forecast errors are based on the ARIMA (20,1,20) modeling of the training samples to produce forecast samples in the testing period.
2. The model is not chosen to project forecasts of JKSE monthly price due to the mean absolute error (MAE) and mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) values that are not the smallest compared to other candidate models.

Source: Author's calculation using EViews 12 Student Version.

APPENDIX IX

FORECAST PERFORMANCE OF CANDIDATE ARIMA MODELS (CONTINUED)

Notes:

1. The forecast errors are based on the ARIMA (20,1,1) modeling of the training samples to produce forecast samples in the testing period.
2. Based on the mean absolute error (MAE) and mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) values of the ARIMA (20,1,1) forecasting model that are the least among all candidate models, the model is pursued to forecast the projections of JKSE monthly price for the testing period.

Source: Author's calculation using EViews 12 Student Version.

APPENDIX X

CORRELOGRAM OF ARIMA(20,1,1) AUTOCORRELATION TEST

Date: 08/27/23 Time: 20:23

Sample: 1990M05 2021M12

Included observations: 379

Q-statistic probabilities adjusted for 2 ARMA terms

Autocorrelation	Partial Correlation	AC	PAC	Q-Stat	Prob	
		1	-0.009	-0.009	0.0325	
		2	-0.045	-0.045	0.7986	
		3	0.006	0.005	0.8130	0.367
		4	0.059	0.057	2.1354	0.344
		5	-0.043	-0.041	2.8353	0.418
		6	0.020	0.024	2.9906	0.559
		7	-0.058	-0.062	4.2842	0.509
		8	-0.012	-0.014	4.3415	0.631
		9	-0.045	-0.046	5.1247	0.645
		10	0.068	0.064	6.9332	0.544
		11	-0.040	-0.036	7.5760	0.577
		12	0.000	0.003	7.5761	0.670
		13	0.028	0.030	7.8764	0.724
		14	0.014	0.000	7.9502	0.789
		15	-0.080	-0.068	10.462	0.656
		16	-0.033	-0.046	10.900	0.694
		17	0.040	0.039	11.530	0.714
		18	-0.037	-0.044	12.077	0.739
		19	0.027	0.045	12.366	0.777
		20	0.002	-0.009	12.367	0.828
		21	0.050	0.058	13.361	0.820
		22	-0.067	-0.071	15.182	0.766
		23	-0.016	-0.029	15.283	0.808
		24	0.092	0.091	18.740	0.661
		25	0.000	-0.007	18.740	0.716
		26	-0.074	-0.050	20.993	0.639
		27	0.043	0.027	21.761	0.650
		28	-0.089	-0.083	24.994	0.519
		29	0.050	0.051	26.026	0.517
		30	0.005	-0.003	26.037	0.571
		31	0.035	0.029	26.556	0.596
		32	0.016	0.047	26.666	0.641
		33	-0.002	-0.021	26.667	0.689
		34	-0.010	-0.012	26.705	0.732
		35	0.045	0.040	27.550	0.735
		36	-0.006	0.010	27.568	0.774

Source: Author's calculation using EViews 12 Student Version.

APPENDIX XI

BREUSCH-PAGAN-GODFREY HETEROSKEDASTICITY TEST OF THE RESIDUALS

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

F-statistic	39.12152	Prob. F(2,376)	0.5893
Obs*R-squared	65.56165	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.4960
Scaled explained SS	205.4710	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.9975

Test Equation:

Dependent Variable: RESID^2

Method: Least Squares

Date: 12/24/22 Time: 02:29

Sample: 1990M06 2021M12

Included observations: 379

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.018703	0.023886	-0.783004	0.4593
RESIDLJKSEAR20	0.003942	0.007734	0.509732	0.6259
RESIDLJKSEMA1	0.000967	0.002729	0.354408	0.7335
R-squared	0.168539	Mean dependent var		0.000966
Adjusted R-squared	0.164231	S.D. dependent var		0.002447
S.E. of regression	0.002237	Akaike info criterion		-15.51342
Sum squared resid	0.001932	Schwarz criterion		-15.42265
Log likelihood	1823.411	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-15.61300
F-statistic	39.12152	Durbin-Watson stat		2.559059
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Author's calculation using EViews 12 Student Version.

APPENDIX XII

ARIMA PROCESS INVERTIBILITY OF ARIMA(20,1,1) MODEL

Inverse Roots of AR/MA Polynomial(s)
 Specification: D(LJKSE) C AR(20) MA(1)
 Date: 01/09/24 Time: 11:47
 Sample: 1990M05 2021M12
 Included observations: 379

AR Root(s)	Modulus	Cycle
0.637165 ± 0.637165i	0.901087	8.000000
-0.802874 ± 0.409085i	0.901087	2.352941
-0.637165 ± 0.637165i	0.901087	2.666667
-0.409085 ± 0.802874i	0.901087	3.076923
0.409085 ± 0.802874i	0.901087	5.714286
-0.140961 ± 0.889993i	0.901087	3.636364
0.140961 ± 0.889993i	0.901087	4.444444
0.802874 ± 0.409085i	0.901087	13.333333
0.889993 ± 0.140961i	0.901087	40.000000
-0.889993 ± 0.140961i	0.901087	2.105263

No root lies outside the unit circle.
 ARMA model is stationary.

MA Root(s)	Modulus	Cycle
-0.231479	0.231479	

No root lies outside the unit circle.
 ARMA model is invertible.

Source: Author's calculation using EViews 12 Student Version.

APPENDIX XIII

STATIC FORECAST PERFORMANCE OF ARIMA(20,1,1) MODEL

Notes:

The static forecast errors are based on the ARIMA (20,1,1) modeling of the training samples to produce static forecast samples in the testing period.

Based on the lower root mean square error (RMSE), lower mean absolute error (MAE), and lower mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) values of the selected ARIMA (20,1,1) model using static forecast compared to using dynamic forecast, the static forecast is consequently more preferred for the ARIMA(20,1,1) model because static forecast indicate higher accuracy of the projected outcomes.

Source: Author's calculation using EViews 12 Student Version